

**MINDUM: ACCOUNT OF YAMPHU ORIGIN AND
INDIGENEITY**

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Submitted by

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Letter of Recommendation

I certify that this M. Phil dissertation entitled *Mindum: Account of Yamphu Origin and Indigeneity* has been written by Mr. Hom Prasad Rai under my constant guidance and supervision. The research scholar has, in regular consultation with me, also made necessary revisions in it by incorporating my appropriate comments and suggestions. In my opinion, it is now satisfactory in scope and quality as a dissertation for the degree of M. Phil in Anthropology. I, therefore, strongly recommend the dissertation for the approval and acceptance by the Tribhuvan University.

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APPROVAL AND ACCEPTANCE LETTER

We, the undersigned, certify that we have read this dissertation and that, in our opinion, it is satisfactory in scope and quality as a dissertation for the degree of M. Phil. in Anthropology. The candidate has successfully defended his dissertation during the *viva voce*.

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Dedication

To my beloved wife Manju and our sons Appy and Ayush

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ABSTRACT

This dissertation examines *mindum* and its political-religious and cultural dimensions. In this study I argue that *mindum* is the knowledge of the past that forms Yamphu ideology; it explains the origins of man and the universe; it encodes the basic cultural themes, ancestral values, and propositions of the society; it evokes a spiritual attachment to the lands and offers Yamphu a means of establishing and maintaining relationships with ancestors and lands.

The central idea is that *mindum* gives Yamphu a capacity to transform themselves as sovereign people to the land. I argue that *mindum* provides Yamphu with an ideological ground to legitimize their identity, to exercise sovereign power over the territory, and to conceptualize their territoriality as ancestral land- “we emerged from here.” Yamphu spatialize their identity as *jimi-bhumi* into the present landscape through *pellam*. It is a key way of inscribing ancestral past into the landscape that in turn gives Yamphu a *sense of sovereign people* to claim rights to the land. Such understating of making sense of indigeneity, place and territoriality through oral tradition is essential to understanding the relationship between land, people and identity in Nepal.

Chapter One

INTRODUCTION

My long standing desire to study my own community encouraged me to pursue this study. I had long felt a special sense of responsibility that comes precisely from my membership to my community. Here, I would like to discuss some humors and beliefs attached to *mindum* and its cultural specificities and peculiarities embedded with it.

Before I undertook the study of *mindum* – oral tradition (sometimes Yamphu refer *mindum* as analogous to *pellam*, but I use both the terms as required by context they fit it), I frequently used to discuss with my mother, maternal uncle, Bhim Bahadur Gaurung and other Yamphu elders about *mindum*, its significance for Yamphu culture and its present status. Knowing my desire to explore *mindum*, my mother often made me aware of the fact that recording *mindum* and *pellam* is not an easy task. She told me about the difficulties and complexities that I might face while recording *mindum* and *pellam*. She also made me aware of the possible consequences of recording *them*. In fact, she seemed little worried about my research as I might be punished by concerned divinities for exposing them publicly.

Among Yamphu, *pellam* is the thing which is neither talked about much nor communicated openly because they considered it highly sacred and adored. According to Yamphu, *pellam* needs to be expressed and communicated only in Yamphu mother tongue. Otherwise the sacred words may lose their evocative power as it is believed that the ancestors cannot understand the chanting. On the other hand, the words and metaphors used in *mindum* greatly vary from ordinary Yamphu language. Therefore, people who want to learn *pellam* need a great dedication and a very good language command. Hearing all these made me understand how challenging my research would be but I became more enthusiastic and determined in exploring *mindum* and *pellam*.

My mother said, "We no longer have Yamphu elders with good knowledge of *mindum* like there used to be in the past." However, she indicated that there might be some elder and suggested me that the elders from Hedangna who might know *mindum* better than people from an elsewhere. But, the problem was that people who know *mindum* in bit or more most of the times do not put themselves forward as knowing correct and complete *mindum*. The unwillingness of them to tell *mindum* has bearing on the fact that they do not know the complete *mindum* and they think there would be some people who would know more about *mindum*. Or simply, *mindum* experts are reluctant to pass on such knowledge because access to such knowledge is generally restricted to certain persons, and institutionalized through the definition of priestly categories (Gaenszle, 2002:16). Another reason may be because of its political nature which is one of the main objectives of this dissertation.

If we talk about Yamphu culture, the people Yamphu have many legends and local stories attached to *mindum* and *pellam*. For instance, they believe that people who chant *pellam* without a proper way of learning or in depth knowledge may go mad. The *pellam* must be chanted solely in Yamphu language and a failure to incomplete acquisition may threat wellbeing of the person or even threat his or her life. Such dispositions embedded with *mindum* were sure to make *mindum* recording more challenging. My maternal uncle Bhim Bahadur told me:

Long ago, may be five or six generation ago, there was a female Yamphu from *kesha* clan. She possessed very good knowledge of *pellam*. It is said that when she chanted *pellam* she had power to make the tips of two bamboo poles which were horizontally erected meters apart join together. With the same power, she could make the tips once joined together, would fall apart. But today we cannot find such people who can chant *pellam* like that. *Pellam* has lost its originality and hence its power. An expert *pellamdang* can even lead the soul of a dead person who has died of unnatural death, for example, a person died of in an accident.

(Field note, 2012)

Therefore, Yamphu believe that a *pellamdangba* can even control over a *mangba* (shaman) through the power of *pellam*. He or she can teach a *mangba*, and can point out mistakes made by *mangba*. A *mangba* may not be able to call his guru (deities) in his night performance if a *pellamdangba* wish to control the *mangba* by posing obstacles to his way of ritual performance. In this regard, I have an incident narrated by one of my informants, Tek Bahadur Yamphu, from Seduwa. He told me:

When I reached the house where the *mangba* was to perform, the *mangba*'s *bewaring* (dholes) were setting up the altar. When they finished their work and set up the altar, the *mangba* got ready for the night performance, wore all his apparel, his bead necklaces and a waist band of bells, and washing (a head -dress made up of feathers). Then he took his seat and began to chant *mindum* by beating the *dhyangro* (drum). But to the astonishment of all of those who were present, the priest was not able to shiver and tremble. *Deutai ayena* (the shaman could not call his guru).

The *mangba* tried and tried again, he tried his best; he began to feel something has done wrong and feel uneasy as he was not being able to call his *guru*. *Mangba* seemed restless, but still again tried to being the process again, but all went vain. He shouted, "What is happening today?" He again tried to begin the process, but all went in vein. Finally, pressing his both hands together (Namaste 'N'), he turned towards his audiences, and bow them saying, "Among you, there must be one, may be *pellamdangba*, *sakmiyongba*, or *lekhuba* (knowledgeable persons). Forgive me if I have failed to pay due respect to you unknowingly." He further pleaded and said, "Forgive me if I happen to make any mistake. With all my reverence, I request you to come forward."

This event made the spectators feel amazed. People who had come to see the night performance wondered, and started to look each other in suspicion. Everyone was looking for such a person among themselves. A middle aged man stood and shouted, "Who could be such a person, among us?" While almost all the spectators were in confusion, suddenly we noticed an old person sitting at the corner; quiet and calm. He was wearing a shawl. He sat there pointing his eyes towards the floor as if he were unaware of all these happenings. Some of us talked about his silence. After a while, the *mangba* got up, went to the old man, and bowed him. Then the old man admitted what he had done. He threw some *akchhyata* (uncooked rice kernels). After that everything became normal. The *mangba* started to sake and tremble this time as he was able to call his *guru*. For the first time, in my life, I witnessed such a scenario and actually realized the power of *pellamdangba*. But to our bad luck, the old man died a few years back. Today, I am feeling bad. If I would have recorded the *mindum* of that person and I could have preserved his knowledge which could be very important and precious for all of us.

(Field note, 2012)

Such ethnographic statements and narratives are of the prime focus of my study because in those narratives, people express their local concept of *mindum* and *pellam*. Such

folk narratives are considered, in Malinowskian term "a corpus of *inscriptionum*" (1922: 24) as *mindmu* is supposed to be the primary factor that shapes Yamphu world view. Previous studies of Rai mythologies carried out by some scholars have shown that Kirat mythology is the totality of Kirat identity and religion (Hardman, 2000; Gaenzle, 2000; Nicolette, 2006; Gaenzle and Ebert, 2008, and Allen, 2012). For instance, in the case of Lohorung Rai, Hardman contends that "*pe-lam* is central to the Lohorung sense of identity, continuity, and their psychological and physical well-beings" (2000:109). Lohourng is considered to be very close clan brother of Yamphu. Yamphu and Lohorung have many common cultural practices and world view. In fact, they do not see any difference between them.

Such anthropological studies about Rai Kirati myths and oral tradition show a link between *mindum* and human thought process. However, contemporary anthropological studies have moved beyond literary and psychological analysis of myths and oral tradition to explore their socio-historical and political values in preserving the memory of important experiences.

This study is the ethnographic study of oral traditions known as *mindum* of Yamphu who are one of the eastern Kirati groups of upper Arun valley, eastern Nepal. The *mindum* tradition is well known and practiced among the eastern Kirati groups. *Mindum* tradition is common for all Kirati cultures. It is taken as a sacred corpus of knowledge about the ancestral past. Such knowledge is expressed in different forms such as *pellam*, oral histories, narratives and myths. This study aims to investigate how *pellam* as the story of ancestral past "connects the past and the present by literally mapping the space between them" (Blackburn, 2003/04:17). In so doing, I have examined how the sacredness of *mindum* constitutes the foundation of a spiritual tie with their land and territory and thus, a *sense of place* and belongingness. I have also examined the political-religious dimensions of *mindum* through

which how Yamphu establish and legitimize the sovereignty over their territory and resources attached to it.

1.1.The Yamphu

Yamphu represent one of the Kirati groups of Nepal. The Kirati are "many-tongued" people (Hodgson 1885:447) which constitute groups like Kulung, Chamling, Limbu, Sunuwar, and Bantawa and so on. Yamphu has been reported as a separate Kirati group only in the census of 2011. For several decades, they have been subsumed under the ethnonym "Rai" as a linguistic group. However, the census report shows the total Yamphu population and Yamphu language speakers were recorded as 6,933 and 9,208 respectively (CBS, 2012). The cause of the inconsistency in the number of population and speakers might be thought that some Yamphu reported "Rai" as their ethnic name and language. For several decades, they have been subsumed under the ethnonym "Rai" as a linguistic group. It is evident that "Rai" has only in recent history come to be an ethnonym (Gaenszle, 2000; Russell, 1992). As a result, Yamphus are one of the very least known groups across the country, be it in historical documents, recent ethnographic writings or even among the diverse Kirati groups. Borrowing Eric Wolf's (1982) words they have become somewhat like "people without history".

However, now days, Yamphu are averse to use "Rai" as their ethnonym. They prefer being considered Yamphu or *yakhaba* which is the more correct denomination of the group. The Yamphu identify themselves as *yakhaba* and call their language as *yakhaba khap*. Yamphus are autochthonous inhabitants of upper Arun valley of Sankhuwasabha district. Historically, this region falls under Pallo Kirat.

Lohorung and Yakkha who are also the Kirati groups of the upper Arun valley are close brother clan groups of Yamphu. They share some linguistic and cultural affinities with

each other (Yamphu, 2007:34). For instance, Lohorung and Yamphu use a similar autonym *yakkhaba* to denote themselves. They have same clan groups such as *ketra* and *rangbisong*. Similarly, Yakkha also call themselves *yakkhaba* (Russell, 1992:98).

If we look back to history, Yamphu as a *kipat* holder enjoyed their cultural autonomy even after their subjugation and integration into the Hindu Kingdom from Gorkhali kings (Forbes, 1996). The Gorkhali king granted *kipat*- traditional form of land-tenure that recognized customary rights to the land. Yamphu used to occupy these areas under *kipat* tenure by virtue of being "first settlers". Numerous linguistic relics and landmarks still bear witness of the period in which the Yamphu are the first settlers in their territory (Yamphu, 2012). The *kipat* was the basis of cultural autonomy of Yamphu. *Kipta* seemed as a symbol of ethnic and political identity among the Yamphu (Yamphu, 2007).

The *kipat* system was put to an end with the introduction of Land Act in 2022 B. S. Dissolution of *kipat* resulted as symbolic obliteration of Yamphu from the landscape because it resulted in removal from its history, memory and representation. In the case of Limbu of eastern Nepal, to whom Yamphu consider a brother group, Caplan noted that "Kipat is fused with and articulates the culture, and any assault on Kipat is seen a threat to the very existence of the Limbu as a separate community within the society" (2007 [1970]: 174) By the abolition of *kipat*, the state undermined and destroyed the local system of power and authority to legitimize and authorized the alien power. Consequently, the Yamphu lost their sovereignty over their land and resources. The loss of *kipat*, in turn, marginalized them in socially, economically, culturally and politically.

Yamphu have well practiced oral tradition known as *mindum* which is the centrality of their traditional way of life. However, today, it is not well-remembered and has no written form. Their traditional life is based on *ancestor worship*. Hodgson has rightly noted that "They (Kirati) have no name for the God of gods" (Hodgson, 1885:451). Unlike other groups

of Nepal whose religion is based on the faith of God (s) and goddesses, Yamphu seems to have no concept of God or the Gods. What they believe is in their ancestors who are the first human and believed to have become like gods and constantly live among them and support them in their existence. Ancestors are more powerful than real humans to whom they are bound by an ancestral debt. They believe that ancestors gave them everything – land, wisdom, and so on. Therefore, they owe respect, obedience, and gratitude which Yamphu most often express through their oral tradition - *mindum*.

Yamphu believe that their ancestors and evil spirits are able to influence the health and prosperity of people, the bounty of the harvest, the fertility of cattle, and the harmony of the community. They have faith in ancestors and supernatural beings and believe that they control over various aspects of the cosmos and explain causality, including accidents, sicknesses, death and incomprehensible phenomena. Yamphu *mindum*, offerings and sacrifice serve as the main vehicle of Yamphu to maintain their link with their ancestors. They are the primary means for balancing and adjusting the relationship between human, ancestors and supernatural beings. Each type of ancestors and supernatural being is associated with certain location and a particular power to affect the lives of the living. Yamphu thus have special knowledge to deal with their ancestors and supernatural beings. This knowledge can be termed as *mindum*.

Disappointingly, for a number of reasons *mindum* is being gradually eroded away and it is almost on the verge of extinction. The Yamphu elders admit that ritual performance has lost its originality and has come to remain merely as a formality in the recent times as never before. *Mindum* is sacred oral text. It is enigmatical. Therefore, transforming *mindum* to young people is not easy and not being possible. New generation or adult speakers are not learning *mindum*.

In addition to this, the state's hostile policies (such as one language, one culture, one dress) pressured many indigenous communities to give up their languages and even ethnic and cultural identity in the past (Lawati, 2005; and Gurung, 2006). It is well known that historical processes of Hindunaization has caused in the progressive decay of *mindum* (Gaenzle 200:223; Nicolette 2006). Nepali Khas language, the national lingua franca, is rapidly supplanting many indigenous languages. Yamphu language is one of the endangered languages of Nepal (Yamphu 2007; Yadav and Turin, 2005).

1.2.The Study of the Oral Tradition

In his article entitled, *The Historical Development of Himalayan Anthropology*, James F. Fisher's (1985), contends that Furer-Himaindrof's works on Newar, High Hindu castes, Tamang and Sherpas in 1950s marked the beginning ground-breaking anthropological activities of modern anthropology of Nepal. By the 1960s, the native sociologists and anthropologists, for instance, G.S. Nepali's (1965) *The Newars* and Bista's (1969) *The People of Nepal* started to study their own societies. The decade of 1970s, witnessed unprecedented anthropological research works in Nepal (Fisher, 1985). In Fisher's view, the anthropological foci of Nepal are religion, social structure, ecology, village studies, development and women. By the 1980s, anthropology in Nepal flourished and covered every branch of anthropology and expanded exponentially (1985: 105). Since 1990s, ethnicity, federalism, identity politics and indigenous peoples' struggles for rights claims have been highly contested issues of public debate in Nepal. Then, anthropologists and other social scientists have increasingly turned their attentions to these issues (Hangen 2010; Lawati, 2014; Gellner 1997 and others).

As concerned with anthropological studies of oral traditions, in Gaenzle's view, it began since mid-seventy in Nepal. Regarding the Kirati oral tradition, very few studies have been conducted (Gaenzle, 1992b). The Kirat people of eastern Nepal have considerable

linguistic diversity and oral traditions. Some comprehensive scholarly works of western scholars (Allen, 2012; Hardman, 2000; Gaenzle, 2000; Nicolette, 2006) and non-western scholars (Chemjong, 1965) about Kirat oral tradition gives us some bright insights into the nature and structure of *mindum* tradition. *Mindum* tradition is a common feature among all Kirati cultures. Kirati *mindum* demonstrates a common theme: the historical continuity of each group in the present territory (Gaenzle, 2000:224). This tradition has been instrumental for an expression of cultural heritage or an instrument for installation of indigeneity. These studies about Kirati oral texts reveal that oral tradition among Kirati people is to install indigeneity and instrumental for an expression of their cultural heritage.

In case of Yamphu, Rutgers (1998:6) rightly says: "Society and economic life, in fact nearly every aspect of daily life, is thoroughly intertwined with the tradition of ancestor worship." They believe that their ancestors, nature gods, spirits, and ghosts are able to influence the health of people, the success of the clan, the bounty of the harvest, the fertility of cattle, and the harmony of the community. Yamphu believe in ancestors and supernatural beings that control various aspects of the cosmos and explain causality, including accidents, sicknesses, death and incomprehensible phenomena. Yamphu rituals serve as the main vehicle to maintain link to their ancestors. They are the primary means for balancing and adjusting the relationship between human, ancestors and supernatural beings. Each type of ancestors and supernatural being is associated with a certain location and a particular power to affect the lives of the living. Yamphu people thus have special knowledge to deal with their ancestors and supernatural beings. This knowledge can be termed as *mindum*.

Such instrumental and cultural heritage was to be explored with the study of Imansing who was the first indigenous scholars who studied oral text. Chemjong's (1967) book entitled, *The History and Culture of the Kirat People* is considered as the first book that deals particularly with Limbu *mundhum*. Chemjong's main emphasis was to explain religious

aspect of *mundhum*. He (1967: 21) asserts that "*mindum* means the power of strength and the Kirati people of east Nepal believe it to be true, holy, and powerful scripture." However, he has not described why Limbu and Kirat people consider *mundhum* so. Therefore, his book is mere a description of various religious functions of *mundhum*.

Yamphu consider Lohorung and Mewahang as their close clan groups. In the case of Lohorung, Charlotte Hardman (2000) has produced a comprehensive monograph on Lohorung Rai of Pangma village. In her book, "Other World: Notions of Self and Emotion among the Lohorung Rai," Hardman has suggested that terms *mundum* and *pe-lam* are used interchangeably among Lohorung Rai. In this study, she was more interested to explore ethnopsychology of Lohorung individuals and groups. This type of concern has focused in particular on the effects of *sammang* (*dewa 'N'*), *pe-lam* and ritual texts in terms of the development of psychological orientation towards social worldview. In so doing, she (2000:104) has seen *pe-lam* as the knowledge of the past for the present and writes: "*Pe-lam*, in terms of content, includes those Lohorung customs, habits, traditions, rituals, and myths ... the *pe-lam* gives the Lohorung cultural identity and unity." She has also discussed the significance of *chawa* and *samek* in relation to territorial association of Lohorung clan groups. However, she has paid little attention on what legitimatizes a particular Lohorung clan group's claim over a particular territory.

Another important study of ritual text comes from Martin Gaenzle in Mewahang Rai. Gaenzle has published the first ritual text oriented study on the ritual texts- *mindum* of the Mewahang Rai. In this study, Gaenzle has also focused on religious aspects of Mewahang *mindum*, and elaborated the significance of *mindum* in maintaining Mewahang indigeneity. For instance, Gaenzle (2002:21) states, "Even today, *mundum* continues to be the essential to their identity, and something of which they proud of." Like Hardman, Gaenzle also finds that the *muddum* of Mewahang as complex notion of mythic past which is being intrinsically

linked to the present. In similar vein, studying Thulung mythology, Allen (2012) asserts that Thulung take *diumla* as great pride in their tradition. He argues that *diumla* distinguishes Thulung from their non-Kirati neighbors, forming the base of their identity. In relation to Yamphu *mindum*, Ann Forbes (1999:84) has discussed, to some extent, the political aspects of Yamphu *mindum* in relation to land *kipat*, and concludes that *mindum* delineates Yamphu ancestral territory in the present land.

The literature discussed above shows that mostly they focused on religious aspects and the importance of oral text in maintaining ethnic identity. *Mindum* is considered primarily a religious-functional requisite of society. However, these studies have inadequately analyzed political aspects of the oral text that define and legitimize a certain group's sovereignty over a territory signifying their internal differences, conflict and politics. The analysis of previous studies on oral text reveals that they have overlooked how oral text serves political-religious purposes above and beyond the simple aesthetic and religious values. Significantly, earlier studies have not explored how *mindum* as sacred knowledge reflects the power relations of the distinct positions in a hierarchy, in the political-religious totality of an indigenous peoples' society.

1.3.The Statement of the Research Problem

Local narratives I presented above little help to exemplify Yamphu concept of *mindum* and *pellam*. Such statements also indicate that *mindum* and *pellam* is being eroded and have lost its originality and thus, power. For this reason, ethnographic study and recording of oral traditions of Yamphu have become as an urgent task. Moreover, recent development communication media, modern education and social change in rural areas have caused irreversible disappearance and a radical transformation in transmission of oral traditions. Such local histories and cultures founded on these legends are rapidly dying out or

being absorbed into groups with more alien (Hindu and Christian) culture. It is, therefore, imperative that anthropologists record these cultures before they are lost forever.

Moreover our research studies must not only be confined within the purely academic practices, but also should focus on oral tradition that would help better understand the functioning of oral traditions in contemporary society. Since memories of the past, what Africanists call "indigenous past" (Tonkin, 1986:203), is transmitted by oral tradition, the ethnographic study of them is of the greatest importance in tracing out the local histories hitherto not recognized by the modern Nepali history. It should be noted that such endeavor will also add to the knowledge and understanding of Nepali society. Anthropologists have well accepted that tribal groups have a lot to offer to the world. Therefore, it is argued that to ignore indigenous peoples' local histories as cultural construction is "like burning the library before we read the book" (Thornberry, 2002:21). Oral traditions is "making history" Gaenzle (2003/04). To my knowledge, anthropologists and historians have done very little in this field in Nepal.

If we talk about the historiography of Nepal, it is seen that "the official history of Nepal was for long time only the genealogy of ruling dynasties, and mainly it focused on national unification" (Schlemmer, 2003/04: 119). Here I remember Ranajit Guha's remarks on Indian history. He is of the opinion that Indian history does not represent subaltern as it has been written by the elite, about the elite, and for the elite and by definition and intent in the process has ignored everyone else the contribution made by the people, on their own and developmental scenarios (Guha, 1988). Likewise, according to Willy Kymlica, a political scientist, "liberal-democratic states have been nation-building because they attempted to integrate all the citizens especially ethnocultural minorities into common public institutions operating in a common language through citizenship and natural laws, education laws, linguistic laws, policies regarding public service employment, military service and so on"

(2001:2). As a result, the ethnocultural minorities have only three options: either they accept to be integrated into common institutions and seek help in doing so, or they can try to build or maintain their own common institutions, or they can opt simply to be marginalized permanently (Kimlyca, 2001:27-28).

Nepali history is the history of nation-state which to use Gaenszle (2003/04:13), "leaves no room for local identity." Harka Gurung writes, "History is the construction of the conquerors while the vanquished are left only with bitter memories. The present Nepalese history is also the story about rulers and their legitimacy" (2003:14). Consequently, since the late 18th century, Gurung argues that, "a Hindu theocracy became the state ideology by suppressing ethnic identities in order to consolidate and centralize power" (2003:4-5). Therefore, Martin Gaenszle contends that "the memory of the past is not the privilege of professional (or semi-professional) historians, and there is a broad field of more localized "indigenous" genres of history-making that exists alongside the dominant discourse, complementing, ignoring, (creatively) misunderstanding, and – often – countering the latter" (2003/04:7).

The oral tradition that can be found among the Kirati groups has been expropriated in their own indigenous terms such as Yamphu- *mindum*, Lohorung- *mundum or pe-lam* (Hardman, 2000:103), Mewahang- *muddum* (Gaenszle 2008:05), Limbu- *mundhum* (Chemjon 1963 I: 18), Kulung- *riddum* (Nicolette 2006: 35), Thulung- *dumla*, Chamling – *rishiwa* (conversation with Bhogi Raj Chamling, April 16, 2014), Yakkha- *mutum* (Russell, 1995).

Ethnographic research on mythology and oral tradition has only recently begun in Nepal, especially by foreign researchers. Despite its short origin, they have been able to record the oral literatures from many indigenous groups. Some comprehensive scholarly works of western scholars (Hardman, 2000; Gaenszle, 2000; Nicolette, 2006; Gaenszle and

Ebert, 2008) and non-western scholars (Chemjong, 1965) about Kirat mythology have significantly contributed to broadening knowledge about oral tradition. An examination of these studies of myths and oral traditions of Kirat Rai groups reveals that they have, by and large, focused on religious aspects of oral traditions. They have mostly dealt with aesthetic and religious values of the mythologies, and have portrayed them as sacred texts. In the case of Lohorung and Mewahang Rai, Hardman (2000) and Gaenzle (2000) suggests that *mindum* evokes spiritual attachment of a particular clan group signifying as the first occupant of the territory attached to it. In the same way, *mindmu* as oral performance can be taken as remembering history in the present. Fage suggests that "oral tradition is often in reality an explanation, in quasi-historical or legendary terms, of existing or of currently relevant past social or socio-political relationships" (1954:16). For Vansina, "oral traditions are testimonies of past which are deliberately passed from mouth to mouth" (1960:45). In this sense, I see that *mindmu* has social- political implication which provide philosophical ground for Yamphu to claim the first settlers that has played role in the production of social relations is unanswered. *Mindum* has a political dimension because it is used to define and legitimize a certain group's sovereignty over a territory signifying their internal difference, conflict and politics.

Previous works on oral traditions give inadequate attention on historical and political dimensions of oral tradition through which how a certain group identify themselves as an "indigenous group". Therefore, in this study, my aim is to go beyond the religious-functional analysis, to see how Yamphu society has conceived it. How *mindum* tradition has been instrumental for an expression of cultural heritage or an instrument for installation of indigeneity among Yamphu. It is clear from a survey of current literature that it is yet to study how *mindum* as corpus of knowledge emerge as sacred and thus legitimize the cosmic and social order of the society Godelier (1999).

As a member of Yamphu society, I have often heard that somebody who dares to chant *mindum* without proper knowledge will suffer from misfortune and will even go mad. A common notion strongly prevailed among Yamphu is that "Don't recite *paella*, (sometimes *mindum* and *paella* are used interchangeably) *asikhya?ye* (will lose mind and go mad)." This shows that *mindum* is considered sacred chant. In anthropology, it is well accepted that it is a "cultural phenomena" that explains social or social-political relationship of the past (Tokin 1986: 203). Therefore, religious and aesthetic values and meanings embedded with *mindum* seem to have some political-religious aspects which are still unexplored. Furthermore, it is not analyzed that how *mindum* chanting as remembering past has provided strong basis for different groups to claim to be the first settlers of Nepal. *Mindum* contains nothing more than the footprints of ancestors, the names of places they travelled in search of unsettled places. Therefore, *mindum* reflects the power relations in the political-religious totality of Yamphu society. Here, it is not hard to understand why *mindum* is sacred if we borrow Godelier's concept of "sacred".

Studying Baruya society, he (1999:171) has conceptualized "sacred" as a relationship and defines "...the sacred is a *certain type of relationship that humans entertain with the origin.....*" In such relations, as argued by him, real human are replaced with imaginary human. Argued from this perspective, *mindum*, as sacred knowledge, is an explanation of the origin of things, not only signifies the spiritual attachment of Yamphu in the present landscape, but beyond this, it creates supra Kirat identity (Limbu, Khombu and Yamphu, Lohorung, Mewahang, and others) to which Yamphu feel they belong to. From the above discussion, it becomes clear that some essential aspects of *mindum* have been unexplored and overlooked. Unlike previous studies, this study thus investigates not merely the social and religious functions of oral traditions but also their imaginary and symbolic components that constitute social relations, that organize real society; not merely so-called mythic and

psychological dimensions but also their political-religious aspects of *mindum* which provides foundation to make a claim as a first settlers of Nepal; and also how a certain group legitimizes their sovereignty over a territory signifying their internal differences, conflict and politics.

1.4. Research Questions and Objectives

Based on the above discussion, there are some issues which this study aims to address. First, I have examined the issues of inalienable relations of Yamphu with the land and territory. Patrick Thornberry suggests that in order to understand and conceptualize indigeneity, we need to examine four interwoven strands as important elements: association to particular place (all indigenous peoples have roots to somewhere); indigenous is synonymous with priori inhabitation- (we are here before you); original or first human to inhabit a territory; and distinctive societies- the diacritical marks of culture (Thornberry, 2002:37-39). In this study, I have considered these issues in depth. I have investigated what binds Yamphu individuals belonging to distinct kin groups to a particular place and territory? Or how Yamphu claim themselves as an indigenous group? What are the bases for asserting their rights over land (territory) and makes them feel sovereign people to exploit the resources attached to it. What legitimizes Yamphu claim of the sovereignty over a territory and resources as first settlers? What is the thing that brings a group of individuals together into a whole that adds to each individual an overarching and shared Yamphu identity?

Second issue is related with contemporary political context and *mindum* as local history. Anthropologists have argued that "the issues of identity are not merely theoretical concerns in people's lives rather it is historically multifaceted construction and lived reality" (Godelier 2009:12). Oral traditions have been used, with varying degrees of success, to compose history. In his book entitled *Oral Tradition as History* 1985, Vansina argues that

oral tradition is invaluable in the reconstruction of history, especially that of societies lacking in written documentary sources.

The expansion of global capitalism has powerfully affected both material condition and social consciousness of indigenous peoples and cultural and ethnic minorities (Turner, 2004). These new insights have come to work to conceptualize ethnicity and indigenous peoples' struggles for rights claims in different ways which have been highly contested issues of public debate in elsewhere. More than before, ethnic identities are being more solidified because the process of globalization is creating new spaces of interaction between local and global (Appudurai 2002; Lewellen 2002; Kimlyca 2001; Kearney 1995).

This is evident in Nepal since the Second Jana Andolan 2062-63. Identity politics and multiculturalism has been accompanied by new forms of activism in support of indigenous peoples. Discourses on indigenous peoples and their identity, ethnic identity and political autonomy are being more asserted in present day Nepal (Lawati 2013; Hangen, 2010). The discourses on ethnicity and nation building have taken new dimension and direction. Ethnic identity and political autonomy is being more asserted in the changed political context. Many indigenous groups have become more sensitized in their rights, and they have become more committed to their struggles for identity and local autonomy. They increasingly perceive the assertion of their traditional cultures and the maintenance of traditional ritual and social institutions as an integral part of their political resistance to the loss of their land, resources, and powers of self-determination. Indigenous people have become more aggressive and successful in asserting their collective rights. Indigenous peoples by making such courageous moves have, in turn, catalyzed the development of more politicized form of indigenous activism. As a consequence, culture and ethnic difference has become a basic principle of contemporary social and political life of present Nepal. In this context, this study examines the socio-political implications of *mindum* i.e. how Yamphu use *mindum* to assert their rights

and legitimizes their claims in the contemporary discourse of identity movement and federalism.

To answer these questions, the objectives of the study are:

1. to document and analyze the indigenous concept of *mindum* and its genres;
2. to explore how *mindum* serves to each Yamphu an overarching, shared identity distinct from other and;
3. to explore the political-religious aspects of *mindum*, that define and legitimate Yamphu sovereignty in the present landscape.

1.5.Theoretical Approach

Mindum as an oral tradition has endured for countless generations among the Yamphu. Basically, *mindum* speaks of ancestral actions/activities that are inscribed in physical environment of Yamphu. It is *mindum* through which Yamphu acquire a capacity to evoke sacred relations with ancestors, and thus, a *sense of place* and belongingness in the present territory. I use two theoretical propositions closely connected and complementary to each other but are not the same: anthropology of landscapes (Santos-Granero, 1998; Morphy, 1988; Basso 1988; Stewart and Strathern, 2003; Guo, 2003 and others) and the *social origin of sacred* advocated and advanced by Maurice Godelier (1999; 2009).

The concept of landscape provides an important analytical category for understanding the ways by which *mindum* inscribes Yamphu past history into the present landscape and hence produces a *Yamphu sense of place*. Stewart and Strathern (2003:4) have noted that the term "landscape" "refers to the perceived settings that frame people's *senses of place* and community." In this sense, local concept of landscape becomes an important component to understand contemporary issues regarding identity and territoriality of indigenous peoples

because it helps us understand how Yamphu have come to live in the land since time immemorial as in the first place and how the surrounding land have become *ancestral land*.

Anthropological theories of landscapes remind that "the senses of place and embeddedness within local, mythical, and ritual landscapes is important" because "these sense of place serve as pegs on which people hang memories, construct meanings from events, and establish ritual and religious arenas of action" (Stewart and Strathern, 2003:3). In so doing, people make a sense of place and belonging. They argue that "...people's perceptions of and values attached to landscape encode values and fix memories to places that become sites of historical identity" (2003:1). In Guo' view, landscape can serve as "a key component of how people perceive, memorize and represent history (i.e. their history), and how they configure their sense of selves" (Guo, 2003:193). In Guo's view, landscape symbolizes the ancestral past by connecting people to the land, and thus land ownership. He argues that Langalanga of Solomon Islands appropriate ancestral trees "in arguing the authenticity of their 'history' 'for' the claims of ownership." (Guo, 2003:196). Within oral tradition, *pellam* is a category which explains the ancestral past, ancestral migration, and the names of places where the ancestors are believed to have travelled. Naming the places of the physical environment where we live is a way of evoking ancestral relationship with those places, "a way of creating home" (Forbes, 1998:28). That is, people explain their history in terms of place names, migration and paths and landscapes. These place names and ancestral actions associated with particular places, what Santos-Granero (1998) would call "features of landscape" are imbued with and local histories. Such theoretical concepts can serve as an important framework to understand why Yamphu associate with the place where they inhabit and how they appropriate the landscape (Basso, 1988) through *mindum* so as to strengthen their "political identity" (Stewart and Strathern, 2003: 3).

However, a scholar Guo says, "the relationships between landscape and ancestral past can go beyond much more than representation and symbolization" (2003:195). He argues that apart from this, "supernatural power is involved in the relationships between ancestral history and landscape" (Guo, 2003:196). He further says that Langalanga maintain "the relationship with the ancestors (*agalo*) through sacrifices to secure land rights and prosperity" (ibid.).

In connection to supernatural powers' involvement in the relationships between land and people, Maurice Godelier's concept of "the social origins of sacred" can serve a powerful theoretical framework here. It enables us to provide an analytical account of the ways in which Yamphu relationship to present territory evolves from their power to communicate with ancestors. This relationship is then in Godelier's view, is *sacred* that enables Yamphu to view themselves as a *sovereign people* to define and legitimize their rights over the territory and its resources. In Godelier's perspective (1999: 171) "the sacred is a certain type of relationship that human entertains with the origin of things." In this relation "when a supernatural origin is imagined for the social sphere, the social becomes sacred, and society is legitimized as sacred it stands" (1999:124). While doing so, the real human replicates with imaginary human (ancestors) where the real human disappears. Then, the social sacred emerges from the relationship with imaginary representation that "facilitates communication with such powerful, invisible beings constituted an essential component of the exercise of sovereignty over a territory, over the resources found and exploited and often the human groups living there" (Godelier, 2009:146).

Mindum explains the origin of things that evokes the spiritual attachment of Yamphu in the present landscape (Yamphu, 2012). This in turn reflects the power relations in the political-religious totality of Yamphu society. Argued from this perspective, I find that *mindum* is a key way from which Yamphu and their ancestors reconstruct their past collaborately.

1.6. Conceptual Framework

Though *mindum* is understood as corpus of ancestral vices, a primordial knowledge, the contents of *mindum* are produced and reproduced in varying degrees in different time-space. This study assumed that *mindum* should not be confined only to ancestral knowledge, but can also be viewed as historical narratives, philosophical texts, as well as rhetorical and cultural practices of Yamphu.

We know that cultures are being shaped and reshaped by the ever-changing and ever shifting interactive contexts of global processes (Wolf 1996). Cultural construction and reconstruction occur when cultures react to these changing contexts, Wolf argues that “incorporate these reactions, and carry these effects on even as they go forward to the encounter of new interactive contexts” (1996:88). Given this context, this study has considered *mindum* as a cultural process through which it is transformed, produced and reproduced in different time-space.

Similarly, it should be noted that various factors such as "artistic, social, cultural and mnemonic" (Vansina, 1985:186) influences the production and transmission of *mindum*. Moreover, the contents of *mindum* and *pellam* might also be impacted by the performers' inherent interest of interpretation, his or her social position, inter clan relationship, the selectivity of sources, and historical social, economic and political context. I believe that only by understanding these factors we can investigate the political-religious-social aspects of *mindum*. That is why we find competing versions of *mindum* and *pellam*. Therefore, in describing and analyzing the texts of *mindum*, this study has given emphasis on the politics and poetics of *mindum* in the light of these factors. The politics and poetics of chanting *pellam* displays emergent forms of representation produced by local actors, in an apparent attempt to set at least some of the terms by which their social world would be regimented. Hence, in order to investigate the research questions I have outlined above, this study

concentrated on how we can understand the relation between the politics and poetics of *mindum* and the broader social and cultural world in which they were produced.

This study also examined local stories and discourses because, I believe, *mindum* is greatly shaped by them. In so doing, this study takes in account of what Jean Vnasina (1985) terms "historical gossip," "personal traditions," "group accounts," "linguistic expressions of past events" (folk etymology), "reminisces," and "etymological materials" that belonged to different localities and clan groups.

In order to examine the Yamphu claims of the sovereignty over the territory as an indigenous group and the core element that brings them together into a whole, major analytical units this study have considered are derived from two major themes: first this study considered *mindum* as moral and political because it has a particular rhetorical force that guarantees the individual subject's acceptance of the social order and meaning they give to it. In other words, *minudm* has been conceptualized as narrative which legitimizes "a given social and political order by being narrativized" (White, 1980:17).

Second, this study has made a critical examination of social relations between clan groups to explore the politics of *mindum*. Yamphu *mindum* and *pellam* as oral tradition, I do not consider them as only *sacred knowledge*, but as a "generation of verbal messages" or the Yamphu indigenous past as Vansina has viewed oral tradition as "testimonies of the past" (e.g., Vansina, 1985). The past in the form of oral tradition, I have considered *mindum* and *pellam* as culturally mediated and historically produced texts which find itself in a continuously changing world of meaning.

Figure-1: Yamphu Mindum

1.7. Chapter Organization

This dissertation includes six chapters. The first chapter begins with how I became interested in studying *mindum*. This chapter introduces the dissertation by discussing research problems, research questions and objectives of the study. It also outlines theoretical and conceptual framework I used for investigating these research questions.

Chapter two deals with fieldwork orientation and processes, *mindum* documentation methods my field experiences as an insider. In chapter three, I examine the central concept of

mindum and *pellam*, and examining indigenous notion of *mindum*. This chapter investigates how Yamphu make a sense of ancestral place. In chapter four, I exclusively deal with *chawa*. Here, I examine how Yamphu understand and interpret by reference to *chawa* and explains that *chawa* as the genesis of clan identity that binds and makes possible Yamphu society since time immemorial.

Chapter five provides an analysis of the importance of the political and social dimensions of *mindum* by examining how Yamphu use *mindum* including shamanic versions, local narratives and historical evident to construct the past to restructure the present. The final chapter provides summary of this dissertations with conclusions. In this chapter, I highlight some potential contribution of this dissertation in anthropological study of oral traditions in relation to constructing history, indigeneity, place and identity of indigenous peoples in Nepal.

Chapter Two

FIELD ORIENTATION AND METHODS

In this chapter, I outline fieldwork processes, *mindum* documentation methods and my field experiences as an insider.

2.1. Doing Fieldwork at Home

Among the anthropologists, there is an increasing trend of studying their own culture as their first culture of research. Ohnuki-Tiernry (1984:584) views that studying one's own culture is indeed very different from studying a foreign culture and theoretical and even epistemological implications of such study are profound.

I decided to study my own people and culture because I discovered that I lacked knowledge of my own culture. On the other hand, there was and is still a shortage of ethnographic literature on Yamphu. The changes in rural life are more intensified and ongoing because of global flows of people, technologies, communication and ideas. Here, I would like to describe some of my experiences that I went through when doing the fieldwork in my own community.

I had enormous advantages in being a part of my society from the start such as I could understand Yamphu way of thought which would be difficult for a foreigner or European to attend over many years. I experienced that an *insider* or *indigenous* can understand and read verbal cues. Brayboy and Deyhle argue that "outsiders are, of course, plagued by failing to see nuances from the perspectives of the informants" (2000:165). Most importantly, as an insider, I could *sense the people and their inner spirit* that anthropologists often seek to explore during their fieldwork. Therefore, I believe I became able to project a more trustworthy, authentic understanding of *mindum*. My insider status provided me with the

cultural knowledge to transcribe and interpret properly. Though I have no adequacy in my language, very often I tried my best to speak in my mother tongue which proved to be really a great asset because first it brought me warmness of the people.

Second, speaking in my own language facilitated communication, saved time and enabled me understanding the inner view of the people. My knowledge of Yamphu language, though it proved to be very inadequate in the field, saved me the problem of learning a language which is both time consuming and not easy for an *outsider*. I could pose more intelligent questions to narrators immediately after he had finished the chanting which an outsider would hardly have. In the case of Thulung Rai, Allen has noted that "I was never in a position to ask intelligent questions of a narrator immediately after he had finished speaking" (2012:16).

When I moved throughout the village, I found myself received with affection. My fieldwork in my own community led to the discovery of many strange and important aspects of my own society that still conceals itself from general Yamphu. I have learned, for example, a good deal more about *mindum*, *pellam*, and *chawa* that I took for granted before.

In addition to this, as an insider, I found myself in more advantageous position in understanding the emotive and psychological dimensions of behavior which are hard for outsiders to understand. There are also enormous advantages in studying one's own culture. I have intimate knowledge of daily routines, moral conducts, festive occasions, geographies, sacred sites and so on that are exceedingly difficult for outsiders to observe. As the member of my own society, I had easy access to not only the intellectual dimension but also to the emotive and the sensory dimensions of these behaviors.

One of best leanings from my study is that if insider anthropologists can maintain balance between their personal selves and their culture as collective selves, they can make an important contribution to anthropology because of their access to intimate knowledge of their

own culture. I was aware of that the premises of "reflexive anthropology help us to be more critical about our own culture (Geertz, 1973). By extending Geertz's view on reflexivity, Jacobs-Huey (2002791) suggests us that "Being reflexive enables researchers to critically consider their own cultural biases and negotiate various ways of seeing while investigating and translating culture."

Of course there are some little discouraging experiences I went through during my fieldwork. One of the difficulties I experienced in the field was that people most often wanted to me to about current political issues rather than this old thing *mindum*. At one point of discussion, my maternal uncle told me what some people were saying about me. I was told that some people said that I was doing this all because I received a lot of money for this.

2.2. How I started to Record Mindum

On the 15th of Chaitra, 2012, I made everything ready for recording *mindum* and *pellam*. I packed my recorder and camera then I set off to Hedangna early in the morning. I was accompanied by my maternal uncle Bhim Bahadur who is also well known *pellamdangba* in Num. We reached *Gadi*, around one o'clock in the afternoon. *Gadi* is a small bazaar on the way to Hedangna, where I met some of my friends. I have many friends and relatives from Hedangna in that place. I talked to them about my purpose to visit to Hedangana. They became happy to see me and more excited to learn that I am going to record *mindum* and *pellam*. But at the same time, it is a high time for such endeavor since many of our rituals and traditional practices are being eroded away day by day. They also admitted that if the trend continues, within a few years the *mindum* will also be completely lost. They told me that there are only few persons just one or two who know *mindum*. According to them, Gurungnimba and Khasinimba the two persons from Gairi Gaoun who are knowledgeable ones. But they also signaled that since these persons are already very old,

and they may not be able to tell complete corpus of *mindum* and *pellam*. In their views, reciting *mindum* and *pellam* needs good memory of an individual which might be difficult for very old people.

It was March 29, 2012 when I reached Hedangna. It is three hours walk from Num (my village). After a brief conversation with my friends from Gadi, I asked them about the location of Gurungnimba's, a well-known *pellamdangba* house. After I got instruction of the place, Gairi Gaoun where Gurungnimba's house is located, I headed to towards it. Upon reaching there, I saw an old man of wrinkled face. He was sitting on the wall with both his knees bent, in a crouching position. He seemed to me approximately of 80 years, old. His grey hair was covered with a Nepali Dhaka Topi. I approached him and introduce myself. He smiled at me and showed me a place to have a sit. After a while, I offered him some *koseli* (bottle of *raksi*) which I had taken with me from my house, Num. Meanwhile I explained my purpose to visit him. At first he did not accept that he knew *mindum*. He laughed and said "who said you that I know *pellam*? Without any particular reasons, these villagers say so. Actually, I don't know. There are other people who know a lot and better than me." I was quite aware of that it is the part of our culture that people generally do not put forward themselves as they know. Even though he was saying so, we kept on talking. I kept on talking why the study and recording of *mindum* was really necessary. Finally, he agreed to tell me about *mindum*. For this, we decided to meet in Mathilo Gaoun (Upper village of Hedangna) in the following day. It really made me encouraged in collecting *mindum*.

After that I took a leave from him and headed towards Mathillo Gaoun where my maternal aunt lives. In Mathilo Gaoun, I went to see some of my friends. After some causal talk I told them about my visit. When they heard that I will be seeing the Gurungnimba on the next day, all of them said that they would attend the recording to hear about *mindum* and *pellam*.

I was desperately waiting for the next day. I was really anxious to hear and to record *mindum* and *pellam*. Though I am from the same community, I had ever heard or witnessed chanting of *pellam*. The next day we went to the place where the Gurungnimba had asked me to meet. It was around 11 o'clock in the morning, he had not arrived there. Some of my friends along with interested villagers were already there to listen to *mindmu* and *pellam*. All of us waited for him anxiously. But he was late and we kept waiting for Gurungnimba, hours passed, but he did not show up. While waiting for him, we talked and kept wondering why he did not show up. Some of the people waiting with me became a bit impatient and seemed little worried: why Gurungnimba made us keep waiting. It was already four o'clock, so we decided to go to his own place. The two *ma?ma* (grandmother) who had been waiting with us said that they would also accompany me. They said, "He is our brother, let's go to see him and also ask him why he did not show up." So, we headed down towards his house in Gairi Gaoun.

When we reached down there, he was not at his home. The family members informed us that he had gone to attend *khamang* ritual (pitri 'N') in the neighborhood. The *khammang* ritual is mostly observed in the evening. We came to know that he was at his home whole day while we were waiting for him in Mathilo Gaoun. Then, a friend who accompanied me from Mathilo Gaoun went to call him. After a while he arrived. He apologized to us for not being able to come to the upper village. Some people who had been waiting for him with us complained and asked him for the reason of keeping us waiting. He replied that he was about to come but something came up.

After such interaction, then we sat together with Tongba and kept on talking village matters. We discussed a lot about different aspects of *mindum* and *pellam*. Gurungnimba chanted some *pellam*. Having passed some hours with him having Tongba, I found Gurungnimba very co-operative. We talked about *mindum* till the mid-night.

The next morning, when everyone left, he revealed me the reason why he did not show up in the place we had decided to meet. He said that, "You know, these people (people who had come with me) have come here to learn *mindum*." Since then Gurungnimba and I have become good friends. In my last visit (December 2013), he publicly announced that *Hom le malai guru thapeko chha*. This is how I began to record *mindum*. This ethnographic description provides a readily available window onto the concept of *mindum* and *pellam*.

2.3. Data Collection Methods

The study is based on the ethnographic approach with a goal of collecting and analyzing oral texts related with Yamphu *mindum*. My ethnographic fieldwork is interrelated with two distinct activities: First, I tried to win the goodwill of elders and knowledgeable people to persuade them to divulge their sacred knowledge *mindum*. Second, I regularly maintained field notes in a systematic way of the recordings and what I observed and learned from the field observations and interactions. These two interconnected activities comprised the core of this study.

The ethnographic field work of this study was conducted from mid December 2013 to March 2014. However, I had already recorded most of the texts of *mindum* in between 2012 and 2013 and some more oral text was collected during this fieldwork 2014. The primary data of this study were collected by field observation, in-depth interview, group discussion, and recording the text of *mindum* from key informants since 2012 onwards.

My field work was based in three major Yamphu settlements¹ of upper Arun valley which is located in north from Khandbari, headquarter of Sankhuwasabha district. A local bus takes four hours' drive to reach these places. Though, I did research at home, I was in essence not really at home. My long absence from home as well as the complexity of my research topic has, somehow made me an outsider throughout the fieldwork. During my

fieldwork, from 2012 onwards, I interviewed nineteen² Yamphu elders, *shakmiyungbaji*, *pellamdangbaji*, *mangba* and *yadangbaji* (knowledgeable persons, ritual experts and shamans) and recorded *mindmu*, local histories, and legends in order to understand social, political, and religious dimensions of *mindum*. Such interviews enriched my understanding about *mindum*. In addition to this, I discussed with them about the accounts of personal experience, historical accounts, narratives, inter-ethnic relationship, legends related with *mindum* and its metaphors.

I also organized formal and informal discussion with village elders, knowledgeable persons, and shamans and priests in order to explore necessary information about the political-religious aspects of *mindum*. The group discussions helped me to bring more clarity and consensus, since informants were not always in agreement on various matters, such as meaning of ritual words, content of the myths et cetera. Impertinently, group discussions proved to be so instrumental that the context of *mindum* and the figurative language and metaphor used in the texts could be properly translated, analyzed and interpreted.

Mindum is heterogeneous in term of ritual speech form, location and their social background. To record this heterogeneity of *mindum* I organized formal and informal discussion with village elders, knowledgeable persons, shamans and priests of different villages. Such conversational discussions remained so fruitful that it helped me to contextualize *mindum* and to interpret the figurative language used in the texts.

During the fieldwork, I regularly maintained field notes, which includes observational notes about the field insights and experience. Field note writing involved the interpretation and sense-making of social reality. By field note writing, I tried my best to inscribe social life and social discourse of Yamphu people that was dramatized in the public spheres and interactions. Keeping all these in mind, I considered field notes in the way as Geertz (1973:19) has characterized: "the ethnographer inscribes social discourse; he writes it down.

In so doing, he returns it from a passing event, which exists only in its moment of occurrence, into an account which exists in its inscription and can be re-consulted." As inscriptions, in this sense, field notes are the product of and reflection conventions for transforming witnessed events, persons, and places into words on paper. In this study, field notes are used to provide description and notes to the original recorded texts and used in the analysis of the texts.

2.4. Mindum Documentation Methods

Num, Hedangna and Makalu were my major ethnographic sites. On the basis of performance and ritual context, *mindum* chanting can be classified in two categories: first, *mindum* of *mangba* and *yadangba* who only chant in ritual performance, and second, *mindum* of *mindumdnagba*, and *pellamdangba* who can also chant in non-ritual performance. In other words, to record shamanic version of *mindum*, we need ritual context such as in *sammangs*, lifecycle rituals and other collective ceremonies otherwise recording becomes impossible. Such shamanic *mindum* involves "...complex sacrificial offerings and verbal journeys..." (Gaenzle, 2002:36) through which they call ancestors and communicate with them. Then, to record the shamanic version of *mindum in situ*, I tried to attend every possible ritual and other cultural ceremonies. These ritual and cultural events included marriage ceremonies, *yumang* (Bali Puja 'N') ritual, *sammngs* and night performance of *mangba*. This enabled me to record the corpus of ritual texts in detail in the contextual setting. Though I have recorded *mindum* of *mangaba* and *yadangba*, this study does not include them. I focused more on *mindum* of *mindumdangba* and *pellamdangba* which were chanted in non-ritual context. Since this part of *mindum* deals with creation of the world and human kind and Yamphu continuity in the present territory, clan splits and dispersal, I found it central to Yamphu history, identity in relation to territorial attachment. In addition to this, I have focused on a number of local

accounts of *mindum* and *pellam* that have added more details to understating political-religious aspects of *mindum*.

Figure-2: The Map of Sankhuwasabha District and the Study Areas

Unlike shamanic version of *mindum*, there are other oral historical narratives chanted in rhythmic style by *mindumdangba* and *pellamdangba*. This version of *mindum* is generally called *pellam*. In essence, shamanic *mindum* and *pellam* are not different but they differ from each other in terms of ritual speech and in the way they are performed. This is why Yamphu use *mindum* and *pellam* interchangeably. Though, *pellam* also chanted in ceremonial context

such as marriage, inauguration ceremony of new house, festivals and social gatherings, it doesn't require ritual context. Therefore, *pellam* chanting can also take place in non-ritual context too. In such *in vitro* recordings the text were chanted only for recording purposes.

However, recording *mindum* and *pellam* was not free of constraints. Being a member of my own community, naturally, I experienced different impressions both let say *encouraging* and *discouraging*. But most of them are encouraging. All of the elders encouraged me to record *mindum* as they thought that people are no longer learning *mindum* and that it would all be forgotten. They not only encouraged me but also helped me in identifying knowledgeable persons, and organizing group discussions. For proper recording of *mindum* and *pellam*, I often met *pallamdangba* and served them with Tongba. This approach really helped me to win the good will of the elders.

2.5. Recording the Text

As is the context, I have recorded the text of *mindum* of shaman *in situ* and *pellam* and other local histories, legends were recorded *in vitro*, i.e. in non-ritual context in the presence of some ritual experts and selected knowledgeable persons. While recording, I selected a bit more peaceful place in order to control for background noise. On the other hand, I have recorded the shamanic *mindum in situ* i.e. in its ritual context. I have recorded the whole text of *mindum* so that we could later make the necessary editing, translation, transcription, coding, and interpretation. Recordings were done by using digital recorders. During the recording, special attention was paid on to follow procedures in making audio recording of the text. Recordings were annotated:

- Who is doing the recording
- Date and venue of recording
- Who is being recorded

- Category/types of story, myth, ritual text, etc.
- From whom and where did the person learn the text, etc.
- Name of other participants

2.6. Recording process

Before we proceed to record the text, I discussed about general cultural context of the *mindum*, and its significance for Yamphu cultural life with local ritual experts (I have mentioned in Chapter one). To observe variation on the content of the text and its way of chanting, I recorded the same *mindum* and *pellam* from different individuals in different settlements. My field experience have revealed that *mindum*, *pellam* and other oral texts vary in relation to geographical variation, inter clan relations and gender. Analyzing such variation enabled me to analyze how and what degree new creative additions have been be made to the text; or how important it is that the text remain in its original form; and where there are cultural borrowings.

2.7. Translating and Transcribing the Text

The study basically dealt with the sacred oral texts of Yamphu. As *pellam* was recorded in Yamphu language, in the first stage, I translated and transcribed the text of *mindum* verbatim and made "a linear line-by-line" translation into Nepali with the help of local ritual experts in the field. The transcription was based on the interviews, observational notes, memos, etc. In this work, Bhim Bahadur Gaurung provided me with valuable insights and perspectives from the very beginning of the study.

For instance, we Bhim Bahadur and me together transcribed *pellam* text into Nepali and annotated the transcribed texts as possible as in the field. Then, we translated the transcribed texts into Nepali. We stayed for hours with *Tongba*, at my home in Num, and

discussed about possible correction pronunciation and meanings of the words that were not clearly pronounced during recordings. The texts we recorded were full of figurative words and of proto-Yamphu speech. It was really very difficult to translate into Nepali. For instance, in some point in the recorded text, we found some speech were spoken in a low voice and were often difficult to understand. In other case, we found many different figurative words and speech that do not appear in everyday language use. Some words seemed to have lost its meaning. Meanings of such speech were negotiated and co-constructed as far as possible. Once we got the text translated, then we categorized it into major themes.

Later on at the end of my fieldwork, I again visited to the key informant and shared the translated text with them. The sharing provided key informants with the opportunity to see how their own speech were transcribed and translated. It also provided them with opportunity to ensure that they did not leave anything out. Then, I revised and refined the texts in Kathmandu by rereading, searching subtopics, or combining under a subordinate category when meanings were similar. I read and reread the texts in detail.

Then next, my friend, Rajendra Thokar who is also linguist helped me transcribe the text into English. For transcription, we have used Yamphu phonetic alphabets that have been developed by Yamphu Kirat Society and later by Summer Institute of Language (SIL). Once I got the text transcribed I translated it verbatim and made "a linear line-by-line" translation into English. We, on the other hand, have used Yamphu grammar by Roland who studied Yamphu language during the 1990s for his Ph. D dissertation.

2.8. Analysis and Interpretation of Ethnographic Data

The analysis process began with assembling the raw data and getting an overview of the entire ethnographic process. It involved reading, rereading, transcribing and exploring

data. This process continued until the project ended. In so doing, consideration of words, tone, context, non-verbal, internal consistency, frequency, extensiveness, intensity, specificity of responses and big ideas were of primary focus. Really, these tasks were not easy. I discussed about these features of the *mindum* and *pellam* with ritual experts for several days in order to understand and capture the actual meanings of them. Such rigorous process involved interpretation of the meanings embedded in the texts of *mindum* and *pellam*. It was carried out by close examination of field notes and insight, and careful attention to the meaning embedded in the texts. The study used field notes as a complete corpus. I elaborated and refined my earlier field insights by subjecting this broader collection of field notes to close, intensive reflection and analysis.

1.9. Limitation of the Study

This study is just the beginning to study the rich Yamphu cultural heritage. *Mindum* as oral tradition is diverse and rich, and I have tried to represent a partial record of them in this study. The text of *mindum* varies as the category of performers varies. Though there are varieties of *mindum*, this dissertation has mainly focused on *pellam* of *pellamdangba*, most of which were chanted in non-ritual context. It does not cover all these genres of *mindum* chanted by different performers such as *mangba* and *yadangba* with few exceptions. In order to compare different narrators' versions, a further study is necessary.

Similarly, *mindum* is heterogeneous in term of location. For instance, I have recorded different versions of the *mindum* in Seduwa, a neighboring Yamphu village to Hedangna which I could not include in this dissertation. My fieldwork also suggests that the interpretation of *mindum* and meaning attached to its metaphors are influenced by personal experience, historical accounts, inter-clan, inter-ethnic relationship. For example, knowledgeable person who belongs to a numerically less dominant group often conceal some debatable facts of

pellam while chanting it because it would create tension in the society. This was well illustrated when Gurungnimba told me history of some clan groups in Hedangna. To compare and analyze such different versions and themes were beyond the scope of this study. It is also true that in all Yamphu villages, people who are above 50 know a bit or more *mindum*, but they do not claim that they know the complete and full version of *mindum*. Therefore, the *mindum* presented in this dissertation should not be regarded as complete, full and definitive.

This dissertation has only focused on Yamphu *mindum*, but my study suggests that before we reach to a genuine conclusion and generalization about Yamphu, we need to collect the oral traditions of other neighboring groups such Lhomi Bhote, Mewahang, Lohorung and Yakkha of the Upper Arun Valley in detail. This is because, so-called myths of these groups show a close historical links with each other. For being so, it is necessary to look for as many links as possible between these groups. For example, the *mindum* of Mewahang Lohourng and Yamphu have many common features, but at some point they are debatable and often confusing (See Gaenslze, 2000 and Hardman, 2000). It will be interesting to investigate why such debatable versions are being narrated by them.

As concerned with recording, transcribing and translating of *mindum*, it found it really tough and time consuming. While translating *minndum* and *pellam* into Nepali and then English at some points, I found that even the narrators are uncertain about *pellam* as it was just heard from their elders without its proper explanation. This was well reflected when I asked Gurungnimba to tell me whether *khokwalun* and Kashi are the same Kashi place or not, I found him uncertain about this. As a result, the *mindum* translated and presented in this dissertation is not free of ambiguities and uncertainties.

Further I have to note that though the politics and poetics of *mindum* along with its contents are shaped and reshaped in time-space by historical, social and political contexts, this study does not provide details of historical contexts that shaped and reshaped the contents

of *mindum*. In a sense, the analysis of *mindum* in this study is synchronic. In other words, the guiding concepts used in this study was found little inadequate to explain temporal aspects of *mindum*.

Chapter Three

THE MINDUM: THE ORIGIN AND INSCRIBING HISTORY INTO THE LANDSCAPE

This chapter provides the central concept of *mindum* and *pellam*, and examining indigenous notion of *mindum* this chapter investigates how Yamphu make a sense of ancestral place.

3.1. The Concept of Mindum: The Origin (Uhileko Kura)

In my second visit, November 2012, my uncle Bhim Bahadur and I approached to Man Bahadur Yamphu who lives in Salbisaune, Gairgaoun Hedangna. He is also one of the knowledgeable persons about *mindum*. He was at home. We sat together and talked about some village matters and *mindum* as well. After having some conversation with him, we asked him about Khasinimba, a *yadanga* from the same locality. He informed us that Khasinimba was in the cowshed. He became ready to lead us to Khasinimba and we followed him. Man Bahadur led us to that place. The place was far below the village near by Arun River. We went down and down until we saw a small hut letting hearth's smoke from the top. Khasinimba was busy with his work, collecting fodders for his cows. He recognized my uncle Bhim Bahadur but not me. My uncle introduced me with him. My uncle and he talked about cows, availability of fodders and finally about *mindum*. We offered him some *raksi* that we had taken with us. In a question of *mindum*, he chanted the following *pellam*.

iei khokwayu ʔaŋbi ʔubeʔe minangsa, namekle huba
ha ha khokwaluŋ dembang ʔaŋbi ʔubeʔe hukmasayabang,
iei mayong songsuwal lam tevakla kading yo
i ei poppo on this pitta sambok (Dubo 'N'), mankind was created;
after creating mankind, death was also created;
i ei ei ʔaŋbi ʔubeʔe (Shiva) created mankind in the underground (khokwaluŋ);
he also created knowledgeable and stupid human as well;
in palumdem, ei ei mankind was created in khokwaluŋ chpchik dem;

iei mankind was created;

Listen! This is *mindum*: Our origin (*pukma* 'Y,' *utpatti* 'N').

The above piece of *pellam* says that *khokwayu tanbi tube?e* (For other Kirati-*Paruhang*) created mankind in the underground world (*khokwalung*). After being created, Yamphu followed the Arun River path. According to Khasinimba, this is the *mindum*: the origin. In his view, Bantawa and Athpahariya have split from Yamphu. He said, "So, they don't have Wan. Wan means what? Wan means, they did not follow River path."

Khasinimba insists that *mindum* means *pukmaya* (*utpatti* 'N'). According to him, the major theme of *mindum* is: where we are from, how we have come to this place and how we should live here. On this ground, *mindum* provides Yamphu with philosophical ground for the continuity of traditional life.

For Chemjong, Limbu *mundhum* is *riti riwaj* (manner and custom) or *thuturi bed* (Veda of the tongue). He states: "The word Mundhum means the power of great strength and the Kirat people of east Nepal take it to be a true, holy and a powerful scripture" (Chemjong, 2003 I: 18). For Yamphu *mindum* is *uhileko kura* (old thing) or the origin (*sirikwa* 'Y'). Yamphu have *mindum* because it is told and re-told by ancestors. A *mindumdangba* narrated *mindum* as follows:

We all are originated in *mindum*. All rituals are originated in *mindum*. It is old thing. It is the way of ancestors. It is being handed over from generation to generation and we are doing so. People, especially young generation, do not pay interest, but I think it is a thing we really need. We need *mindum* whatever we do. We need *mindum* when we do marriage; we need *mindum* when we give birth to a child; we need *mindum* when we become sick; we need *mindum* when we die; we need *mindum* when we plant/harvest crops in the paddy; we need *mindum* when we build a house; we need *mindum* in order to do every ritual. You know, Yamphu life cannot be imagined without *mindum* (Interview, 2012)

The concept of *mindum*, I suppose the Gurungnimba's narration demonstrates, is essentially a totality of Yamphu life. From the narration, we can see that *mindum* is not only corpus of knowledge that speaks of Yamphu origin and history, but is also a thesis on which

"the whole body of principles of social ethics can be structured" (Nicolette, 2006:35). In order to understand Yamphu notion of *mindum* as in the above statement, a useful conceptual framework can be drawn from Godelier's idea of "imaginary realities". According to him, "imaginary realities" lie at the core of human relations. He points out that "cores of imaginary realities serve as their essential components, give them meaning, and are embodied in institutions and symbolic practices that endow them with a visible social existence as well as the status of self-evident "truths"" (Godelier 2009: 22). From Gurungnimba's remarks on *mindum*, becomes clear that *mindum* is a world of ideas, images, and meanings of the things around them. It is similar to the idea of imaginary as Godelier postulates that it is "a real world, but one that is made up of mental realities (such as images, ideas, opinions, reasonings, and intentions)" (ibid.).

Gurungnimba reveals that *mindum* is the genesis of everything and thus, Yamphu are originated in *mindum*. *Mindum* seems to act as the ancestral wisdom by which the meaning of Yamphu life is organized. It has shaped and has been shaping Yamphu worldview on how one is to be in the world and how to live in it; how the ancestral world is populated; and why and how the living should communicate to ancestors. It is with the reference of above remark, we can observe that Yamphu interpret and explain their world they live in through *mindum* as cultural window that symbolize their experience and codify their belief in the present landscape. Therefore, *mindum* as corpus of knowledge gives them insight into how they have come to be the present condition.

Thus, in Yamphu view, *mindum* is neither myth nor history, it is rather a lived reality to be followed, maintained, and respected. *Mindum* is not mere myth or oral traditions but is ancestral knowledge of the past which guides customs, manner, and rituals of Yamphu in the present time. The *mindum* encodes the basic cultural themes, aesthetic values, and propositions of the society. It is corpus of ancestral footprints and actions which embodies

group identity and serves as the foundation for establishing and maintaining relationship among the Yamphu. It should be noted that Hardman's study of Lohorung reveals that "the *pe-lam* gives Lohorung cultural identity and 'unity'" (2000:105). As Malinowski's study of Trobriand myths makes it clear that Trobriand myths were "not merely a story told but a reality lived" (Malinowski, 1948:100 cited by Harwood 1976:784).

Mindum tradition is fairly typical feature among the various Kirati groups in the eastern Nepal. Hardman's study of Lohorung Rai emphasizes the importance of *pe-lam* as follows:

The ancestral past for Lohorung is neither myth nor history: that part of the past is an intrinsic and ever-living part of the present, acting as a constant reminder, an image or consciousness of the knowledge, morality, and correct order of nature and society, which has to be respected and maintained in order to ensure the continued strength of their society (Hardman, 2000:105).

Gaenzle observes an identical notion of *muddum* among Mewahang Rai of Bala:

The *munddum* is conceived as a totality, as a comprehensive body of rituals which is used for the continuation of a cultural order that has been inherited from one's forebears. It is seen as a coherent whole as "the Tradition" and because of this integrity and comprehensiveness which affects all aspects of cultural life it is "a great thing" (2002:34).

Whenever we discuss about Yamphu *mindum*, we often happen to encounter another concept: the *pellam*. Very often Yamphu use these two terms interchangeably. However, in an interaction with Yamphu elders suggest that sometimes *mindum* and *pellam* have different meanings.

If we look at epistemological level, *mindum* and *pellam* are same as both of these concepts because they contain the same knowledge of ancestral past- migrations, clan split and village foundation. But as we look at the trend of using these two concepts, we can find a slight difference between *pellam* and *mindum*. On the basis of discussions with Yamphu elders, it is evident that we can view *mindum* is a much broader term since it covers the whole customs, rituals, traditions and stories of Yamphu. It serves as a philosophical ground

for the present through which Yamphu try to make sense of the world in which they find themselves. *Mindum* is just a corpse of knowledge that can be expressed in any form such as, in social discourse and interactions, in correct ways of doing, in ritual dialogues or in ritual chants of *mangba* and *yadangba*. In other words, we can conceptualize *mindum*, as what Geertz say about culture, is "acted document, context, a symbol coded with public meaning." (1973:10).

As we discussed above *mindum* acts as charter that codifies and sanctions overall socio-cultural activities, social interactions and behavior, interaction with nature and environment, relationship between man and nature, and man and natural species (Yamphu, 20012). *Mindum* always refers to the correct manner of doing things- the performance of *sammangs* and rituals, and even everyday act. This is exactly what Hardman observes in Lohorung Rai that "*pe-lam* refers synonymously as *riti-lam* where *riti* means custom, ceremony, manner, or way" (2000:103-4). She argues that: "Lohorung *mundum/pe-lam* functions as charter" (2000:106). Harwood (1976) notes Malinowskian view on myths for the Trobrianders (Malinowski 1948:96):

The sacred tradition, the myths, enters into their pursuits, and strongly controls their moral and social behavior. In other words... an intimate connection exists between the world, the mythos, the sacred tales of a tribe, on the one hand, and their ritual acts, their moral deeds, their social organization, and even their practical activities on the other.

On the other hand, *pellam* is only a lyrical expression of *mindum*. Mostly, the origins of the earth, human and ancestral migration are song through *pellam*. Sometimes it has no connotation with rituals. *Pellam* cannot be expressed in social discourse or dialogue like *mindum*. More explicit distinction between *pellam* and *mindum* can be made from a simple question. If somebody asked Yamphu, "What guides Yamphu tradition, rituals, customs and everyday act?" The answer is simple: *mindum*. Yamphu say, "Our rituals and traditional way of life is guided by *mindum* but they do not say guided by *pellam*."

However, in some ritual such as performing *tangdupha?wa*, (guiding dead spirit to the world of ancestors), chanting of *pellam* is compulsory. In such rituals, *pellamdangba* often chants a night long poetic form of *mindum*. It is usually *pellamdangba* and *mangba* who is believed to be escorting the deceased soul to the ancestral world. *Pellamdangba* take the soul of the dead by chanting *pellam* which contrastively differs from *mangba*. In this sense, *pellam* is simply a stylistic and poetic expression of *mindum*. Yamphu never call "singing *mindum*" but they call "singing *pellam*". Therefore, *pellam* is used, more specifically, to refer to the poetic form of *mindum*.

In addition to this, *pellam* is also related with the tradition of folk songs³ that are sung especially on the occasion of marriage, *yumang*, *household ceremonies*, and some other social gatherings. Here, the elders sing *pellam* for the purpose of entertainment. Theoretically, singing *pellam* takes place between two parties (either male and female or male and male) in which one party requires to response another and vice versa. Even if *pellam* is chanted as a song for a recreational purpose, it includes ancestral knowledge: creation of the world and other natural species, the birth of humankind, and ancestral migration, clan histories and so on. Since *pellam* is a reenactment of ancestral journey, clan migration and *chawa*, Yamphu believe that it has great strength and power. This is why Yamphu believe that chanting *pellam* without a purpose and context is sometimes dangerous.

As concerned with other Kirati groups, in the study of Thulung Rai mythology, Allen has found similar concept of *diumla* (See Allen, 2012). An identical concept of *pellam* also exists among Chamling called as *rishiya*.⁴

3.2. The Performers and Mindum

From the above discussion, we understand that *mindum* has some categories in terms of its performance. In order to understand the genres of *mindum*, we need to understand the

categories of performers as they use different metaphoric words while chanting *mindum*. In essence, whoever chants the *mindum*, it contains the same knowledge, power and strength. But it differs in the way how it is performed (how it is performed) and also depends on the performer (by whom it is being performed). For these reasons, I will briefly discuss about ritual specialists before discussing about various genres of *mindum*.

Yamphu have mainly three types of ritual specialists on the basis of which *mindum* can be categorized. They are: *mangba*, *yadangba*, and *pellamdangba/mindumdangba*. The first two have almost the same way of chanting *mindum* because they both are the medium of communicating with ancestors. Though there is no explicit hierarchal division among Yamphu priests, there is shared notion that *mangba* is at the apex who deals with various afflictions in the night-long performances. If we follow Rex L. Jone's definition and classification of spirit possession in the Himalayas, *mangba* falls under the category of *Tuteloery possession* (1976:6). Mostly, he is responsible for protecting the society from evil spirits or various malevolent beings. *Mangba* performs rituals only in the night. During the performance, he wears a white turban, feathered head-gear (wasaj 'Y'), and also puts on string of bells, necklaces of *rudraksha* beads (*eloecarpus sphaericus*), snake vertebrae etc. and plays a small drum made up of skin. When he calls his tutelary deities (Guru 'N'), he or she starts trembling. *Mangba* deals with the forces of disorder that afflict individual households. A *mangba* has a power to go to supernatural world in trance and has power to communicate with ancestors and other evil spirits in order to discover why they have afflicted the person with illness or patient and what they require as the price for allowing the patient to get well. In this sense, certainly his *mindum* and way of chanting differs from others.

Unlike *mangba*, *yadangba* does not play drum but holds metal plate or leaves of particular plant. *Yadangba* is similar to *phedangba* of Limbu. Sagant notes that *phedangba* in Limbu is considered as tribal priest who deals with life cycle and other rituals (Sagant, 1976).

He is responsible for everyday ancestral cults such as *khamang*, *chawa*, *nuwagi*, *yumang*, and *sammangs* and other territorial cults. Unlike *mangba*, who performs only at night, *yadangba* performs such rituals either early in the morning or day or even evening. *Yadangba* propitiates ancestral spirits and other deities of the nature. The main concern of *yadangba* is to maintain ancestral cults of the society. He or she deals with the life-cycle rituals, rites concerning the fertility of the soil protection of the corps in the house, the village, the clan and propitiates the *sammang* ancestors.

Figure-3: A *mangba* in the Séance

In contrast, *mangba*, who never performs during the day, deals almost exclusively with the forces of disorder, with the spirits of those who have died unnatural deaths and he or she retrieves lost *lawa*.⁵ It is the *yadangba*, who is primarily concerned with *sammangs*, as opposed to the *mangba's* function to control disorder. As his ritual and performance differs from *mangba*, *yadangba's mindum* little varies from *mangaba* and others.

Pellamdangba or *mindumdangba*, is a person who is an expert in *pellam/mindum*, but he or she has no authority to perform the rituals as *mangba* and *yadangba* have. Of course, an expert *pellamdangba* and *mindumdangba* may have more knowledge of *mindum* than a *yadangba* or *mangba*, but he or she unable to communicate with ancestors. A *pellamdangba* does not tremble, but can make a *mangba* tremble by chanting *pellam*. In the context of Thulung Rai, Allen also indicates such knowledgeable persons who were not priests.⁶

As the categories of Yamphu performers, the text of *mindum* also varies according to the category of performers. Based on the performance and use of textual metaphors, a *mangba's mindum* differs from *pellamdangba*. Generally, Yamphu distinguish *mindum* of *mangba*, and *yadangba* from *pellamdangba* on the basis of the ways through which they make their ritual journeys. Therefore, Yamphu say, *mindum* chanted by *mangba* is *mangba ram* (the path of shaman). Shamanic *mindum* is different from *pellamdangba* because a *mangba* often calls supernatural powers and communicate with them through *mindum*. In this sense, *mindum* chanted by *mangba* is a two way communication: communicating with ancestors and other supernatural powers i.e. responding to ancestors and receiving messages from ancestors. For this reasons, a *mangba* or *yadangba* can only chant *mindum* in a ritual context. In other words, they cannot chant *mindum* in non-ritual context. *Mangba* and *yadangba mindum* are mostly accompanied by the sacrifice of chicken and animals to supernatural beings. But a *pellamdangba* cannot communicate with ancestors but only make them listen. Therefore, his or her *pellam* is one way: communication with ancestor, just chanting. In this sense, the *mangba's* verbal ritual journeys differ from *pellamdangba*. *Mangba* can even go to the *khokwaluŋ*, the seven layers down of the earth. Indeed, a *pellamdangba* never goes *mangba ram* because he has no authority to go that way. Therefore, as the way of communicating with ancestors differs from each other, the variation in the content of *mindum* is obvious.

Martin Gaenzle has divided Rai mythology into four parts. They are: "the myths of creation, the myths about the culture hero, the myths of ancestral migration, and the myths about the first settlements and village foundation" (Gaenzle, 2008:6). On the basis of performers, Gaenzle's work on Mewahng Rai's mythology, divides Mewahng *muddum* into four types: ceremonial dialogue, lay invocation, invocation of elders and ritual texts of the initiated ritual specialists (Gaenzle, 2002:35-36).

Mindum can be divided into four basic parts on the basis of content. First part of *mindum* deals with the origin and creation- for instance, origin of the earth, human, and nature, travelling of ancestors in search of unsettled place, clan splits and dispersal in the present territory, incorporation of other tribal groups into Yamphu, and village foundations. Second part of *mindum* is *mangba ram* (shaman's path) which explicitly deals with *sammangs* and supernatural beings. Such *mindum* is called *me?chira* (Bakhan 'N'). This type of *mindum* is not easily accessible as it is chanted only by *mangba* and *yadangba*.

Third part of *mindum* concerns with life cycle rituals such as wedding ceremonial dialogues⁷ and death ritual dialogues.⁸ And final part of *mindum* includes a great number of ethical codes that signifies correct way of mannerism and traditional oral genre such as legends, local histories, genealogies, inter-clan conflict, and local stories of mythical ancestors, recreational songs and folktales.

Though there are varieties of *mindum*, this dissertation has mainly focused on *pellam* of *pellamdangba* which were chanted in non-ritual context. Since this part of *mindum* deals with creation of the world and human kind and Yamphu continuity in the present territory, clan splits and dispersal, I found it central to Yamphu history, identity in relation to their territorial attachment. In addition to this, I have focused on a number of local accounts of *mindum* and *pellam* that have added more details and enriched my understating in politico-religious aspects of *mindum* as well.

3.3. The Shiri?wa (The Creation)

*he he he khokwayu ṭaṅbi ṭube?ε pappa (Paruhang),
he he he khokwayu ṭaṅbi ṭub pappa?εko he he created niwaluṅ (conceptualized in mind);
he he he ṭaṅbi ṭumma ma?me?ε (Sumnima) also created niwaluṅ;
he he he created niṅwaluṅ;
he he he on top of niṅwaluṅ he he he the place of wind happen he he he the place of wind
happen;
he he he on top of this wind he he he sisaluṅ happen, he he he sisaluṅ happen;
he he he on top of this sisaluṅ he he he (Shiva) created khokwaluṅ; (underground world);
he he he ṭaṅbi ṭuba pappe?ε (Paruhang), he he he created khokwaluṅ;
he he on top of this khokwaluṅ, he he he on top of this khokwaluṅ he he he water happen;
(Krishna Bahadur Yamphu, April, 20102)*

According to Krishna Bahadur, in the time of origin, *khokwayu ṭaṅbi ṭube?ε pappa*⁹ (Some other Kirati groups call him Paruhang) created *niwaluṅ* (imagined the world in his mind). The world of wind (*hikwaluṅ 'Y'*) was created above this. Then, *sisaluṅ* was created above it. The *khokwaluṅ* (underground world) was created on top of the *sisaluṅ*, and *ṭommaluṅ* (Lake) was created above it.

In Gurungnimba's version, on top of this *makkhim tomma* (also *tommalung*), a plant called *dumsinṅla* (Shrikhanda 'N') sprang up. The wind and storm broke the branches of *dumsinṅla*, the wind and storm made the leaves fallen on the water (*makkhim tomma*) from which the earth was formed. There sprang up *Pitta Sambok* on the soil. From the clash of cloud and wind, the stone (*luṅjira*) was created on the earth. The *ulaminam tankhiyanam* (Paruhang and Sumnima) created *minagsa* (humankind) on top of the *pitta sambok*.

But, in Krishna Bahadur's version, first humankind were created in a plant. *Ṭaṅbi ṭumma ma?me?ε* (Sumnima) sowed seeds and sprout seedlings. From the seeds and seedlings the plant bore humankind- five sons and two daughters- as the fruit in the plants. He chanted *pellam* as follows:

*he he he mashyami ma?ma (Paruhang) sowed seeds;
he he he then, the plant bore humankind- five sons and two daughters- as the fruit;
hui hui he he he five sons were created;*

The three versions of *pellam*, I presented above, have a common theme the first humankind was created in *khokwaluŋ*. However, their versions remain salient about mother and the name of the first human.

As concerned with other Kirati groups, the concept of *khokwaluŋ* as the place of origin is very common theme in oral tradition, but it is known in different terminologies. For instance, Mewahang *muddum* recalls *khokwalung* (Gaenszle, 2000), Chamling *muddum* calls it as *khowalung* (Ebert, 2008), Thulung diumla calls it *nagidin agidin* (Allen, 2012).¹⁰

3.4. Chanting Pellam: Inscribing History into the Landscape

Gurungnimba chanted the following *pellam*:

Minangsa (humankind) was created;
This *minangsa* gave birth to Sudahang; and Sudahang to Maguhang;
ei Maguhang gave birth to Sabahang, and Sabahang gave birth to three *minagsa* (humans);
ei ei The eldest son established Maha China;
ei ei Sarumbang (the second eldest son) went to the East and established Japan and Burma;
ei ei Seven sons were born to Yangsarumba;
ei ei he gave birth to seven sons; two of them departed from *Saikhuwa and Sadiya*;¹¹
ei ei ei the youngest two sons stayed in the Tarai region, Kochay-Mechay;
ei ei the eldest son took Dhudha Koshi as his share and followed Dudh Koshi and established Solukhombuwan
ei Second eldest son took Tamor as his share and followed Tamor and established Limbuwan;
Yansarumba (the third eldest son-Yamphu) got Arun as his share and followed Arun and established Yamphuwan.

As will be seen in the *pellam* above, Gurungnimba Yamphu *pellam* encompasses pan-Mongol identity. According to the *pellam*, Chinese, Japanese, Burmese and Eastern Kirati are the descendants of common ancestor- Sabahang. As the *pellam* describes, Sabahang had three sons; among them the eldest son went towards China and established Maha China. The second son went to East and established Japan and Burma. The third gave birth to seven sons. Among them, the eldest brother (Khombu) followed Sunkoshi and Dudhkoshi. Second brother (Limbu) followed Tamor Koshi and Kabeli route. The third son, Yamphu followed

Arun-Barun route. The youngest two brothers (Kochaya-Mechya, Danuwar and Dhimal) stayed in the Tarai region. Gurngnimba's *pellam* shows ancestral (origin) affinities not only with Kirati, but also with Chinese, Japanese and Burmese. In this way, it shows that the seven sons of Sabahang set off their journey to north in search of unsettled places and established their territory.

Regarding the question why the ancestors set off their journey from *khokwaluṅ* to north? Khasinimba chanted *pellam*:

ei there, in *khokwaluṅ*, was no pace for living for human;
ei ei so, our ancestors set off their journey from *khokwaluṅ* following River path in search of a place for living;
ei from *kunjani dem, madaye dem, nagaye dem, waksuye dem, phokma dem*,¹² ancestors set off their journey;
ei though, humans were created, there was no place for dwelling;
 So, they set off their journey from Tarai in search of place;

In Khasinimba's version, the ancestors set out their journey from *khokwaluṅ* because there was no dwelling place. Therefore, they set off their journey following river paths in search of unsettled places. The following *pellam* chanted by Krishna Bahadur describes the travels of ancestors from the Tarai region.

KB¹³: *Khokwa Pappa* and *Ma?ma* (Paruhang and Sumnima) created five brothers and two sisters.¹⁴ They gathered in *yangli* (Tarai 'N') and started their journey towards northward from there.¹⁵ They continued their journey. At one place, called Makwarung dem/Phikwarung dem,¹⁶ *Phikwarung Pappa?*, *Phikwarung M?mye?* closed their path. When they requested *Phikwarung Pappa* to let them go upward, the Pappa commanded them to sacrifice their sisters (*hiṅwa*) if they wanted to go further up. Immediately, they caught a *wiwinjrokwa sowā*¹⁷ (Chibrike 'N') and sacrificed it to Phikwarung Pappa telling that the bird is their sister. Then, the *Pappa* (ancestor like god) became content and let them go. The five brothers worshiped him and the *Pappa* blessed them for their successful journey. These five brothers and the two sisters reached at Barachhetra.¹⁸

They rested there for some days. During that time, the two sisters were said to have gone down to Tarai to fetch oil. At Barachhetra, the four brothers divided the River tracts as their shares: *tummi wawa* (eldest brother) got the Dudh Koshi and Sunkoshi as his share, *Hangsarumba*¹⁹ (second eldest brother) got Tamor and Kabeli Koshi, and *Rungsarumba*²⁰ (third eldest brother) got Arun River. But when the four brothers were dividing their shares, their sisters had gone to Tarai. When the sisters came back, they did not find their own shares. They came to know that their brothers did not separate shares to them. As they divided, the elder brother (Khombu) followed Dudh Koshi and Sunkoshi and established *Khombuwan*. Similarly, *Hangsarumba* (Limbu) followed the course of Tamar Koshi and established *Limbuwan*. *Rungsarumba* (Yamphu) waited for their sisters and followed the course of Arun and established *Yamphuwan* (present territory). *Yungsarumba* (the fourth-born son) went to foreign country (out of these river courses) and became *Nepahang*.²¹ For some reasons, the *Syakpa* (the youngest) returned back to Yangli (Tarai) and followed the course of Mechi and settled around. The two sisters followed their Yamphu brother. These two sisters got married to *Chupchihang* at Chupchikmi dem.²² While following the course of the Arun, the Kashi Papa (Yamphu) came straight up to *Sambahang dem* (Lhasa in Tibet).

The above *pellam* suggests that the Kirati ancestors set off their journey from Tarai *khokwaluṅ* before settling in the present territory. They set off their journey in search of dwelling place. After walking along the river path, they arrived at Chatara, where the five brothers departed: Khombu ancestor followed Sunkoshi and Dudh Koshi and established Khombuwan; Limbu ancestor followed Tamro Koshi and Kabeli and established Limbuwan; Yamphu ancestor followed Arun-Barun and established Yamphuwan; and the youngest brother (Kochaya-Mechya, Danuwar and Dhimal) returned back to Tarai and followed Mechi River and stayed in the Tarai region.

Figure-4: Arun River and Hedangna

The *pellam* also shows link of origin of Yamphu with other Kirati groups and Kochya-Mechya, Danuwar and Dhimal. Dor Bahadur Bista (2004 [1967]) has also noted similar Dhimal oral story that shows Limbu and Dhimal are brother clan groups.²³ Such migration myth is a common feature among the Kirati groups. However, myths of other Kirati groups seem silent about Yamphu. For instance, according to Nicolette (2006), Kulung myth talks about four brothers- Khombu, Limbu, Menho and Mertup who set off their journey from near Kashi. Here, the two brother groups Khombu and Limbu can be identified but the other two Menho and Mertup are not explained to whom they represent today.

Therefore, Kulung myth does not talk about Yamphu ancestor.²⁴ Similar case exists among Mewahang and Lohorung Rai. Though Yamphu *pellam* claims that Yamphu ancestor followed the Arun path from Baharchhetra, the migration myths of Mewahang and Lohorung

do not accept this. Mewahang *muddum* says that Mewahang ancestor followed Arun from Chatara (Gaenszle, 2000).²⁵ Gaenszle has portrayed Mewahang as the forefather of Yamphu and Lohorung. According to him, "Mewahang is the forefathers of the Rai groups of Arun Valley" (2000:274).

On the other hand, Lohorung *pe-lam* tells that Lohorung ancestor followed Arun from Chatara (Hardman, 2000). In the case of Lohorung, Gurungnimba told me the following narrative:

That Yamphu boy went to fishing in the *iwa* (Arun). He had fishing net. *Swattai!* When the body casted the net into the Arun, he caught a Lohoro (a stone rolling-pin) into the net. *hui*, he threw the Lohoro into the middle of the Arun. Again he casted the net into the Arun, but this time he tried in different place (khewa 'Y'), but again he caught the same Lohoro. The boy said, "*thetterika, mabachain parne haina*, why is this stone all the time?" He again tried in a different place, but the result was the same – Lohoro instead of fish. It was three times he got the lohoro into his net. Then he kept the Lohoro into his bag and he casted the net. This time he got fish into his net. Then he knew that the Lohoro was the sign of good luck.

He brought the Lohoro with him at home and kept in a place. The next day, he went out for working. In the evening, he came back from his work. He was surprise what he found that the meal was ready. He asked himself, "Who might be this guy who cooked me food? Again the next day he went out for working and came back in the evening. When he reached at home, the meal was ready. Ah ha! He said, "Who prepared this meal for me?"

After some day, he hid nearby his house to look who was the person who was preparing the meal for him. After a while, he saw a *tik tik ma rani* (a beautiful queen) coming out from the Lohoro. Immediately, the boy ran to the house and caught the queen. He asked the queen, "Who are you?" She replied, "You don't know, I often fall into your net to be your wife. Let us be husband and wife" So, the offspring from them are called Lohorung. They are our own brother.

The most interesting aspect among all these is that none of their *pellam* or *pe-alm* or *muddum* tells us about the origin of each other but each of them claims as the descendants of the primordial ancestor who got Arun Valley as his property and followed the Arun. This suggests that the Yamphu, Lohorung and Mewahang are the descendants of the ancestor who followed the Arun, they are the very recent split off clan groups from the common ancestor. At the time of primordial split off four brothers at Barahachhetra, there was only one ancestor

who followed Arun path. This argument is supported by recent studies on Lohourng and Mewahang, which shows a clear link between these three groups. Gaenszle writes, "the fact, we repeatedly came across indications that the Mewahang are closely related to the Yamphu and Lohorung, and many details support the supposition that the former split off from the latter, and not vice versa" (Gaenszle, 2000:279).

Thus, the question of who had followed Arun is just politics. Establishing oneself senior (descendants of the primordial ancestor who followed Arun) to other group has some symbolic significance of seniority – who found the Arun Valley as the property. Among the Kirati groups, there is a tradition that a person who is senior in terms of age has special benefits in social functions and rituals.²⁶

As concerned with politics of seniority, here once again, I would like to quote Khasinimba, his version regarding in the case of Bantawa and Athapahariya Rai. He said, "So, they don't have *Wan*. You know, what *Wan* means? *Wan* means, they (Bantawa and Athapahariya) did not follow River path." This shows that *pellam* has political implications. While in the field, I heard that most often such issues becomes a topic of great debate among Kirati groups in social gatherings.

I interacted with Mewahang and Lohorung Rai informants and they also unanimously agree that Yamphu, Mewahang and Lohorung are the descendants of a common ancestor. The politics of claiming to be the descendants of the ancestor who followed Arun has bearing on the event that three brothers divided three rivers - Dudh Koshi Tamor and Arun - their share at Barahachhetra. This past has a role to play in the present day politics of identity which I will discuss in some detail in chapter six. Here, I have just mentioned it since this chapter is focused only with some common themes oral tradition of Kirati. A common notion Kirati oral tradition shares is the concept of the origin place and ancestral migration following the river path. The notion of *khokwalun* is found in other Kirati groups but known

in different terms (See Gaenszle, 2000; Nicolette, 206; Hardman, 2000). The ancestors started their journey from *khokwaluŋ* and departed from Barahachhetra.

Yamphu believe that *khokwaluŋ* is located under the soil. According to *pellamdangba* and *mangba*, it is situated under seven levels down the soil.²⁷ Some informants use *khokwaluŋ* to refer to Kashi and so does other Kirati. However, Yamphu are not certain of where the *khokwaluŋ* is exactly located in Kashi. There exists ambiguity among them.

The *pellam* says, in the time of origin (*Shiri?kwa 'Y'*), there were seven brothers and two sisters. Among them, two youngest brothers settled down in the Tarai. Yamphu believe that Koche-Meche and Dhimals are descendants of the youngest brothers, and thus in Yamphu view, they are clan brothers. In this sense, Yamphu migration *pellam* gives Yamphu an overarching shared identity with other Kirat groups. In what follows, Gurungnimba describes migration of Yamphu ancestors who returned back to the present place from Lhasa. Gru²⁸: In Kharta, Tibet, Yamphu married Mayakni (a Tibetan girl) and got two sons. Then he decided to come back.²⁹ They set off their journey to North. From Kharta, they came to Popti.³⁰ In Popti, they did some rituals and took the oath that they would stay in the place where they would find two things: *sam?ma* and *phuru* (stick and dozing mug). So they did *hyanjrungrma* (prayed to god) in Rudanŋ pond in Popti and let the *sam?ma* and *phuru* be carried away by the stream. Immediately, the *sam?ma* and *phuru* vanished.³¹ After that the two brothers followed the *sam?ma-phuru* travelling *makkham lam* (land way): they travelled Khartalung dem³² to Poptiyuŋ dem. From the Poptiyuŋ dem, they came to Pangdok dem, Pangdok dem to Damdamuk dem, Damdamuk dem to Oktiŋa dem.³³ In Syaksila, they saw the *sam?ma-phuru* spinning around in a pond of Okteŋwa spring. They looked around the area whether it was suitable or not for them to live. They did not like the place.³⁴ Again, they did *hyanjrungrma* praying *Tanđutuba-Tanđuma?ma* (Paruhang and Sumnima) for another place, and solemnly pledged

themselves to stay where the *sam?ma-phuru* would reappear. The two brothers kept following the *sam?ma-phuru*. They came to *asiñyak dem* (Shyaksila); from *asiñyak dem*, they further came down to *gongu dem* (above Baklek). From *gongu dem*, they came to *nokluñna dem*³⁵ where the two brothers built a memorial in their parents' name, Mani. After building that Mani, the two brothers split off at that point. The elder brother was Seppa and his brother Mennawa. The Seppa went South-West where he demarcated the present territory attached with Noklung *chawa* and founded present village Seduwa. Today, this place where they split off is called Seppa *lamjoñ* (also known as Mane Danda). The village's name was derived from Seppa. The younger brother came straight down to Rudanñ (now Hedangna). Rudanñ was a thick forest which used to be the home of tigers. No human presence. So, he claimed up a peepal tree (*pyapolin* 'Y'). He seated on a branch like *tukuwama* and looked around for *sam?ma-phuru*. He first looked at a spring called Pyakkhim whether *sam?ma-phuru* was spinning around. He saw the *sam?ma-phuru* spinning around, not in Pyakkhim spring, but in a small Rudanñ pond which was just under the peepal. Then, he looked around the area whether it was suitable or not for him to settle. Mennawa decided to settle down there as *sam?ma-phuru* were spinning in Rudanñ pond and also found the place suitable for settling down.³⁶

Mennawa saw *sam?ma-phuru* spinning around the Rudanñ pond. At the same time other four clan groups also arrived there who were heading toward the north from Tarai.³⁷ Since then, they became five clans *tubaji* (ancestors) of Yamphu. They were Khombuwa Tyangsa (Sunakhari Lambuwa Chawadangba)³⁸, Prithya Tyangsa (Kripanwa Chawa apphokdangba), Mangbakhim (Shovaya Noklung Chawadanba), Tingyak and Miring (Phembulawa Chawa Apphokdangba) and Mennawa (Pyakkhim Chawa).³⁹ They became *hanghang* (very happy) when they got together. They danced

and sang with joys. After that the Rudañ spring was named *Hanghong chawa* as a common to all five clan groups. The *ñajipasing* (five ancestors) laid out the paving five stones for each to mark their arrival to the land.⁴⁰ They built the five water ponds for the five clans. They performed *chawa* ritual delightfully for peace and prosperity. They again danced and sang with joys. Then they collected and asked the four *lawas* go along with them. They established the present village. They carried up *charawa* (the tokens of prosperity) in a basket to the *Maktokhim* (house). The mother at the *Maktokhim* (house) received the *charawa* and they placed them upstairs, in the attice where the rice storage was located. After putting them there, they sprinkled millet beer around the ancestor shrine. In this way, the five ancestors - Khombuwa Tyangsa, Prithya Tyangsa, Mangbakhim, Tingyak and Mennawa settle down and had a good time.⁴¹

The *pellam* above recounts ancestral travelling from lowland Tarai, one Yamphu ancestor, Mennawa reached as far up as the Kharta of Tibet, where he intermarried with a Tibetan woman (*maye?ma* "Y").⁴² After five to six generation in Kharta, two Yamphu ancestors decided to set off their journey to the South. On the other hand, other four clan groups: Khombuwa Tyangsa, Prithya Tyangsa, Mangbakhim, Tingyak came up to Hedangna who did not reach up to Lhasa. Gurungnimba revealed that until some year ago, Yamphu used to be associated with Lhomi Bhote. Although Lhomi are distinct in many ways from Yamphu, their clan names are similar to Yamphu. For instance, Yamphu clans such as *Mangbakhim*, *Mennawa*, *Thikkepa* and *chaba* are also found in Lhomi. An informant from Shyaksial, Parbu Lama, told me that Limbu, Rai Kirati and Bhote are the descendants of common ancestor. He said:

We call Hedangne Rai as *thikkepa*. People say Hedangna, but this is *Rudanglamjoñ*. In our tongue, we call Rudaña. (January, 2014)

Likewise, another informant from Honghong, to whom I met at Gola, told me:

Rai and Limbu are our brothers (*Daju Bhai ho ni 'N'*). We are das (ten) Limbu, das Rai Kirati and das Bhote. We are the descendants of three brothers. The elder brother settled down in Bhote Khola, so he became Bhote. The second elder brother settled little down area (Pahad 'N'), so they are Limbu. The younger brother settled down in Tarai, they are Rai Kirati.

(Interview with Temba Bhote, January, 2014)

Yamphu often admit that the Bhotes are their clan group. However, due to some negative connotations attached to Bhote term⁴³ Yamphu feel uneasy be associated with Lhomi Bhote. Lohorung Rai also refers Lhomi as their clan brother. In Hardman's study of Lohorung, she writes:

...'brothers' for the Lohorung include all those they call Khombu living to the west of the Arun all the Yakthumba (or Limbu), all the Yakkhaba as well as the Mech-Koche and Dhimal of the Tarai. Lohorung also accept as brothers a clan calls Lohorunge of the Tibetan-speaking Lhomi of the Upper Arun who they refer to as Syamdang 'chi' (might be Samba chi instead of Syamdang chi). ... Nevertheless, they still refer to them as a – 'brother' clan (Hardman, 2000:116).

Figure-5: Seppa Lamjong, the Place Where the two Brothers Split off in Mindum. The Manis in the picture are believed to be built by the two brothers – Seppa and Mennawa.

Having discussed the genealogical implications of *pellam* as it is indicated above I now turn to analyze how the *pellam* inscribes ancestral past into the landscape that in turn gives Yamphu *a sense of sovereign people* to claim rights to the land.

Figure-6: Ancestral Migration Route and Territory

It is evident that anthropological studies about myths and oral tradition have moved beyond literary and psychological analysis of myths and oral tradition to explore their socio-historical and political values in preserving the memory of important experiences. I use anthropological theories of landscapes to understand how *pellam* constitutes writing history into the landscape and thereby Yamphu realize *a sense of place*. In Santos–Granero’s (2005:174) view anthropology has recognized "the importance of landscape as another means of encapsulating and transmitting historical memory in both literary and non-literate societies." In the same way, according to Guo's view, landscape can serve as "a key component of how people perceive, memorize and represent history (i.e. their history), and how they configure their sense of selves" (Guo, 2003:193). He is of the opinion that landscape symbolizes the ancestral past by connecting people to the land, and thus land ownership. His work on Langalanga of Solomon Islands has illustrated how ancestral trees “in arguing the authenticity of their "'history' for' the claims of ownership" (2003:196).

Further, anthropological studies on Amazonian areas show that Amazonian indigenous peoples write past history into the landscape through "topographic writing" (Santos-Granero, 1998:140). He argues that topographic writing is based on topograms (features of landscape) which are imbued with myths, oral traditions and rituals. Consequently, topograms, as linguistic signs signify an historical event, ancestral footprints or actions and express a concept. Thus, in his view, "topograms have their present configuration as a result of the past transformative activities of human or superhuman beings" (ibid.). Thus, when such topograms are arranged in a sequential manner, they form topographs. The topograms and topographs into which all the myths and rituals get inscribed write the past history into the landscape. Drawing on his ethnographic data from Yanesha, Santos-Granero argues that while writing history into the landscape, Yanesha attribute "a transcendental reality to particular elements in the landscape" and "they transform these salient natural elements into signs that recall past events" (ibid.).

As we have noted in the *pellam* above, among the Yamphu, the ancestral migration from Tarai to Lhasa and back to present territory reflect past events. They followed Arun path. The different place names marked by ancestral foot prints recapitulate the ancestral migration from Tarai to Lhasa Tibet. For example, while returning from Tibet, two Yamphu ancestors set off their journey from Khartalung to Poptiyun, then to Pangdok, followed by Damdamuk, then to Oktiṅa, and finally at Rudan, the present place. These places can be identified even today. Guo notes that "naming is more than giving a linguistic sign to a particular place or landmark: the names usually record historical events" by which people become connected to particular place (2003:196).

In the *pellam* above, it seems that the four ancestors were also travelling following Arun path and met Mennawa at the Rudan. When they met, they became happy (*hang hang* 'Y'). As a consequence, they named Rudan spring as *Hanghong chawa*. According the

pellam, the five Yamphu ancestors settled down there. They established the village. They laid out the paving five stones for each by building five water ponds in Rudaj spring. Even today, we can observe these five pillars of stones in Hedangna. Because of this ancestral activity, the Yamphu ancestors have been transformed into *Hanghong chawa*. Therefore, *Hanghong chawa*, five ponds and erected stone pillars, Arun River have become important sacred sites (topograms) where Yamphu special rituals take place. The fact is that among Yamphu, each individual clan group possesses a particular *chawa* from where the groups have emerged. Yamphu are obliged to be associated with their respective *chawa* to communicate with their ancestors. The Yamphu believe that there is not a single Yamphu individual who does not possess a *chawa*. In their view, Yamphu life cannot be imagined without *chawa*. Today, these ponds and stone pillars have become key symbol that demarcates local boundaries, codifies the memory of the past and hence, signifies Yamphu ancestral land.

It is, therefore, clear that the place names, Arun River and *Hanghong chawa* into which *pellam* is inscribed have become the elements of landscape, and thus they become topograms and topographas, and are used to write Yamphu history into the landscape. Hence, the landscape gives Yamphu a *sense of place*. It provides Yamphu with the philosophical ground to imagine as *sovereign people* of the present territory. That is, in order to legitimize their claim over the territory, Yamphu describe and relieve how their ancestors came to this place first.

However, "the relationships between landscape and ancestral past can go beyond much more than representation and symbolization" (Guo, 2003:195). Guo is of the opinion that apart from this, "supernatural power is involved in the relationships between ancestral history and landscape" (2003:196). Studying Langalanga people, Guo maintains that "the relationship with the ancestors (*agalo*) through sacrifices to secure land rights and prosperity" (ibid.). In the case of Yamphu ancestral involvement is fundamental for making *a sense of*

place and belongingness. *Chawa* as the symbol of ancestral continuity in the present land is identical to Langalanga because Yamphu observe *chawa* rite to maintain their land rights and prosperity in the present landscape.

3.5. Journey to the Ancestral World

Now let us consider another *pellam* to see how Yamphu escorts a deceased's soul to the place of ancestors. The following *pellam* was chanted by Gurungnimba in a non-ritual context. It has two parts: first he takes away the dead soul to ancestral world (*naulakha shilakha*), and second, he takes away the evil spirits (Sehe Sindi 'N') down to the place of origin *kho?waluy* (Kashi 'N') and delivers it to the Kashi ancestors. By this *pellam*, I argue that the places and landscapes are conceived to exist and give a sense of their identity as connected to the land and territory.

Yamphu have a special ritual path through which they lead the soul of deceased to the ancestral world. In the evening of the final purification day, a group of village elders (*pellamdangba* together with other knowledgeable persons and other interested people who wish to listen to the *pellam*) gather at the house of the deceased's family. Here, a *pellamdangba* escorts the dead soul to the ancestral world by chanting *pellam*. This is often done chanting *pellam*. Gurungnimba chanted me the following *pellam* that leads to deceased's soul to the world of ancestors.

he he he ino inoe inoenoe respected elders;
i ei friends, ladies and gentlemen, young girls and boys, grand fathers and grandmothers,
we (like you and like I) are gathered here in the name of the deceased: (deceased name);
and you all placed me as *pellamdangba* here, I know nothing about *pellam*.
I don't know the content of the *pellam*, I don't know the way of chanting *pellam*,
if I could not chant *pellam* properly, if my tongue slept, I request you to keep my soul
held high

i ei in the name of the past,
i ei in *rumahan dem*, pond of water was created;
On top of pond of water, *dumsingla* sprang up;

The wind broke the branches of *dumsinḡla*, made the leaves fallen on the water from which the earth was formed;

i ei on the earth, the stones were formed by means of the clash between cloud and wind;
i ei there sprang up *Pitta Sambok* (cynodon dactylon) (Dubo 'N');
on the *pitta sambok*, the *ulaminam tankhiyanam* (Shiva and Parbati 'N') created human and became soul of human being;
legs and hands began to develop; eyes gained its sights; ear started to function; and hair began to grow.

i ei legs and hands began to develop;
he or she (the deceased) visited the *namakya?ma dem* (the east); also visited *yanliluḡ dem* (Tarai); and also visited *shambaluḡ dem* (North, Bhote muluk);
i ei ei you visited; *i* like *lenjuamaḡok pemmalonḡliasa*, *sisiamadok thyanḡmuisa*

*i ei pappo*⁴⁴
i ei, now, in your name, you have followed the path of dead; *cugibula mehubendi* (you are dead now);
now, as you have gone to that path, a person like me who knows nothing, who is known noting, like a dumb, is going to take you to the world of ancestors, with a load of snacks;
i ei I take you with gold *akchheta*, lightning gold *diyo*, and coins;
i ei loading leg of pig, *raksi*, and millet beer in the basket, I take you to that place;
i ei lahai (name of the deceased)! *riḡgisumba*, *coi?numba khenjasimba* (You were good looking, and loved by all and kind person);
ei let's go to the place of moon; the place of snow; let's go to *gonḡu* carrying this load of snacks;
lahai let's go! I take you to your house, in the place of dead!

i ei lahai, let's go!
i ei I walked and arrived at the porch (sikuwa 'N'); Walking down I arrived *panluḡ dem*, and then to yard where cynodon dactylon (*pittasambukhaba*);
from *pittasambukhaba* to *thesiḡbu*; walk from the place where we find *saptiḡbu*; walk from the place where *kokiliḡ kha?waliḡ* are found; walk from where *uraliḡ* grow; walk from the place where *waibuliḡkhaba* are found;

i ei walking with a walking stick; wiping the sweat off;
I take you the place of the dead;
i yo pappo, let's go!

i ei lahai riḡgisummo, *coi?nummo khenjasibo*;
i ei let's move to *mendokha dem*;
taking rest in *mendokha dem*; having a breadth and rest, begin to walk towards *tobkhonḡi dem*;

i ei walk from *bokhonḡi dem*⁴⁵ to *sebukya dem*⁴⁶
i ei let's have a breadth and rest at this place; I breath and rest;
i ei after resting;

lahai let's move!

let's move! walk from the place of *omya?luŋ*; keep on walking from the place of *thakpaluŋ*; walk from the place where we find *wabuliŋ*, then from the place where *makpuliŋ* grows, then from the place of *aŋgeri dhaŋgeri*; and walk from the place of *cinjakhabaŋ yobaŋ*;

i ei ei walk to *deurali dem* (above Baklek);
let's breadth and take rest here; after having rest, let's move from here too;
i ei ei let's walk through the place of *kokpaliŋkha*;
let's walk through *samghyaŋliŋkha*; let's walk through the place of *baŋlaliŋkhaba*;⁴⁷
i ei ei, from there, we arrived at *gaikharka*;⁴⁸
let's walk from here to *larewaba bororathiya goŋgu dem*;⁴⁹ now, let's breadth and take rest at this place;

i ei after taking rest, let's begin to walk; walk to the place where we find *sunapati bhairopati*; where we find *bukkiya cimlakhaba*;
look! Barun River following down!

i ei, now from *tokcikya dem*,⁵⁰ we are heading towards *poptiyuŋ goŋgu dem*;
i ei let's take a breadth and rest here;

now, this is the place from where we leave the soil (earth);
Let's move to the place of wind;
from here also, walk to the place of cloud;
walk from here to *thaŋsirijluŋ dem*;
from here also walk to *pha?maru dem* (a place from where *pellamdangba* and the deceased separate);
i ei let's take a breadth and rest here;

lahai from this place, you *riŋicumba, coiknumba, khenjasiŋba lahai!*
i ei right from here, you go alone; carry the load of millet beer, *raksi*, leg of pig;
be happy to go to the world of ancestors; don't fell sorrow, distress
i ei from this place, climb up to the place of ancestors, the place of moon and the place snow with the help of this golden ladder;
i ei i yo pappo (a way of expressing lament), the deceased went!

i ei while returning, I felt so distress, grieving because of separation with the deceased, at the place of dead;
lahai riŋigisumbo, coiksumbo khenjasiŋbo
i ei carry all the misfortunes with you
i ei carry the soul of dead with you;
i I, pellamdangba, will carry the my soul, the soul of living;

i ei i yo pappo the deceased went to the place of ancestors;
I returned from the place of dead;
i ei I have blocked the way so that the deceased would not return and follow me into the world of living;

i ei I also have destroyed the golden ladder;
then, I have returned back with my living *lawa* (Sato 'N')

i ei I arrived at the place of separation; all *lawas*, don't get lost: *lawas: bombalawa sisilawa, sapsa? lawa, hindumlawa*, and *thawalawa*;
Don't leave me! Be with me!

i ei now, I returned, I arrived at the place of wind, and then to the place of soil (*poptiyun makhkham dem*);
here, I have blocked the trail and misled the deceased;
I return back from *oygolun dem* to *tamdamma dem*;
Then, I crossed the Barun;
I arrive at Gola, then to Thakrambu and to Simma;
from Simma to Mane, then to *yard*, and then to Sikuwa;
presence father! I took *ringisumba, coiknumbago* to the place of moon, to the place of snow, and the world of ancestors;
now, I have come back home;
i ei presence mother (gharpati ama 'N')!
i ei father (gharpati ba 'N')! In this house, in this house of living, I have come back;

Again, he goes down to Kashi to deliver the evil spirit (Sehe Sindi 'N'), which is believed to have caused the death to Kashi ancestor so that the evil spirit would not again wander in the village. In this time, he follows Arun path, the same route as travelled by the ancestors. He chanted me the following *pellam*.

3.6. The Journey to Khokwalun (Kashi?)

i ei since you have asked me to deliver the evil spirit (*miriphakwa tanjuphakwa 'Y'*) (the Sehen Sindi that might cause another death in the village);
I step on balcony, then to *panlun dem*, then on, *Pitta Sambok* (the yard of grass, cynodon dactylon (Dubo 'N'));
I go to Kashi to sail the evil spirit;

lahai, I set off to sail and to deliver the evil spirit;
i ei I cross the *hanghong chawa*;
i ei I bowed down my head to *hang hong chawa*;
after crossing the *han hon chawa di ho*;
i ei I sailed the evil spirit like *homsa*
i ei I walked through *sojsowa lam yo*
after walking, I passed confluences of Induwa, Numkhuwa, Neguwa as *homsa*, swims in the river;

i ei I crossed confluences of Kasuwa , Isuwa , and Kushuwa ;
at Kusuwa , I have blocked water with stones, soil and woods to make a lake;
i lahai after making a lake, *ho i ei* crossed confluences of Mukhuwa , Wikhuwa , Apsuwa and Kushuwa;
i ei I crossed confluences of Chirkhuwa, Sanjkuwa, Sobhaya, Piluwa, and Kewalun;

then, I crossed confluences of Maṅmaya, Lewati and Tamor;
from Lewati and Tamor confluence, I cross Haṅrukha and Dudh Koshi;
after crossing Dudh Koshi confluence;
i ei I arrived at Sukoshi confluence;
from there, I moved further and crossed Tamakoshi confluence and reached at
Barahamana temples (Barahachhetra)
in Bahrachhetra, I worshiped the gods, and I walk through forests path (*thaknam lam 'Y'*);

while walking through the forests, a tiger blocked my path;
i ei poor me, I am sacred;
i ei poor me, then climbed up in a tree to save my life;
I sit like wool on a branch of the tree;
while sitting on the tree, the sun set;
as I am sitting on the tree, *namudya* bite me;
i as the cock crows, the morning started to fall;
as the morning started to fall, I looked down; the tiger claws the bottom, and is trying to
climb up;
I feel scared, became fearful;

I also began to feel angry (with the tiger);
i ei I, then, took bow and arrow⁵¹ and shut the tiger;
the arrow stroke at the right womb; the tiger ran away;

i ei I climb down and reached at Saptakoshi;
from Saptakoshi, I moved to Saptasamundar, then to *Gangalung dem* (Ganga), and then
to Kashi;

"Kashi ancestors, and elders, I salute you."
i ei lahai "Kashi ancestors, I bow down before you."
i ei from my village, house mother (deceased's house), house father has sent me here
with a load of the evil spirit (*tanphakwa mirikphakwa 'Y'*);
i ᳵ lahai Kashi ancestor, I deliver the evil spirit to you;

"Please accept it."
i ei when Kashi ancestors accepted I felt very happy;
i ei lahai Kashi ancestors, now I want to return back;
there is no good harvest in my village;

lahai Kashi ancestors, "Please give me good harvest (caraway 'Y');"
i ei lahai "Give me *namkya᳚ma cam* (rice from east), *namama cam* (rice from west),
pyapulijcam (Ghaiya dhan 'N'), *yaṅliluj cam* (rice from Tarai), *shambaluj cam* (rice
north), *baluwa cam* (Kudure dhan 'N'), *syagaba cam* (Masino Kudure 'N'), *nagami cam*
(Kalo Marsi 'N'), *᳚ujbumi* (Andi dhan 'N'), *sigulij* (Seto Marsi 'N'), *supulij* (Kalo
Basane);"

i ei I loaded the good harvest; "I salute you; I bow down Kashi ancestors."
"I have come to fetch *phun᳚jiya phuj* (flowers and leaves as offerings) (Fulpati "N") for
my villagers as they have asked me for;"
so, "Give me *phun᳚jiya phuj*."
Kashi ancestors also gave me Fulpati. I loaded it;

i ei lahai Kashi ancestors,
let's depart;
lahai have good stay;

[Kashi Ancestor speaks of:]

i ei pellamdan̄ba, lahai, "go back to your village with load of *charawa* (good harvest);"
"take the *Fulpati* for your villagers and elders;"
lahai "carry the load of *charawa*, and go back to your village from River path;"

[He returns from Kashi]

i ei I collect *lawa phuwa u?ma*: Don't get lost *bombulawa*; don't get lost *sisilawa*; don't
get lost *sapsalawa*; don't get lost *hindumlawā*; and don't get lost *thawalawa*;
after that, I return back from Kashi;
from Kashi, I arrived to *Gangalung dem* (Ganga), then to *Sapta Samundra*, then to *Sapta
Koshi* (*Saptahongma* 'Y') then to *Barahachhetra*;
at *Barahachhetra*, I worshiped to the gods;

I return from *soṅsuwa lam* (River path)

i ei after worshiping the gods at Barahachhetra, I arrive at Tama Koshi, then to Suna
Koshi dem, then to Dudha Koshi dem, and then to Haṅrukkha dem;
from Haṅrukkha dem, I walked to Lewati and Tamor, then to Maṅmaya, then to Kewaliṅ ,
then to Piluwa, Sobhaya, Saṅkhuwa, Chirkhuwa, Apsuwa, and Kushuwa ;

when I arrived at Kusuwa, I got very tired of carrying the load of *charawa*;
I became exhausted; I even can't move my legs and hands;
I feel dreamlike; I feel uneasy;
I feel insane like;
I even can't move my legs and hands;

i ei pellamdan̄bo, we stupid, sent you to carry down the evil spirit to Kashi from *river
path*;
you handed over the evil spirit to the Kasi ancestor;
after hand-over, you also begged *charawa* for us from the Kashi ancestor;
you came back from *soṅsuwa lam*;
when you arrived at Kushuwa, you may have felt thirsty; you may have become
breathless!
you will be served with snacks; then you will regain your strength, you will move your
legs and hands; you will come in clear sense;

mother (Gharpati ama 'N')! you have come with snacks to serve me; my legs and hands
began to regain power; my breath also came;

lahai house mother! wish you all the best;

i ei house mother! house father! be victorious, be *kripa* (kind), may *raja and kaji* in your
favor;
my your friends in your favor;
you may bright as an Idol;
my live like Done; may live and have strength of thunder bolt;

i ei I removed the woods, stones and soil;
I let the water out of the lake;

with the load of *charawa*, I arrive at Ishuwa and Kushuwa;
Kushuwa and *Kashuwa*;
I arrived at Numkhuwa, Neguwa and Hanghong;
I arrive at *chawa*, then yard, then *paṅlu dem* and;
I arrive at *ombu dem*
house mistress, I begged *charawa* from Kashi ancestor, and have carried up the load of
charawa;
take this *charawa* to upstairs;
i ei may grain store full of grains;

In the *pellam* Gurungnimba first takes away the dead soul to the land of dead ancestors (*sigumbu dem 'Y'*). He starts his journey from the house and leads to north-west Himalaya region. Then, he walks through the places where *saptiṅbu*, *kokiliṅ khaḷwaliṅ*, *uraliṅ*, *waibuliṅkhaba*, *sebukya*, *omyaḷuṅ*, *thakpaḷuṅ*, *wabuliṅ*, *makpuliṅ*, *aṅgeri dhaṅgeri*, *cinjakhabaṅ*, *kokpaliṅkha*, *samghyaṅliṅkha* and *baṅlaliṅkhaba* (all these are names of grasses and plants and grazing lands). He walks through *Deurali* (the place a grazing land [kharka 'N'] located above Baklek), *Gaikharka* (this place is located near Deurali), *Larewaba Bororathiya* (this place is located below Barate and above Gaikharka), *sunapati bhairopati*, *bukkiya cimlalkhaba Tokcikya dem* (the place situated above Barathe, near Makalu Mount, the origin of Barun River). Then he crosses the Himalayan region and reaches to *poptiyuṅ goṅgu* in Lhasa. From there, he gives up the soil trail and flies in the air and enters into the place of wind, then into the place of cloud and finally reaches at the place of separation. From there, with the help of a ladder, he sends off the deceased's soul to the world of ancestors. After sending deceased's soul, he returns and follow different path so that the deceased soul do not follow him. He walks down through *poptiyuṅ goṅgu*, *oṅgoluṅ*, *tamdamma*, Gola, Thakrambu, Simma, Mane danda, and arrives at the house.

Moreover, the *pellam* also indicates that while going down to Kashi, he follows the Arun path. He first walks down to *Hanghong chawa* and then to Arun. He crosses the confluences of many tributaries such as Induwa, Numkhuwa, Neguwa, Kasuwa, Isuwa,

Kushuwa, Mukhuwa, Wikhuwa, Apsuwa, Chirkhuwa, Saṅkhuwa, Sobhaya, Piluwa, Kewaluṅ, Maṅmaya, Lewati, Tamor, Haṅrukha, Dudhakoshi, Sukoshi, Tamakoshi, Barahachhetra, Saptakoshi, Sapta Samundar, Gangalung, and to Kashi. He returns from the same path and returns to the house.

As we see, the *pellam* is full of place names, river names and different routes that are believed to have travelled by the ancestors. Anthropological studies on myths remains us that naming places in myths and narrations shape human thought process making a live connections with the ancestors. In an article entitled, *Speaking with Names: Language and Landscape among the Western Apache*, Keith Basso (1988) persuasively argues that in any community, people appropriate physical environment through *placenames*. In his view, place names Apache people use today were given by their ancestors. Then, naming places orient Apache people's minds to "look "forward" into space," thus positioning them to "look "backward" in time," thus, naming places "cause them to travel in their minds" (1988:112). Ancestral places are infused with traditional life of Apache because "these places are full inseparable connection to specific localities, placenames may be used to summon forth an enormous range of mental and emotional associations – associations of time and space, of history and events, of persons and social activities, of oneself and stages in one's life" (1988:103).

Yamphu also believe that the place names and river names currently they use were given by the ancestors. The discussion with Yamphu elders reveals that the names of these places are chanted during Yamphu *pellam* because they believe that ancestors travelled from this route. They believe that the ancestors constantly went to those places for hunting and gathering and in search of food. This is why Yamphu remember these places and routes. We can argue that chanting the place names and river names in *pellam* what Basso suggests,

"acquires a capacity to evoke stories and images of the people who knew the places first" (1988:112).

Liffman argues the similar case among Waxaritari of Mexico. Wixaritari go to sacred trek to Wixarikuta which is situated in long distance from their heartland, to renew their land rights in the ancestral landscape (Liffaman, 2000). Among Wixarikuta, while doing the journey, "they identify with their ancestors, origins, and ancient practices so it is where they ultimately "root" their kei-settlement pattern" (2000:136).

Thus, when the listeners and *pellamdangba* go to the journey of ancestors, as I discussed above, Yamphu feel emotional association with their ancestors. They feel as if they are travelling through these places where ancestors had travelled. They as if they are standing in front of the ancestral place, as if they are taking rest and so on as ancestors did in the primordial time. By this, what the listeners and *pellamdangba* do is exactly the same as what Munn have argued among Apache that "by taking the ancestor's position, a viewer transforms an ancestral "there-then" into his/her own "here-now". Incorporated into the latter-day viewer's biography, ancestral events then become a particular form of "lived history"" (1992:113).

If we look at the *pellam*, we find that the tradition has endured for countless generations among the Yamphu. By chanting *pellam*, Yamphu imagine what Basso says in the case of Apache, "persons imagine themselves standing in front of a named site, they may imagine that they are standing in their "ancestors tracks"" (1988:112). If we argue in line with Basso, *pellam* shows the ancestral tracks and chanting *pellam* is to follow the ancestral path. Yamphu keep *pellam* because it evokes images of ancestors, emotional bound with ancestors. Therefore, when the places are chanted in *pellam*, they acquire a capacity to evoke sacred relations with ancestors, and thus Yamphu transforms themselves as sovereign people to the land. This is how Yamphu spatialize their identity as *jimi-bhumi* into the present

territory and thus, Yamphu and their landscape have become, borrowing Basso's term, "virtually as one" (1984:122).

Chapter Four

THE CHAWA: WE ARE FROM HERE AND THIS IS OUR ANCESTRAL LAND

In this chapter, I have examined *chawa* in some detail as local foci of self, territoriality and local identity among Yamphu. I have attempted to show how *chawa* displays a conspicuous visible material symbol which is instrumental to mark internal and local boundaries that are of greater significance among Yamphu. I also argue that *chawa* is used to define and legitimize the sovereignty of a certain number of human groups over a territory and its resources, which they can then exploit either separately or collectively, that these relations have the capacity to make these groups into a society. Thus, in this chapter, I seek to examine implications of such associations to understand indigenous notion of identity and territoriality. Moreover, I have examined how *chawa* enabled Yamphu to gain political space in the past, and how it enables them to create *social space* in the present. Now the question remains: How the concept of *chawa* evolved? How *chawa* came to be so fundamental among Yamphu? In short, I have examined the nexus of *chawa*, historicity and territoriality among Yamphu.

4.1. The Concept of Chawa: The Pukmara (The Origins)

Among Australian Aboriginal people, Morphy found that every landmarks and places are marked by ancestral actions. Morphy (1995:187) writes:

As elsewhere in Australia, the physical form of the earth is believed to have come into being through the actions of ancestral beings who travelled the earth from place to place, leaving evidence of their actions in the form of topographical features

An analogous conception can be drawn among Yamphu. The following episode of *pellam*, for instance, demonstrates how the concept of *chawa* emerged because of ancestral

actions in Hedangna. It is worth mentioning the episode of *the pellam* chanted by Gurnungnimba because it tells the way how Yamphu conceptualize the landscape at present.

i: ...ei..ei the younger brother came to Rudañ;
i: ...ei..i:....ei noinoyono oinoyonobañ (and so);
i: ...ei..ei he who came straight from terai to Lhasa and back;
he arrived at *pyakkhim chawa* and appropriated it, thus he became *hangba* (king) of the area;
he seated on the peepal tree (*Ficus religiosa*) like *tukuwama* (wool);
i: ...eu...ei while he was here;
Sunakhari Lambuwa Chawadangba also arrived there from terai;
i: ...ei..ei Sobhaya Nokluñ Chawadañba also arrived there;
i: ...ei..ei Phembulawa Chawa apphokdañba also arrived there;
i: ...ei..ei Kripauwa Chawa apphokdañba also arrived there;

then the five ancestors assembled there;
i: ...ei the five ancestors made five small ponds there;
i ei they became together and became happy;
i... ei.. ei they danced and sang with joys, they played *temmasing* and *ukmasing* (drum and cymbal like musical instrument) (Dhol and Jhyamta 'N');
they danced and sang with joys;
they performed *chawa* ritual;
they asked for the *charawa* (the tokens of prosperity) from (Rudañ spring) *chawa*;
they performed ritual and worshiped *chawa*;
they named the spring *Hanghong Chawa*;

The above excerpt is extracted from the *pellam* chanted by Gurungnimba. This *pellam* is about Yamphu root in the present land. The *pellam* provides authentic narrative of how Yamphu relationship with land and territory began and continue to exist. The *pellam* recalls the arrival of five ancestors in the place, *Hanghong Chawa*. This is the proof of how the ancestors came to the place and how they began to establish the village. Therefore, while doing *chawa* rite, requesting prosperity and fertility of the entire village, Yamphu worship *chawa* by calling "our great-great grandfather (*tubalabaji 'Y'*), you are the true owner of the land". According to the *pellam*, the five ancestors were: the ancestors of Khombuwa Tyangsa, Prithya Tyangsa, Mennawa, Tingyak and Mangbakhim. The place was uninhabited when they arrived and claimed the land. They inhabited the place and produce society. Today's Yamphu of Hedangna, therefore, owe a lasting debt to these five ancestors. After all the

pedigrees of *Hanghong chawa* come to stand for the history of the group itself. It is the control of *chawa* that legitimizes control of a locality. Since then *Hanghong chawa* is taken as an emblem of their clan history that symbolizes the authority of the bearer in certain area. From this sense, here *Hanghong chawa* signifies the first human arrival in the place when there was no homestead.

Since then *chawa* among Yamphu have played very significant role in identifying their ancestral lands. Land possession among Yamphu must be understood in terms of *chawa* and its relationship with landscapes. A Yamphu individual or a family do not automatically belong to this territory, they must actively articulate their relations with their ancestors through *chawa*. Therefore, to respect the ancestors, Yamphu still conduct *chawa* rite in their respective locality. As it was the source of water, the ancestors first settled and cultivated the land around. The *Hanghong chawa* cannot be alienated from the five clan groups because it continually places them in the landscape. The Yamphu belonging to these five clan groups are obliged to keep *Hanghong Chawa* with them as it evokes their origin and ancestral presence. In this sense, the *Hanghong Chawa* gives them an identity by connecting them together with ancestors and the land. In Yamphu view, their identity has rooted in the land by means of *chawa* since the time immemorial or the time when the cosmic and social order was first established and Yamphu people strongly believe their ancestors as the true owners of the land. From this point, *Hanghong Chawa* has become inseparable from the five clan groups, attaching them with the place, keeping them connected with one another and also with their ancestors. Thus the land they live today is inseparable from their lives. It is not only the case in Hedangna but in all Yamphu villages, we find similar local histories that a particular clan group associated with a specific *chawa* which I discuss about in detail in the following paragraphs.

As it is evident from the foregoing discussion that *chawa* denotes the spring from which the ancestors first drank water in the very beginning. Subsequently, they used it as a permanent source of water for irrigation. (Forbes, 1999; Hardman, 2000; Ganeszle, 2000; and Yamphu, 2007). It has been clear that a *chawa* associates a particular clan group to a particular locality such as the five clan groups are associated to Hedangna. Discussing the relationships between Aboriginal people, places, and ancestral past among Australian Aboriginal society, Howard Morphy argues that ancestral past lies at the heart of the Aboriginal society since it attaches the people to places (Morphy, 1995).

By the *pellam*, it has been clear that *chawa* is connected with the past, the origin of Yamphu, their society, and their ancestral actions. It is connected with the foundation of village and thus, has become a source of power. Because of this, *chawa* has been transformed into sacred for Yamphu. They believe that *chawa* plays vital role in the intelligence and psychological development of an individual Yamphu. In Yamphu view, an individual whom his or her *chawa* favors would become bright and genius. In this sense, for Yamphu, *chawa* is an internal force that plays a vital role in the development of personality of an individual and thereby brings prosperity among the clan groups. Only with the favor of *chawa*, an individual can become a *mangba* or *yadangba* or *pellamdangba* or *sakmiyonba*. Among Yamphu, human life is not possible without *chawa*. The person who is favored by *chawa* is believed to be very intelligent and influential one.

The following statement about *chawa* made by Man Bahadur Yamphu from a village Salbisaune has well captured the essentiality of *chawa* for Yamphu society. His idea about *chawa* is as follows:

Chawa navai ta thyappai no vayena, chawa mekning go yakmi go parai ayena. Imangdro kame? In Yamphu, without *chawa* one cannot do *mangani* (asking hands of a girl/engagement). Without *chawa* nothing comes into existence. There will be no way how to act in the society. Alas! how to keep *khamang* (pitri 'N'), how to do *yumang* (Bali puja 'N'), how to do *sammangs* (Dewa 'N'), how to establish marital relationship with other. So, for these reasons, ways of marriage come from *chawa*; *pellam* also originate

from *chawa*; *mangba's mindum* (mecchira 'Y') also originate from *chawa*; *bagdata mindum* also comes from *chawa*; *mindum* of death ritual also comes from *chawa*; Our clans such as *Kesa*, *Hanglemba*, *Mennwa*, *Khikkura*, *Khakkura* and so on are created by *chawa*; all humans (*Yakmi* 'Y') are one, but what differentiates and distinguishes us is *chawa*; we all Yamphu are one but *chawa* has divided us in different clans; *chawa* has made *kutumba* and made marriage possible; it is not us who created *kutumba*, but it is *chawa* that has created *kutumba*; So, *chawa* is our *pukmara* (origin) and *chawa* is our root.

Chawa is our root (*madan* 'Y'). Without *chawa*, there is no way to talk about life, what and how to speak? Therefore, *chawa* is vital while introducing one *Yakhaba* to another *Yakhaba*. *Chawa* is inevitable to make a link with ancestors and to communicate with them. You know, the ancestors cannot hear and recognize you until you recite your *chawa*. Without *chawa*, we (Yamphu) will not be human, we will be like animals. Imagine what will happen if there is no kinship and social relations in the society? How do you communicate with each other? How do you identify yourself? Who is who? Therefore, *chawa* is recited in every lifecycle rituals, *khammang* and *sammangs*. For us, life is not possible without *chawa*. Life cannot be imagined without *chawa*. It is with reference to the *chawa* of each person and each clan/ group, Yamphu establishes relations between the individuals and groups.

(Field note December 14, 2013)

The above narrative by Man Bahadur explicitly shows that *chawa* is origin of Yamphu social relations, identity and history. It seems that *chawa* is the first and foremost essence of Yamphu life and their world view. It is the source of their traditional way of life. It is *chawa* that in the present regulates the Yamphu society and makes up it as a whole. *Chawa* implies the relations between Yamphu themselves and make possible their communication with ancestors. *Chawa* makes them social beings and formulates their cosmic world order. It gives a sense of origin of each person and of groups in the present landscape. According to Godelier, the sense of origin of each person and of group has a direct bearing on the relationship between groups and individuals (1999:169). For this reason, *chawa* has acquired greater value among Yamphu and thus appears to be *sacred*. Through *chawa* ancestors come to act in Yamphu life. Therefore, as Yamphu argue, without *chawa* Yamphu life and society is not possible.

Figure-7: Rudan (Now Hanghong Chawa) in Hedangna. It is believed that Sakma and Furu appeared here. At the Right, a stone pillar erected by the ancestors among the five.

For Yamphu *chawa* is inalienable possession. It is associated with Yamphu origins and thus, governs Yamphu society. It is inalienable because it constitutes an essential part of Yamphu notion of self. It stands as symbol of each clan's identity by showing spiritual attachment with a territory. Most importantly, *chawa* symbolizes their origin in the land. It is the foundation of Yamphu society as it signifies Yamphu way of life. This is why Yamphu believe that each person and group have been created by *chawa*. Every social interaction has been made possible by *chawa*. According to Man Bahadur's remarks on *chawa*, social interaction is impossible i.e. the Yamphu world is impossible without *chawa*. *Chawa* stands as ancestral order to be followed and defines social relations. Since association with a particular *chawa* gives individuals powers and sets them apart from the other members of the society Yamphu acquire a name, land, an identity, and a history from *chawa*. *Chawa* has capacity to produce power through which the society is produced and reproduced. It is said

that in Yamphu culture, while choosing a mate, there must be exclusion of or avoidance of up to seven generations (some say up to ten generations) from father's side and up to five generations from mother's side. However, in practice, I found the clan or *chawa* exogamy rather than this concept of exclusion of generations. For instance, though marriage within clans up to the specified generations is excluded or avoided, marriage is given approval of only if the proposed boy and girl are from different *chawa*. A boy and a girl are not allowed to get married even if they do not fall under the restricted generation group in case they happen to be from the same *chawa*. Man Bahadur said, "Everyone has *chawa*." Before *mangani* (asking for hands of a girl) we must know *chawa* of the girl and boy. If the *chawa* is different, marriage is allowed; but if the boy and girl belong to the same *chawa*, the marriage becomes not possible no matter how many generations depart their families are. It is the *chawa* that connects Yamphu to their ancestors. Therefore, for Yamphu, *chawa* is root or foundation for Yamphu. It signifies their origin, gives meaning to life and also guides and regulates behavior, making it vital. In short, *chawa* is everything for Yamphu.

Thus, among Yamphu, each individual and each clan is associated with a particular *chawa*. Yamphu are obliged to be associated with respective *chawa* because without which their society is impossible, unthinkable and unimaginable. The Yamphu believe that there is not a single Yamphu individual who does not possess a *chawa*. Why an individual is *Yakhaba*? In Yamphu view, it is because he or she belongs to a particular *chawa*. As *chawa* is located in a particular territory, then for any individuals to be associated with a particular *chawa* is to be connected with a particular place. For this reason, *chawa* determines local histories, social relations, kinship, boundaries and local identity of an individual. The following table is the mapping of Yamphu clans, with their respective *chawa* and locality/territory. However, this does not include the list of the whole clan groups and *chawa*.

Table 1: Yamphu Clans and Associated Chawa and Locality

<u>Clan Names</u>	<u>Chawa</u>	<u>Location/territory</u>
Mennawa	Pykkhim Chawa ⁵²	Hedangna
Seppa ⁵³	Nokluṅ Chawa	Seduwa
Khombuwa Tyangsa ⁵⁴	Sunakhari Lambuwa Chawa	Hedangna Near Gadi
Prithya Tyangsa ⁵⁵	Kripanwa Chawa	Hedangna
Mangbakhim	Sovaya Nokluṅ Chawa	Hedangna
Tingyak and Miring ⁵⁶	Phembulawa Chawa	Hedangna
Kesha	Oṅtokwa Chawa	Khonglakhang
	Dumkata Chawa	Dumkatta, near Pilwa
Hanglemba, Chaba, Tinguwa,	Yuma Chawa	Num
Mikchreng		
Chankha ⁵⁷	Khamgowa Chawa	Khogatak
Ala	Chong Chawa	Ala-Uling
Warung	Ambokwa Chawa	Mansingma
	Lingling Chawa	
Rungbisong	Fungling Chawa	Amrang

Field note, 2014

The table above shows that every village and every clan group is associated with their respective *chawa* and locality. For instance, in Hedangna, there are five clan groups who are associated with their respective *chawa*. By such association, the five clan groups are believed to be originally from Hedangna. In discussing the relationship between clan and land among Yolngu of Australia, Morphy (1995:10) writes:

The clan is said to exist in direct continuity with the founding human ancestors of the clan, who were given land by ancestral decree. Ownership of the land entails ownership of the sacra associated with the clan lands.

Over the time, generations have passed and people have moved to other parts of country and India as well, but they keep on *belonging* to their original *chawa* because their root comes to being from the *chawa*. For example, some segments of Yamphu of Hedangna have migrated to Darjeeling, Sikkim and other parts of northeast India years ago, but they always belong to *Hanghong chawa* of Hedangna as they were rooted here.

On the other hand, Seppa clan group is attached to Nokluṅ *chawa*, hence they are believed to be originally from Seduwa. Chankha are associated with Khamgowa *chawa* and

thus they are originally from Khogatak. This argument is supported by the field observation, which shows a clear link between Yamphu settlement and *chawa*. In Hedangna most of the Yamphus are from the five clan groups who are associated with *Hanghong chawa*. We find other Yamphu clans living in Hedangna very rare. On the other hand, in Seduwa we mostly find the descendants of Seppa as they are associated with *Nokluŋ chawa*. This shows that the association between land, ancestral past and Yamphu is reflected through *chawa*.

However, it should be noted that a *chawa* can have two or more clan groups. This is largely because of the migration and absorption of clan groups. In the past, when a brother clan group migrated from their original land to a place which was already inhabited by another brother clan group, they adopted the *chawa* of the host clan group. Over time, their descendants happened to join the *chawa* of the host place. The migrated clan groups also could hold lands under the customary tenure system as if the host clan group held. Since they adopted the *chawa* of the host clan groups, which is called as *thukma chawa*. However, it doesn't mean that they are incorporated within the host clan group. They are incorporated within the *chawa*. Despite their incorporation, they still retain their distinct clan identity and their original *chawa*. For instance, Chankha, Hanglemba, and Kesha were incorporated with *Yuma chawa* of Num. They have become the member of *Yuma chawa* by adoption, not by descent. Therefore, for Kesha and Chankha, *Yuma chawa* is *thukma chawa*, i.e. Kesha's original *chawa* is *Dumkata chawa*. Similarly, the original *chawa* of Chankha is *Khamgowa chawa*. It means, Kesha and Chankha clans were not the first clan groups who first claimed the land of Num, rather their ancestors came there later in Num and joined *Yuma chawa* and hence, *Yuma chawa* is their *thukma chawa*. The first clan group who claimed the land of Num is Hanglemba.⁵⁸ So they claim themselves as *Yuma chawa sakmiyungba* i.e. *Yuma chawa* originally belongs to Hanglemba. From this perspective, Kesha and Chankha are the

second settlers in Num. They cannot claim themselves *Yuma chawa sakmiyoungba*. Nonetheless, this doesn't mean that Kesha and Chankha are treated as outsiders.

Similarly, a *chawa* can have more than one clan groups due to absorption of lineage members. For instance, as can be seen in the table, Hanglemba, Chaba, Tinguwa and Michreng have a common, *Yuma chawa* in Num. The five clan groups are supposed to be *swage dajubhai* ('N'), i.e. they are lineage members by absorption, not by descent. They act in every way as lineage mates. They do not intermarry between *swage dajubhai*. They even observe one day pollution on the death of a member from any of these clan groups.

On the other hand, a clan group can have two *chawas* as well because of clan dispersal. For instance, one branch of Chaba clan group claimed the land of Num while other branch went to Yuba and Bahrabise and claimed the territory. For this reason, Chaba who went to Yuba and Bahrabise associate themselves with Salenchuwa *chawa*. Despite this fact, Chaba of Yuba and Bahrabise admit that originally they came from Num. The case is identical among Lohorung as Hardman (2000:121) writes,

A few *samek* groups have more than one *chawa* because branches of the proto-clan have claimed territory independently. So, whereas all the original four Pangma clans have the same *chawa* and the same *samek*, the *biksik* clan has two *chawa* and one *samek* name, because one branch of the *biksik* stopped and claimed land in Dhupu while the other branch went on to claim territory in *Pangma*.

The notion of *chawa* seems to have common feature among the Lhomi of farther northern areas of Sankhuwasbha who is supposed to be a brother clan group of Yamphu. An informant from Shyaksila told me:

Without *chawa*, how human emerges? Without *chawa* how human or the grass grows? And (pointing to the grass) this grass, this grass, if this grass doesn't have *chawa* under how human grows. Without *thikkepa* (his clan name) *chawa* cannot be produced. Can grass emerge and grow without soil? How *raiti* can be produced without *jimma*? How can this grass grow without soil? *Ammma*, without *Jimma Talukdar*, how *raiti* can be produced? And without soil, how can this grass grow?

(December 13, 2013).

From this remarks on *chawa*, one can easily realize that *chawa* is an internal life force among Lhomi. This concept of *chawa* is very similar to Yamphu. The remark above indicates that *chawa* signifies the origin of human themselves and their root in the locality. How nicely he captures the essence of *chawa* by giving an example of *jimma* and *raiti*. This means to say as the existence of the king is meaningless without people, in the same manner human life is impossible without *chawa*. Another informant from Syakshila told me that "when we use the term *chawa* it means bottom for us."

The findings of the studies on Lohorung and Mewahang, who are the close neighboring brother groups of Yamphu, also suggest that the concept of *chawa* exists among them. In the case of Lohorung Rai, Hardman has well captured the notion of *chawa*: She writes:

Chawa is both the 'first clan watering place' and the territorial name which identifies and binds a clan, identifying the spring to which the clan first spoke when its members claimed that land. It therefore, links the 'person' through identification with the clan to a particular area or territory (2000:121).

As she notes, since *chawa* signifies the first clan ancestor who first occupied the area and claimed the land, today it has been referent point of clan continuity to a particular area or territory. Among Lohorung, performing *chawa* rite, as Hardman argues, is to assert one's claim to the territory attached to a particular *chawa*.

The case is also similar among Mewahang Rai. Gaenzle observes that there are two interrelated concepts *ca:ri* and *ca:wa* among the Mewahang. He explains that *ca:ri puja*, which is also called *dhuli puja* has two parts and writes, "one *puja*, at the central water source (*panero* N, *ca:wa* M), called *panera puja* or *ca:wa puja*, and the subsequent *dhuli puja* (or *ca:ri puja*), which takes place on a field of the incumbent *jimmawal*." (2000:123). Here, the point is that *ca:wa puja* is similar to *chawa puja* of Yamphu. But the *ca:ri puja* is identical to *iksammang/yumang* rite of Yamphu. But in contrast to Yamphu, among Mewahang, *ca:ri* denotes their ancestral land. Gaenzle argues that "*ca:ri* is understood as being a quasi-divine

power, from which derive the fruits of the earth.... though *ca:ri* is a particular, clearly demarcated and named territory, to which concrete political and legal implications attach" (2000:122). Gaenzle highlights the socio-political aspect of *ca:ri*, which is the ancestral stone *sakhewalung*, among Mewhang. We have already noted that conducting *chawa* rite is also legitimating one's right to an area or territory. It was more evident during the *kipat* system because Gaenzle argues that the two concepts "*kipat* and *ca:ri* are still used as synonymously in the territorial sense" (2000:126). Gaenzle notes:

The conducting of the ritual is one of the particular duties and privileges of the local headmen (*jimmawal* or *talukdar*). To be sure, they do not always assume the priestly functions themselves, engaging a *ngo:pa* in those cases where they are not entitled to do so; but they are the ones who serve as "host," and it is at their residence, as pointed out previously, that the main part of the festival takes place. All *raiti* under the authority (*jimma*) of a *jimmawal* or *talukdar* are required to show up on this day at the place of their superior and offer a gift called *perango*" (2000:125)

It is well illustrated from the above ethnographic data that how individuals had to act as a subject, *raiti* to sustain their rights to land. As the headman, a *jimmawal* was to host the ritual and was responsible to feed the attendance. On the other hand, *raiti* had to show up at the ritual with a tributary, *perango*. In other words, the headman used *ca:ri* ritual to legitimize his position in the area. Again Gaenzle writes:

Corresponding to the honor and offerings bestowed on the *ca:ri* is the respect and tributary allegiance shown to the territorial chief. But he in turn is bound to his subjects as a "giver": just as the *ca:ri* nourishes those settled on it, so too the *jimmawal* "nourishes" his *raiti* during *ca:ri puja* (2000:126)

Such rite is a common feature among Yamphu too which is known as *yumang*, *Bali puja* in Nepali, (*ca:ri* in Mewahang) once a year. It is conducted at the land of *jimmawal*. *Yumang* is performed to worship the natural forces, to have better agricultural production thus avoiding drought, frost, heavy rains, soil erosion, insects etc. and prosperity of livestock. It is a communal rite. It is observed during June-July when the monsoon starts and the people will start works for paddy plantation after planting the maize. In this ritual, a pig and seven chickens, millet beer, *akchyata* including ginger are offered to the ancestors. The total budget

of the ritual is shared by each household. In this rite, non-Yamphu household can also take part by sending *bheti* and *akchyata* and *mana chamal* for the ritual.

One of the main ritual acts of this rite is *yawanendam*. In this ritual, a basket covered with a new piece of white cloth is kept hanging at the ritual place through-out the ritual for the purpose of asking *charawa* from the ancestors. This is called *charawa ko?k*. During the ritual, *yadanngba* asks for *charawa* (good harvest) for upcoming season with the ancestor. At the end of the ritual, it is believed that the ancestors have granted good harvest in the basket. The basket of good harvest is taken to an individual house which is known as *yawanendam khim*. The elders select the *yawanendam khim* by making collective decision with the consent of the head of the house.

In the past, like among Mewahang, *jimmawal* was responsible to host *yumang* rite. All subjects under his authority (*jimma*) had to show up in the ritual. It is important to note that unlike today, the basket of good harvest was taken only to the house of the *jimmawal*. This symbolized and legitimized the *jimmawal's* authority over his *raiti*.

4.2. The Chawa Ritual: We Are From Here

The *chawa* rite is similar to *yumang* rite. Like *yumang* rite, in the past, *jimmawal* was responsible for organizing *chawa* rite. But today, it is observed in collective initiation. In every village, Yamphu gather in their respective *chawa*, twice a year. In *chawa* spring, they observe a special ritual: *sañyak* (*ubhauri* 'N') in the month of Baishak (April-May) and *yurak* (*udhauri* 'N') in the month of Ashoj (October-November) and worship their ancestors for good harvest. The former is called *chawa kho?me*, and the latter is known as *chawa tomme*.⁵⁹ For conducting ritual, Yamphu collect money, *akchyata* (uncooked rice kernel), millet beer and *raksi* from each Yamphu household (*ghardhuri* 'N') associated with the *chawa*. However, *bheti* and *akchhyata* are also collected from non-Yamphu households (*riakar*) as

they have settled in the areas but their *bheti* and *akchhyata* are kept separate from that of Yamphu's. During the ritual, *yadangba* calls ancestors and asked for *charawa*. At the end, they have then a communal feast followed by *yawa shri* (dance with drum). The ritual activities such as communal feast, worshiping and praying together installs, to borrow Turner's word (1969:96), a sense of "an area of common living" in each member. Thus, the congregations transform themselves into *de facto* rights holders of the land and resources over the territory.

Yamphu carry over the *charawa* (token of prosperity) which they have asked from the ancestors in a basket (Bamboo basket) to a Yamphu house. At the end of the rite, like in *yumang* rite, collectively the *pasing* (elders) select *yawanendam khim* where they could keep *charawa*. Before selecting the house, they seek the consent of the head of the house. The house is selected on the basis of mutual decision and is called *yawanendam khim*. Before taking the basket of good harvest to *yawanendam khim*, the attendance dance at the ritual place. After that they set off their journey to *yawanendam khim*. A *yadangba* leads the rally by chanting *mindum*. As the *yadangba* keeps on chanting others keep saying, "O hang" (we are happy) till they reach to *yawanendam khim*. When they reach the house, the *yadangba* uncovers the basket and hands it over to the mother. She takes the basket and keeps the *charawa* (good harvest) in store room. After that, elders sing *pellam* for hours with over sipping Tongba to show their happiness for getting the blessings from ancestors for good harvest. Bhim Bahadur Gaurung told me that in the past, the basket of good harvest was carried to the house of *Gaurung* (sub-headman from *jimma*'s clan segment).

The ethnographic description of *chawa* ritual reveals that the ritual keeps alive the subjective awareness to the Yamphu as the descendants of common ancestors to a particular place. The *chawa* is considered to have its memory so as long as Yamphu can ritually reenact the history of that place and its relationships to Yamphu. The above discussion *chawa* ritual

exemplifies that in the past, Yamphu often used to formalize their claim for a place through *chawa* ritual and sacrifice. *Jimmawals* were obliged to conduct *chawa* rite and his *raiti* were in a compulsion to show up in the *chawa* rite. *Jimmawal* as the local headman was responsible to organize the rite and feed the attendance and his *raiti*. On the other hand, every *raiti* under his *jimma* had to show up the rite with *bheti*, *akchyata*, and *koseli* to *jimmawal*. During the ritual, the ancestors are evoked and asked for fertility for the entire village by sacrificing chicken. According to Liffman, sacrifice to the ancestors has a great significance in terms of legitimatizing one's claim for a place. The idea of Liffman about sacrifice is:

In any case, the logic of sacrificial exchange is pervasive: you bring an offering to a divine ancestral dwelling place, whether family shrine, regional temple, cave or mountaintop, and you bring back an embodiment of life for your family and community, whether that embodiment be peyote, water, or some other sacred substance. By doing so, you legitimize our existence in that place (2000:140)

Philippe Sagant's (1996) study of Limbu also shows the significance of sacrifice to maintain relationship between clan and territory. According to him, every year individual Limbu household scarify to Manguenna by which they maintain their relationship with land.

Sagant (1996:122) notes that

Sacrifice to Manguenna maintains the ties between territory of one of the 'Ten Limbus' and the household's membership in a clan.....the sacrificial ritual to another deity, Nahangma, also renews the bonds between a villager and his land and, at the same time, with one of the 'Ten Limbu'.

As *chawa* rite is conducted for prosperity and fertility of the entire village, but it also gives a *sense of belongingness, a sense of common living and a sense of rootedness and identity*. An individual acquires his ancestral history and relations to the land by locating himself with a particular *chawa*. The primordial relationships between Yamphu, divine ancestors and lands are evoked through *chawa* ritual and thus *chawa* becomes the ancestral bases for territorial attachment. For Yamphu, *chawa* is a window through which they see the land as essentially spiritual rather than material and regard it as inseparable part of their

cultural existence and continuity of their way of life. Continuity of the *chawa* rite and the concept of *chawa* itself is thus a key aspect of Yamphu culture.

Chawa stands as an emblem for the maintenance of a continuing association between the Yamphu and the place. In other words, *chawa* stands as a mnemonic to recall the *pellam*, which provide information about history, identity, and life ways for Yamphu. In my interaction with Yamphu elders, they told me that invoking *chawa*, restores emotions, feelings and spiritual bond with the ancestors. By the notion of *chawa*, Yamphu imagine the past of the origin. In so doing, they believe that the ancestors are still present. The ancestors still live with them and act upon them. Their continued presence among Yamphu is attested by the *chawa*. This notion of *chawa* among Yamphu can be analyzed within the Godelier's notion of *social origin of sacred* where real human are replaced with imaginary human (ancestors). In the case of Baruya community, Godelier writes, "the imaginary past of the origin of things is still present because it has become the foundation of the cosmic and social order, an invisible reality, but one which is co-present in the present" (1999:124). According to him, among the Baruya, the continued presence of the supernatural beings (the Sun, the Moon and the ancestors) is attested by their sacred object, the *kwaimatnie*, and by the myths of origin. The past of origin, as he argues, becomes sacred because of its timelessness and eternity. By the notion of the past of origin, Baruya conceive that their ancestors produced the society they live in and reproduce today. Thus, when supernatural beings are imagined in this way, the social becomes sacred. He writes

When a supernatural origin is imagined for the social sphere, the social becomes sacred, and society is legitimized as sacred it stands. Its order must be preserved and reproduced. But when sacred nature of the origin appears, real humans disappear and *imaginary duplicates of these humans appear in their place*, beings in the image of humans but endowed with greater powers and entertaining imaginary relations with the "spirits which give life" to all things, to all the powers which make up the universe (1999:124).

The Godelier's idea of sacred as stated above can be a key concept to analyze how people maintain their relations with ancestors which in turn provides an ideological ground

for any society. A useful framework can be drawn from Godelier's notion of sacred. In his view the sacred as a relation with the ancestors provides any community with spiritual and political ground for an “exercise of sovereignty over a territory, over the resources found and exploited and often the human groups living there” (Godelier, 2009:146). In other words, when an object transforms into sacred, it acquires powers that has a bearing on political, religious and social realms.

In the sacred nature of *chawa*, ancestors as imaginary human appear and real human disappears. Such relationships with ancestors serve as a spiritual ground for Yamphu to legitimize identity and their notion of territoriality- *we emerged from here*. *Chawa* enables Yamphu to communicate with themselves, and with ancestors. Therefore, *chawa* is an integral part of Yamphu - *who they are and how they define themselves*.

In this regard, to be associated with a particular *chawa* is to be able to assert one's right over the land and territory attached to it. This shows that Yamphu use *chawa* to safeguards their land rights and ceremonial status from subsequent arrivals among Yamphu (Yamphu, 2012). As we discussed above, *chawa* is thus special symbol that materializes Yamphu's relations with their ancestors and land. They entertain special relations with their ancestors by means of *chawa*. And it is sure that the land, history, identity and spiritual growth that come from the land will never change. Yamphu view the surrounding area of a *chawa* as the land of ancestors. For non-Yamphu, *chawa* may appear simply a source of water. But for Yamphu, it is valued and revered as sacred ancestral land. Yamphu inherited it from their divine ancestors who established the villages. So, Yamphu are indebted to their ancestors who gave an identity onto the place. For this reason, they often communicate with ancestor to make a link with them. They wish to be blessed with *charawa* (saha 'N'), prosperity, good season and good harvest. By such rituals, Yamphu communicate with their

ancestors, remember their ancestors and dance with great joy in the name of the ancestors who were able to establish Yamphu society in the present territory.

Similarly, in Yamphu, the performance of *chawa* rite not only reinforces the memories of clan members, but also gives historical account of clan continuity in the locality. Thus *chawa* is reference point to territorial attachment as “the boundary delineated by *chawa* is believed to be the place of first occupancy of the ancestor” (Hardman, 2000:125).

Thus, *chawa* also acts as political boundaries. From Rappaport (2005:162) we can learn that “... a knowledge as lodged in the landscape also serves as means of remembering political boundaries: history is a direct means for defending territory.” Therefore, the area Yamphu inhabit today, they think, is inherited from ancestors so they claim the land as their own and thereby, they assert their rights to the places. This is how Yamphu conceptualize and legitimize their rights to the present territory. It should be noted that Yamphu often link and use such memory and history to present concerns of identity and territoriality in the defense of their rights. This is how Yamphu internalize their identity in relation to the land. And this is how Yamphu conceive the present land as “Ancestral Land” which, Yamphu think, is inalienable.

4.3. The Discourse of Chawa: Identifying and Making Themselves

At a point of discussion, Man Bahadur Yamphu from Gairigaoun revealed me that there is an ongoing dispute about the ownership of *Hanghong Chawa* in Hedangna. He explained that such debate often takes place in the time of marriage and other social gatherings. There is a tension between four clan groups regarding who is the original owner of the *Hanghong Chawa*: Kessba-Cha-Mennaba, Yungsaba-Mennaba, Kessaba-Cha-Khakkura and Yungsaba-Khikkura. According to him, these four clan groups have debated over the ownership of the *Hanghong Chawa*. Man Bahadur who himself belongs Kessaba-

Cha-Khakkura finds no reasons for such debate arguing that *Hanghong Chawa* does not belong to any one single clan group. Rather, it is, in his view, the common *chawa* of all clan groups. General public opinion, as I experienced, indicated that both Kessba-Cha-Mennaba and Yungsaba-Mennaba are known as Mennawa; and similarly, Kessaba-Cha-Khakkura and Yungsaba-Khikkura are known as Khakkura.

Yungsaba Mennawa have claimed that the first ancestor who had arrived at the Hedangna was Mennawa, the rest of the ancestors joined him later. Therefore, Yungsaba Mennawa is the *Hanghong Sakmiyoungba* (who established the *chawa* as the first comer). By such argument, Yungsaba Mennawa want to establish his seniority among others. But other three clan groups have claimed that their ancestors were the first to arrive and established the *Hanghong Chawa*. Yamphu pellam doesn't speak of who was the first to come at Hanghong. *Pellam* recounts that when the ancestor of Mennawa who had come from Lhasa was sitting on the branch of tree and looking for *sam?ma-phuru*, he saw other four clan groups coming to toward the same place. It says that then they together founded Hanghong *chawa*.

Such debate may have far-reaching consequences in the existing socio-cultural relationships between them. To debate over a *chawa* is then is to dispute over clan identity, status, and social relations between clan groups. Implicitly, the debate is about “whose ancestor had first arrived to the *Hanghong Chawa*. On the other hand, such debate also influenced marital relationship between these clan groups because Yamphu boys and girls who belong to the same *chawa* are not allowed to establish marital relationship.

4.4. The Chawa: The Origin of Political Space

From the above discussion, it becomes clear that the concept of *chawa* is interlinked with identity, history, and territory. In order to understand politico-religious aspects of *chawa*, the relationships between them need to be carefully assessed. We found that *chawa* is

crucial to maintain their relations with ancestors, spiritual attachment to land and territory and inter-clan relationship among Yamphu. In fact, the concept of *chawa* is crucial among Yamphu because it makes up their society a whole. The arguments above about the *chawa* have shown that the ability of Yamphu individuals to connect themselves to the land emerges by virtue of his association to his *chawa*. Therefore, in order to understand political, religious and social realms of *chawa*, it is necessary to discuss little about *kipat* that Yamphu used to hold till few decades ago under the *kipat* system.

As I have discussed earlier in the introductory chapter, Yamphu were *kipatiya* (*kipat* holders). *Kipat* was one of the land tenure systems in Nepal. In the *kipat* system, according to Regmi, an individual had "a right to exclusive use of a particular piece of land" (1999[1977]:87) not because of the grant of the state but "by virtue of his membership in a particular ethnic group and their location in a particular area" (1999 [1977]: 19). Here, the point in case is that among Yamphu, each person had to be associated with particular *chawa* to have *kipat* land because, as argued above, *chawa* is the element that binds an individual with his clan group and a particular area. Among Yamphu, individuals associated with a particular *chawa* would be associated with clan and then ethnic group and thus to be able to assert his *kipat* right over the land and territory attached to it. Ann Forbes's study of Yamphu *kipat* makes it clear that *kipat* tenure was primarily based on *chawa*. Defining *kipat* for Yamphu, Forbes writes, "as a symbol expressing the past glory of their ancestors, *kipat* was part of a narrative that links the Yamphu Rai to their past and to the lands on which that past has unfold" (Forbes, 1998:39). She writes:

...to be *kipatiya*, an individual had to have a *tsawa* (*chawa*), which meant they had to belong to one of the five springs from which the ancestors first drank on arriving in Hedangna. The tie to the land of their ancestors expressed in the *tsawa* was sanctioned by the *kipat* system, and local categories of identity were reinforced by the national political framework. From Yamphu perspective, to be a *Kipatiya* an individual must be associated with a *tsawa* (water spring where the ancestors first drank on arriving in Hedangna) and thus be an original or an adopted descendant of the ancestors who founded the village on the ridge of Hedangna. Even if an individual is a Kiranti and a *Kipatiya*, without a *tsawa*

in Hedangna, he could not hold *kipat* rights to the lands in the village. Political boundaries designating who could and could not hold land in the village thus coincided with the cultural boundaries delimited by the *tsawa* (Forbes, 1999:134 glossed in the footnote). Here it is interesting to note that those Yamphu who are associated with a particular *chawa* were only eligible to be called *kipatiya*. In the past, *chawa* used to enact a sense of political location. To be a *kipatiya*, an individual must be associated with a particular *chawa*. That is to say, an individual who has no *chawa* is not a Yamphu and he could not hold *kipat*, the ancestral land. Viewed in this way, *chawa* acted as the ground by which a Yamphu obtained rights to *kipat* land. However, during my entire fieldwork I did not find any single Yamphu was not associated with any particular *chawa*.

As we discussed above about the relation between *kipat* and *chawa*, it is logical to assume that before the introduction of *kipat* system, *chawa* used to function as the local authority system for landownership and resource management. An informant told me that, before the *kipat* system, *chawa* used to function as indigenous socio-political unit. Under this system, natural resources, such as land and forests were controlled by clans and distributed in accordance their respective *chawa*. In other words, each clan segment was associated with a particular *chawa* and individual rights to land and territory were secured on the basis of membership with that particular *chawa*. The clan groups used to hold customary ownership and obligation of certain natural resources such as farm land, grazing land, and water sources. Each potential user had complete autonomy to use the resource since no one has the legal authority to exclude others. Households had a common and customary obligation to one another in both social and economic matters. The essence of village life was a structure of both permission and restraint, within which all human endeavors operated. Indeed, one could argue that the very purpose of a village was to serve as a unit of cooperation and so that the welfare of the group would be enhanced. The village served as an economic and social unit of great social significance in regard to the use and management of land and related other natural resources. In a nutshell, the village community enjoyed the effective system of self-governance. Obviously, the leadership was provided by the clan headman (*hangba* ‘Y’) within the localized territory.

Concerned with *kipat* of Limbu, Sagant (1996:123) has noted *thoksing thang sing* tenure system under which land were collectively owned by clan members. He writes:

As the indo-Nepalese population gradually advanced onto 'tribal' lands, they codified this system, progressively modifying it and, like all land-clearing this system, called it *kipat*. The word seems to have appeared in Limbu sometime after the conquest, between 1770 and 1810. And with this term came the legislation (Sagant, 1996:123).

In this sense, we can argue that *kipat* system was only the evolution of this indigenous land tenure system based on a customary and communal basis. *Kipat* system recognized this indigenous authority system which coeval with Yamphu existence in the land. In doing so, the local clan headmen were incorporated into its administrative apparatus and made *subba*, *jimmawal* and Rai. This argument is supported by the study of Limbu *kipat* by Caplan as he writes:

The state absorbed the Limbu headmen into its administrative apparatus and mad them responsible for the collection of taxes and the maintenance of law and order in the settlements. The judicial council of headmen became a court of original jurisdiction, with rights to hear minor civil cases and with authority to impose limited fines. State policy at this stage thus served to crystalize the authority of these traditional leaders within the lineage organization (1967:108).

In similar way, Regmi writes, "Land was therefore held on a customary and communal basis, under what later came to be known as the *Kipat* System" (1999[1977]:89-90). From Sagant's study on Limbu, we know that Kipat system recognized clan territorial divisions between Ten Limbus that existed before the Gorkha conquest. Sagant (1996:123) notes that

The subba's holding, then, was the territory of a clan segment....He was responsible for maintaining the lands owned collectively by the members of the clan segment (*bhayat*), as, perhaps, Limbu headmen once were, when the land was originally being cleared.

It is clear that the clan headmen were recognized as *jimmawal*, *subbas* or Rai under the *kipat* system. Even under the *kipat* system, the relationships between land and Kirati were clearly delineated through a royal decree (Lalmohar). The royal decree stated that land of

kipatiya were inalienable possession. As Forbes (1999:117) has noted that such "rights were embodied in the land tenure system of *kipat* and sealed in a royal decree (Lalmohar)."

Until the cadastral survey of 1992, Yamphu enjoyed their sovereignty over land "that set them apart from other castes and ethnic groups who cultivated land under freehold tenure known as *raikar*"⁶⁰ (Yamphu, 2012:2). However, the cadastral survey conducted in 1992 in formally demolished the *kipat* system and thus *chawa* as local authority system.

Legally, *kipat* system was put to an end with the introduction of Land Act in 2002 B. S. This legal action accelerated the deterioration of village-level social conventions that had previously acted on control resource use. Dissolution of *kipat* can be taken as symbolic obliteration of Yamphu from the landscape because it resulted in removal from its history, memory and representation. The state undermined and destroyed the local system of power and authority to legitimize and authorized the alien power. Consequently, the Yamphu lost their sovereignty over their land and resources. According to Godelier (2003) when a society lost its sovereignty over their resources, it no longer remains society; rather it becomes a local tribal community. These remote powers brought fundamental changes in social relations and structures that hindered to take the necessary, and customary, collective actions to address natural resource shortages. Collectively managed lands were invaded, converted into *raikar* and appropriated by settlers. This process of marginalization and powerlessness resulted in loss of identity. Viewed from this perspective, after the end of the *kipat* system, the Yamphu have ceased to be society, and become a local "tribal community".

Thus, the argument I made above highlights the importance of *chawa* as a *political space*. It is seen that in the past, *chawa* used to act as a *political space* through which Yamphu acquired political identity and territory. Even today, the *mindum* which originates from the *chawa* has been used in the contemporary political discourses of identity through which Yamphu seek political position within federalism.

In sum, *chawa* lies at the center of Yamphu society. *Chawa* enables Yamphu to conceptualize their relationships with place, and ancestors. In other words, it connects Yamphu, their place and their ancestors. In principle, evokes Yamphu's relations with their origins (ancestors) and through which Yamphu make a link with ancestors. Hence, borrowing Godelier's idea of sacred, such social relations with invisible power has provided spiritual basis to establish sovereign power of a human group. This is well illustrated in Yamphu as their special relationships with ancestors have become a philosophical ground to legitimize their identity and to conceptualize their territoriality as ancestral land- "we emerged from here." Given this, *chawa* remains an essential concept through which they conceptualize self, identity and territoriality. Therefore, for Yamphu, *chawa* symbolizes the present land as "Ancestral Land". On this philosophical ground, Yamphu justify their indigenous rights to land and territory and deny the legitimacy of others to the land and resources. There are numbers of groups, whose boundaries are defined, perceived and recognized through their respective *chawa* which cannot be challenged or claimed by others. *Chawa* is inalienable possession of Yamphu, and thus land and territory.

Chapter Five

THE MINDUM AS POWER IN THE PASTENESS: LGITIMIZING THE PRESENT AND CONSTRUCTING THE FUTURE

In this chapter I examine the importance of the political and social dimensions of *mindum* by examining how Yamphu use *mindum* including shamanic versions, local narratives and historical evident to construct the past to restructure the present.

5.1. Yamphu Activism and Mindum: Weaving the Past to Rationalize the Future

In September 2002, some Yamphu activists and students who were studying in Kathmandu decided to establish a national organization of Yamphu - Yamphu Kirat Society - with the aim of preserving, protecting and conserving Yamphu culture, language, and religion.⁶¹ The chairperson of Yamphu Kirat Society explained that since then, Yamphu-Kirat society has been actively engaged in the construction of the past, revitalization of their cultural practices in the new political context. Yamphu, along with indigenous groups attend rallies, seminars and workshops in their own traditional attires; they participate in a number of activities such as organizing food festivals, producing pamphlets and cassettes of songs, celebrations of festivals, feasts and carnivals like *udhauri* and *ubhauri*. Previously, indigenous peoples' culture, dresses, language, and way of life were supposed to be obstacle to development as they were marked as signs of backwardness by modern values.

But in recent times, like other indigenous peoples of Nepal, Yamphu have become eager to know about their past, their traditional/origin, cultural histories and values. Yamphu Kirat Society is engaged in various activities such as development of folk songs and music in audio cassette tapes, even videos, introduction of their cuisine in food festivals and display, sale of handicrafts in different occasions at both local and national levels are some examples

that show they want to trace out their roots and culture. By such activities they want other to understand their identity, and also want to tell the other about who they are.

The reason behind this is that recent emergent movements of indigenous peoples in Nepal. Such movements of indigenous peoples have become successful to establish "the notion of ādivāsi as a powerful, political category of collective rights, including the right to political autonomy" (Rai, 2013:16). Since last two decades, the politics of identity in Nepal have highly become contested issues of public debate. Identity movement are being mobilized for recognition of different group of people on the basis of ethnicity and caste, especially of indigenous peoples with focus on bases like language, religion, and regional identity which "have become increasingly central players on the contemporary political stage, reshaping debates on the definition of the Nepali nation, nationalism and structure of the Nepali state" (Hagen and Lawati, 2013:5). These social movements for justice of indigenous peoples has contributed in raising critical awareness of indigenous peoples' rights enshrined in national and international human rights instrument from grass root level to national level.⁶²

In this movement, indigenous peoples want to revive their age old cultural practices together such empowerment. Hagen is of the view that various indigenous organizations, except some, which have mostly emerged after the restoration of democracy in 1990 seek to promote and protect their cultural practices. He writes:

Cultural politics includes activities through which indigenous nationalities define and promote the cultural practices of their own communities. Guiding these cultural activities is the belief that the indigenous nationalities should reject the culture of high-caste Hindus, which was imposed on them, and revive their own distinct histories, languages, religions and other cultural practices (2010:37).

Hagen's this remarks on ethno politics of Nepal shows that indigenous peoples' "images of past" (Morphy and Morphy, 1984) has served as an ideological ground from which they are making the statement of the present. The local histories and cultural practices which were at the margin of the national historiography has become the major source of

indigenous peoples' consciousness and provided a framework for their cultural politics and future action. Morphy and Morphy take the view that "history becomes the part of present consciousness" in every society (1984:59). Some decades ago, it was assumed that local populations need to abandon their traditional values and aesthetic preferences to become modern and developed. This perspective explicitly underscored that indigenous past and their histories, languages and cultures are the sign of backwardness. But today the time has changed.

Figure-8: The Inauguration Session of Yamphu Conference, September 2012

In the following sections, I have tried to show how Yamphu activists and elders sought to prove themselves as a historically legitimate indigenous group of Upper Arun Valley. I begin with a brief ethnographic data of the conference of Yamphu Kirat Society held in Hedangna which I attended.

In the second week of January 2009, the Yamphu Kirat Society organized a two day Third National Conference in the premises of Himalayan High School, Golechaur, and Hedangna. Yamphu from different districts – Dhankuta, Sunsari, Morang, Ilam and Jhapa participated in the conference. The conference was inaugurated by Purna Prasad Yamphu Rai, the then Constitutional Assembly (CA) member. In the first day, as the first part of the conference, Yamphu participants demonstrated cultural dances with traditional songs. Most of the participants were in their traditional attire. They played traditional musical instruments (cymbals and drums) and danced in circle going round of the *sayar*. Why they dance so enthusiastically? I thought, by dancing and singing songs, Yamphu were creating their life world, an identity of space and existence - the recognition of their distinctive being. Such cultural activities performed in the conference evoked Yamphu consciousness about place and people. I took these cultural activities as the principle of group identity and as a cultural device for the pursuit of group interest to the present.

In the second part of the conference was close session where Yamphu delegates, representatives, elders and activists discussed about socio-political issues that they wanted to get addressed in the New Nepal. They also argued that they live in Yamphuwan and they insisted that the state must recognize Yamphuwan autonomy in New Nepal. One of the strongly argued cases was the incorporation of Yamphu territory into Limbuwan. They enthusiastically expressed their views that Yamphu are of equal status along with other Kirati groups such as Limbu, Khambu and Yakkha. Yamphu elders and activists argued that their traditional territory – Yamphuwan – and culture is under the threat from the Limbuwan movement as the Limbus have claimed that the nine districts of eastern Nepal as their federal unit.⁶³ They refused to be incorporated within Limbuwan for that they are unique. They urged Limbu to respect Yamphu's historical autonomy which is equal of Limbu that was recognized by the common *kipat* category. Yamphu decided to submit their memorandum to the political

parties and CA members for the recognition of Yamphuwan in the Upper Arun Valley as an autonomous region.

At this gathering, while Yamphu were making the claim of Yamphuwan, I frequently posed the following questions: What is the historical ground of Yamphuwan? What are things that bind Yamphu special way to present territory that differs from the way that bind other ethnic and caste groups residing in the same region? Or how Yamphu argue that they are the first settlers in the present territory than others? And in so doing what are the bases for asserting their rights over land (territory) as first settlers? What makes them feel sovereign people, than others, and what legitimizes their claim of the sovereignty over Yamphuwan?

In response to my queries, most of the Yamphu elders often linked Yamphu identity and territoriality through two sources: *pellam* and local narratives (oral histories) and historical evident such as *kipat*. I have analyzed each of them below.

5.2. Power in the Pastness: Legitimatizing the Present

Here I begin with Hardman's remark on Lohorung ancestral past. According to Hardman, for Lohorung, the ancestral past is:

That part of the past is an intrinsic and ever-living part of the present, acting as a constant reminder, an image or consciousness of the knowledge, morality, and correct order of nature and society, which has to be respected and maintained in order to ensure the continued strength of their society (2000:105).

The case is similar to Yamphu. *Mindum* is also the ways of thinking, behaving, obligations, and prohibitions that are obeyed and maintained more or less strictly by Yamphu. However, my argument goes beyond this in line with Godelier's idea that "religious beliefs and rites contribute to establishing the sovereignty of a human group over a territory" (2009:147). How a religion contributes to establish sovereignty, he writes:

First myths and stories that comprise the content of the beliefs usually offer explanation of the origin of the universe and humankind and the relations that, following a course of

imaginary events, were set in place between such components as gods, humans, plants, animals, mountains, and the sea. Religions thus offer a cosmic foundation for a social order. Second, through its collective rites and individual conduct that adheres to its dogmas, a religion strives to associate with human powers those other, more powerful forces whose aid must be sought. As such, religion will play a major or minor role depending on the form of sovereignty a human group exercises over a territory and the peoples living there, and is essential when the sovereignty is embodied and exercised by an individual who is viewed and celebrated as a god living among mortals; that is, when there is a veritable fusion between the political and the religious in the person of the sovereign, as well as in the social relations and institutions of which he or she is the lynchpin and the (apparent) source (Godelier, 2009:147-48).

In contrast to conventional anthropological propositions, Godelier (2009:21) postulates that it is not the "kinship relations and family are the basis of all societies," and not economic relations; rather it is "political-religious relations that are used to define and legitimize the sovereignty of a certain number of human groups over a territory and its resources, which they can then exploit either separately or collectively, that these relations have the capacity to make these groups into a society." In his view, foundation myth as "imaginary representations" lies at the heart of the political-religious relations that legitimize "the power structure and the place of each group" in the social hierarchy by attributing divine origin to some among" (Godelier, 20009:149-50). In Yamphu, their ancestors who established the territory and Yamphu villages come to act as "imaginary representations" because "these imaginary representations became the source and the *raison deter* of real social relations" (ibid.) of Yamphu.

This is evident in the case of Yamphu. *Mindum* and *pellam* are the major sources of explaining ancestral past. By this, Yamphu view that the only humans are their ancestors who founded the villages and governed the territory. For this reason, Yamphu worship the ancestors as gods and experience them as true owners of the land. *Pellam* offers explanation of Yamphu origin and the five Yamphu ancestors who established the villages. Therefore, Yamphu in the present under this ancestral authority, claim to be the sovereign group of the land.

In order to analyze how Yamphu maintain their boundaries, to borrow Godelier's words "political-religious social relations" within themselves and with other Kirati groups, I again would like to cite the excerpt of the *pellam* from chapter four.

he he he inoinoe

eiei the brothers took different routes from Barachhetra;

eieiei the youngest two sons stayed in the Tarai region, Kochya-Mechya;

eiei the eldest son took Dhudha Koshi as his share and followed Dudh Koshi and established Solukhombuwan

ei second son took Tamor as his share and followed Tamor and established Limbuwan;

Yansarumba (the third son-Yamphu) got Arun as his share and followed Arun and established Yamphuwan.

eiei they split from the Barahachhetra;

i eipappo (*ei* lailai 'N')

As they divided, the elder brother (Khombu) followed Dudh Koshi and Sun Koshi and established *Khombuwan*.

Similarly, *Hangsarumba* (Limbu) followed the course of Tamar Koshi and established *Limbuwan*.

Rungsarumba (Yamphu) waited for their sisters and followed the course of Arun and established *Yamphuwan* (present territory).

From the above excerpt of *pellam* it becomes clear that what enables Yamphu to claim the present territory as *Yamphuwan* is their knowledge of the past –oral and written. Here, it is important to note that Yamphu *pellam* signifies political-religious relationship at two levels: on the one hand, the *pellam* unifies all the Kirati groups (Limbu and Khombu) by a common origin and history. On the other hand, it maintains Yamphu's identity and territory within them. Yamphu derive their power from the *pellam* that articulates their historical attachment to the present territory by virtue of being first settlers. They also claim that other groups who reside in Yamphuwan have no such oral history which could prove them that they are the first settlers of this region. The main significance of *pellam* seems to prove that Yamphu are the first settlers of Upper Arun Valley and have become "a central element in the indiginist construction of memory and of the legitimate of their culture" (Schlemmer, 2003/04:126).

Since *pellam* recounts the primordial link between Yamphu and Upper Arun Valley it is crucial for Yamphu identity to legitimize their relations with other Kirati groups such as Limbu and Khombu. In this sense, *pellam* is used to define and legitimize their primordial the sovereignty over the Yamphuwan. The *pellam* demonstrates how the present territory came to be Yamphuwan as their ancestral territory. The ancestral connection to following Arun Valley from Barhachhetra, taking as his own share and establishment of *Hanghong Chawa* in Hedangna, for instance, keeps alive a particular image of the land and territory. This ancestral image has become a focal point in the present day politics to formalize territorial boundaries. Therefore, **the past image is closely related with the present by which Yamphu act on other.**

According to the *pellam*, the present territory belongs to Yamphu because Yamphu ancestors followed the Arun basin route when they reached to this place. I have already discussed that *pellam* recounts the major events of ancestral past; split of four brothers at Barahachhetra and the division of their territory demarcated by the rivers that followed the establishment of their sovereign indigenous territory. This has become the major ideological ground for Yamphu to claim that Yamphu, Limbu and Khombu are historically autonomous groups having their own ancestral territories. Hence, the *pellam* reflects historical continuity of Yamphu to the present landscape. The present territory has ancestral connections and so a source of Yamphu identity and history. Therefore, the past not only acts as mnemonic, but also influences human actions. Hence, chanting *pellam*, Yamphu confirm their existence in their ancestral land by excluding others.

Here the *pellam* delineates the Yamphu's political and historical relationship with other Kirati groups, in turn which, constitutes the basis of their overarching tribal identity. **The above *pellam* clearly brings out the close relationship between Yamphu and the land.** Hence, the present land has become ancestral or historical identity of Yamphu. They view the land and territory as imbued with ancestral past. Morphy has noted that "the ancestral past is

continuously re – created by the sedimenting of past and present experiences and political outcomes on pre – existing logic" (Morphy, 1995:204). Today, the ancestral past of Yamphu is being renewed and transformed through activism for political gain.

The *pellam* provides an account of *political-social relationships* between Limbu, Khumbu and Yamphu. In Yamphu view, Limbu, Khumbu and Yamphu are of equally sovereign groups with their ancestral territory. For instance, when the three ancestral brothers reached at Barahachhetra, they decided to share the river valleys as their *Ansha*. Khumbu got Dudha Koshi- Suna Koshi and followed it; Limbu got Tamor-Kabeli and followed it; and Yamphu got Arun-Barun Koshi and followed it. The *pellam* recalls that later on, the descants of the three ancestors established Limbuwan, Khumbuwan and Yamphuwan respectively. Therefore such oral histories have become a crucial element of Yamphu activism that gives the legitimacy of their culture and historical continuity in the present landscape. Thus, Hardman writes in the case of Lohorung Rai:

Thus, the *pe-lam* gives Lohorung cultural identity and unity. It is one of the key ways of Lohorung maintain their boundaries and express and experience their own distinctiveness in relation to other groups. It sets them particularly apart from Hindu groups and brings them closer to neighboring Kiranti (2000:104).

In this sense, for Yamphu, *pellam* is part of the present, it constantly reminds them an image of the past, or historical consciousness of their ancestral land. This consciousness about of the past has been strength of their society in the present. Thus, *pellam* can be taken as a powerful way to legitimize society to the present boundary in the present. By describing Arun Valley as ancestral territoriality, (*Ansha* ‘N’), Yamphu define the landscape as their first place and hence legitimize their presence in the present. In order for Yamphu to validate their claim as the first settlers in the present landscape, they relate the *pellam* of the origin and migration to the landscape to produce their intrinsic relations with lands and to formalize their political legitimacy in relation to the landscape. The precedence derived from *pellam* as

the past ancestral events that connects Yamphu to the lands of Arun Valley is crucial to the present because as Liffman argues that past as mythological precedence serves as the ideological imprimatur for the legitimacy of land rights (Liffman, 2000).

In anthropological literature, much has been discussed about how indigenous groups rely on their oral histories, myths of the origin and other landmarks to formalize their presence and rights in the territory. In analyzing Waxarika (from western and north-central Mexico) territoriality, for instance, Liffman argues that Waxaritari used chanting and ritual practices to evoke ancestral links for their "territorial identity" (Liffman, 2000:139). According to Liffman, in order for Wixaritari to "claim to a place, they have to describe and relive how their ancestors moved there from an authenticating sacred site" (2000:136). Wixaritari go for a long trek to Warikuta, the sacred desert in San Luis Potosi, "to register one's claim to a piece of land" (ibid.). Friedman writes, "Self-definition doesn't occur in a vacuum, but in a world already defined" (1992b:837). This is exactly, what Friedman argues that "History, then, is very much a mythical construction, in the sense that it is a representation of the past linked to the establishment of an identity in the present" (1992a:195). By extending Sahlin's view on culture, Friedman argues, "history is the organization of the past in term of the present situation (i.e., the construction of the identity), the culture is the organization of the present in terms of the past" which he calls as "mythologization of the past" (1992a:196). In this way, *pellam* becomes the basis of Yamphu self-definition. Yamphu identity is being constructed on the basis of *pellam* that places them in the present territory. Therefore, keeping *pellam* is constructing history.

By now, it becomes clear that Yamphu use *mindum* to assert their rights and legitimizes their claims in the contemporary discourse of identity movement and federalism. However, Yamphuwan territory, except Limbuwan, is neither visible in the histography of Nepal, nor in the contemporary political discourse of identity, ethnicity and federalism. On

the other hand, Limbus have incorporated Yamphu as a sub-group under the territory of Limbuwan.⁶⁴ At one point of my discussion, Khasinimba described to me political attitudes of Limbu and Khombu on Yamphu:

Now, the Limbu and Khombu are absorbing us (Yamphu) within their territory. They both claim us as their sub-group. Do you know? We are about to be incorporated under them. The Limbu and Khombu have been debating on our territory (Arun-Barun).

Khombu claim: *Rai vannejati - Yakkha, Bantawa, Sangbong, Amdong, Hatuwali, Dawali, Athpahariya, Yamphu, Lohorung sabai Majh Kirate Solukhombuwanmero ho* (All those who are called "Rai" - are Majh Kirate – are ours, Solukhombuwan).

Limbu claim: *HamroArunBarunkodholbajaunejatimero ho* (Those who reside in the region of Arun and Barun and who play drums are ours).

In reference to Khasinimba's version, Yamphu history is rich and dates back as far as that of others and Yamphu culture is on an equal footing with the culture and history of other Kirati groups. In this sense, Yamphu are distinct from Limbu and Khambu and are equally genuine indigenous group of Upper Arun Valley. He said:

Limbu's territory is Tamor-Kabeli. Khombu's territory is Dudha Koshi and Sun Koshi. Our territory is Arun and Barun River. Limbu have no *sayer*(Lingo 'N') that is erected while performing Chyabrung (traditional dance of Limbu). They perform Chyabrung without erecting *sayer*. But, Yamphu compulsorily erect *sayer* in the front court yard while performing *kelang* (traditional dance of Yamphu). In the case of Khombu, no need to talk, they have no tradition of such dance let alone *sayer* (November, 2012).

What is the position expressed in such local narratives? Here, we can notice that Yamphu struggle to defend their true essence of past history against any kind encroachment at the local levels. This is how Yamphu define their political-religious relations with Limbu and Khombu in the discourse of identity and territory.

Analysis of *Janajati* movement in Nepal leads us to believe that the ideological basis of their movements and demands are largely based on the construction of the past history in the present. For instance, Martin Gaenzle (2003/04:7) portrays Nepali Janajati movement as "ethnic," "tribal" or regional "making-history" which is based on "the construction of the

pastness as an ethnographic phenomenon." In his view, unlike earlier claim of anthropology, "there is no "people without history" rather the history must be taken "as cultural representations and imaginings of the past, as practices of remembering previous times (ibid.)." I agree with Martin Gaenzle's idea that there are no "people without history," rather they are deprived of writing their own history. The indigenous peoples are deprived of writing their local history in the official history of Nepal. Janak Rai, who studied Dhimal an indigenous group of Tarai, writes:

For Dada and many other Dhimal activists, the 'history of land' and their *Jatia Itihas* (ethnic history) are mutually constituted. But Dhimal collective experiences of losing ground not only led to their political-economic marginality but also silenced their ethnic histories and severely weakened their collective ability to reproduce themselves as 'Dhimal' (2014:326).

The point I want to make here is that for indigenous activists and intellectuals, indigenous past has become an important source of power to restructure the present. They increasingly perceive the assertion of their traditional cultures and the maintenance of traditional ritual and social institutions as an integral part of their political resistance to the loss of their land, resources, and powers of self-determination.

The construction of the past as ethno history in relation to the present has become a central theme among anthropologists. In the case of Paez of southern highland Colombia, Rappaport (1990:180) has effectively argued that "the Paez are not interested in guarding pristine texts, but in incorporating the knowledge they acquire from the world around them into their reflections upon the events of former times, which in turn, are employed from transforming the present." His study of the process by which the Paez revalidate their history has highlighted that the Paez has begun to revalidate their historical past to fight against the marginalization. Rappaport argues that "for them, history is a source of knowledge of how they were subjugated and of information about their legal rights, the beginnings of a new

definition of themselves as a people, a model upon which to base their national structure" (1990:1).

Yamphu activism has well demonstrated this observation. If we analyze the Yamphu activism, we find that their past has been an effective way to express their demands of identity and local autonomy. Their demands find its roots deep in the past. In this sense, for indigenous peoples the interpreting the past has been so important ways for defining and empowering themselves in relation to dominant society because their past incorporates the memory of their subjugation, discrimination and marginalization.

There are numerous examples to support this argument. In discourse of the federal states of Nepal, for instance, indigenous peoples have demanded that federal units must be based on the ethnicity. In other words, as their demands indicate that the federal units must be based on *history and identity*.⁶⁵ For them, the ancestral past that exhibits their continuity from the past to the present is a source of knowledge to make a legitimate claim in the discourse of federalism. Indigenous peoples argue that federal units must be carved out in such a way that would recognize indigenous peoples' territories as autonomous unit since they have historically occupied the territories and have practiced distinct forms of socio-cultural systems. The focus is that while devising federal units, emphasis should be given on historical continuity and identity of indigenous groups. By this it becomes clear that the past has been the ideological background for many indigenous groups to assert their claim for local autonomy as their autonomous regions to be recognized in the federal structures of Nepal. Therefore, I argue that culture and cultural difference have become preeminence basis for the struggles against repressive treatment including claims to territory and rights to cultural separateness.

In so doing, indigenous activists and intellectuals have relied on a range of sources to interpret their past. In the struggle of identity, therefore, the past has been, to borrow

Appudurai's (1981) word, a "scarce resource" for indigenous activists and intellectuals. The source of information regarding their past for indigenous peoples are either the historical and legal documents (such as *kipat*) and books written by scholars (often foreign scholars) or oral traditions, local histories, personal reminiscence (Schlemmer, 2003/04) and their *thak thalo* (traditional territory) within which history is inscribed. However, given that fact that most of the indigenous societies are non-literate in the context of Nepal as in many other countries, the indigenous activists have constructed the past using oral traditions as complement to other sources of historical documents. Schlemmer (2003/04) has noted that Kirant indigenists have used different sources of texts and local histories collected from the elders to express their histories and identity.⁶⁶

This is actually making the past for the present. Schlemmer's analysis of how eastern Kirati groups have utilized the past to defend their territory in the present shows the similar case. In Schlemmer's view Kirat activists and intellectuals, in his own words, Kirant indigenists, are engaged to construct "new past" to "promote their culture and identity" (2003/04:120). In addition to this, Kirati of eastern Nepal often use *kipat* system as historical evident to construct memory and of the legitimacy of their claim as the first settlers of the regions. Hence, the importance of analyzing the political and social dimensions of *mindum* as the Yamphu history is an essential part in this dissertation.

4.5. Uhile Raja Rechhoni Kaning: We were the Then Kings

Caplan has already noted the significance of *kipat* in the political struggles of Limbu. In 1970s, he defined *kipat*, not only as a traditional land tenure system of Limbu but also as "Limbu way of life" and "cultural identity" that becomes "political identity in the context of the struggle to preserve the *kipat* system" (2007 [1970]:174). Concerned to the present context, in analyzing how Kirati are interpreting their past, Schlemmer has noted that

reinvention of the past has "become a corner stone of indigenist speeches, legitimizing all identity claims and their vindicate aspects" (2003/04:127)

It is evident in Yamphu. Interpretation of Kipat sometimes comes to play important role in the discussion of Yamphu identity and territory. In other words, *Kipat* as the past has also provided a framework for Yamphu in the struggle of identity. As I have already discussed in previous chapters that Yamphu were granted *kipat* through royal decree. According to Forbes (1999) *kipat* provided a framework within which the Kirati were able to retain a degree of local autonomy that was unique in Nepal. In the case of Yamphu, she writes:

For Yamphu Rai their past defines who they are politically, culturally and economically, in the present. Much of this history is embedded in *kipat*, *kipat* as a set of rights to the land, *kipat* as a political system, *kipat* as a story about the past. But *kipat* is not defined locally. It is the framework within which the Yamphu Rai fit into the historical and contemporary context of Nepal as a kingdom and as a nation – state (Forbes, 1995:150)

Though *kipat* system was abolished many years ago, its memory is still fresh among the Yamphu. There are some instances in which the claims are derived from the legacy of *kipat*. Khashinimba interpreted the past as follows:

Raja rechhoni uhile kaning. We did not used to eat carcass, dead body of an animal. We needed *chokkho* (pure and clean). We needed *kuleko-gaheko*, *jhariyo-pariyo* (good and fresh) *jagar-bagara* (the wetlands along the river banks), *mahabhir* (metaphorically it means the steep where we find wild honey), *pahauri* (den of a kind of frog that is eaten), *kasturi*, small fish, *and titte machha*. The hills also belong to us. The Tarai also belongs to us. Later *raiti* (non-Yamphu) came and settled (November 2012).

In his view, Shah Kings had recognized the cultural identity of the Kirat through royal decree. Yamphu were granted cultural and economic autonomy by recognizing their customary laws and cultural practices in the *kipat* system. The same is argued by Forbes that "the 1774 Royal Decree sanctioned and legitimized an 'original' claim to the land that is expressed in the *tsawa*" (1995:159).⁶⁷ Without *jimmawal*, other non-Yamphu could not hold the lands. At a point of discussion, an elder Tamang informant from Num gave me the

following oral history about the significance of *jimmawal* during the *kipat* system. He explains:

Long ago, when Num was virgin, Tamang were the first people to settle down in Num. In Num, there were no Rai *jimmawals*. Though the place was not occupied by Rais, Tamang could not claim Num as their ancestral land. In order to settle down there permanently they had to look for Rai *jimmawal*. So, they went to nearby Yamphu village, Yuba in search for Rai *jimmawal*. The Tamang brought a Yamphu who belonged to Chankha clan to Num by carrying on their back. Since then the Yamphu became the *jimmawal* of Num and the Tamang his subject, *raiti*.

However, in a little different version, my uncle Bhim Bahadur shared me that "as I heard from *purkha* when Tamang came to Num, it was uninhabited." He said:

As there (in Num) was no *jimmawal*, Tamang tried their best to worship local deities (*sammangs*), but they could not pacify them. This is because we *jimmawal* are called *jimi* – *bhumi*, and *jimindar*. They even worshiped *ma?ma* (*female* spirit of jungle) in order to live in Num, but the situation remained the same. So, they faced problems and started to suffer from hardships. They had no rituals such as *yumang* for asking *charawa* from the ancestors as they were not Yamphu. So, Tamang carried Chankha a *jimmawal* on their back from Yuba and brought to Num.

This explanation illustrates the intrinsic relationship between land and Yamphu. Such local memory carries meaning in the discourse of who are indigenous and who are not indigenous in Yamphuwan. In Yamphu view, their traditional territory as Yamphuwan was once recognized by *kipat*.

In sum, the use of reconstruction of the past has enable Yamphu to assert their original claims over their territory. By constructing the past in the present political context, *mindum* and *pellam* have provided Yamphu with capacity to create new political space in the struggle of identity. Their beliefs in *mindum* and *pellam* and their relations with ancestors reinforce their arguments for their existence in the present territory. Their past plays a crucial role to define their boundaries and identity in relation to the other Kirati groups. Moreover, it gives them the proof of their existence and legitimizes the political – religious relations with others in the present landscapes.

Contemporary activism attempts to link together the multiple collectivities that make up the Yamphu nation. The past images articulated by Yamphu activists are elaborations upon oral traditions – *mindum* and *pellam* – and historical documents. In what follows, I have examined a *hangji sammang* (worshiping kings) in order to illustrate how Yamphu entertain special relations with ancestral past through a shamanic *mindum*.

4.6. Hangji Sammang: Enactment of Ancestral Sovereignty

In one evening January 2014, Hari Bahadur Yamphu, who lives in Samsing, Num came to my house to invite me to his *hangji sammang* which he was going to conduct in the following day morning. He told me the place where the *sammang* was going to take place. I accepted his invitation. According to him, the reason to conduct the *hangji* was that for six months, he was suffering from a severe problem in his left eye. He came to Kathmandu for the treatment. In Kathmandu, he went to a well-known private hospital for his eye checkup so that he would get well treatment. Despite number of biopsy tests of his eye, the hospital could not rule out exactly what had happened to his eye. Finally, the hospital referred him to go to India for further checkup. He even went to India and eventually the problem was diagnosed. Having the problem diagnosed in India, directly came to the village to do some *sammangs* as he suspected that only hospital treatment may not cure his eye. Therefore, before he will undergo intensive treatment of his eye in Kathmandu, he wanted to do *sammangs*.

As per his invitation, the next day, early in the morning I went to the place where the *sammang* was going to be performed. I was little down wards from my house. By the time I reached, the *phiguyang* (assistant of *yadangba*) had already started building shrines. The atmosphere of the scene was like a picnic. Hari Bahadur's wife's was making leaf plates (*duna 'N'*). His wife's sister was making a fire place. Hari Bahadur and his wife together warned of the children and said that it was dangerous to make noise in the *sammang* place. After a

while, the *phiguyang* signaled *yadangba* that everything was ready. The *yadangba* chanted the following *mindum* that I recorded taking his permission.

Ayo samsabami niwalagi?me. Dhal tarabar hangbaji hening;

Today, you are the king having the shield and sword (Dhal-Tarabar), bring back the *niwa* of this person;

Kashi hangbaji hening; Dajubhai bandu so dokha api?me;

You are the Kashi kings, don't trouble brothers (the sick person's) also;

Ayu, panchbhaladmi, hera dandakundanung hero amminingbe? man bhauyungba;

Today, you are worshiped and honored you in the presence of pancha bhaladmi *hera*, with dandakunda *hero*;

Mindumdangbaji, mecchidnagbaji hening. Dhal Trabardangbaji hening;

You know *mindum*. You are the kings having the shield and sword (Dhal-Tarabar);

Dokh aallabi?me; suriallabi?me; niw aallabi?me. Disana-masana, sai-strusobayu so chembi?me;

Don't give trouble. Don't take away the mind. Don't bring anger. Drive away all the evil spirits, enemies and even wind;

Chade!!

I bow with reverence to you

In the second phase, the *yadangba* chanted:

Chade chade chade, ayu hero, samsaba, kessaba, kasihang, Hangbaji, hanbaji Hanbaji

I bow with reverence to you; today *hero*, you kings, you kings, you kings;

Pagarihangbaji hening, raikar karbar danbaji hening, dhal tarabardanbaji;

You are the kings – *jimmawal*; you holding *karbari*, *raikar*; you are the kings having the shield and sword (Dhal-Tarabar);

Senjidanba, maksidanbajihanbaji, hanbaji;

You are the kings who can see future. You the kings;

Sayalagi?me, kasihangba kessba, kessaba kasihangba;

You are the kashi kings, came from the Kashi. Bring the *saya* of the person;

Karbari raikar dangbaji hening sayalagi?me;

You *karbari*, you *raikar*, bring the *saya*;

Hero ayu tommara bung Ai samsabami;

Hero, today (we are here to worship you) this person with millet beer and flowers;

Dokha allabi?me, surfuri allababe?me, hangbaje, hangbaje, hanbaje;

Don't bring trouble, don't bring anger, you kings, you kings, you kings;

Surifuir allabi?me, sayalagi?me, huklang hembu?me;
Don't bring anger, bring *saya*, make (his) hands and legs work;

Igo samsabami hero, dukhai biraihata lyapi?me, saisampati lyapi?me, saya pu?me;
Drive away worries and sufferings of this person; bring (him) wealth, held the head high (of this person);

Dajubhaibe? so dokha api?me, Hanbaje, Hanbaje, Hanbaje;
Don't give troubles (his) brothers too. You kings, you kings, you kings;

Senjidanba, maksidangji hening, sayalagi?me, niw alabi?me;
You who can see the future, bring *saya*, and *niwa* (of this person);

Huklan so hembikme, yumachawa, chawadangbaji, senjidangba, maksidanbaji hening; duwardangbaji hening,
You *yumachawa*, owner of *chawa*, who can see the future; you who are guarded by *duware* (gate keeper), make (his) hands and legs work;

Karbar raikar danba, manapathi tulo pathi dangbaji hening hero;
You holding *karbari* and *raikar*; you who manage *panapathi tulopathi hero*;

Hangbaje, hanbaje, hanbaje, hanbaje, dokha allabi?me;
You kings, you kings, you kings, don't give trouble;

Noklung chawa, hanghong chawa, thu?ma lesungmi hero;
(We) joined *Noklung chawa*, *hanghong chawa hero*;

Lhasa lasong dangbaji hening hero, dokha allabe?me hening, hangbaje, hanbaje, hanbaje yo;
You the Lhasa kings *hero*, don't give trouble, you kings, you kings, you kings;

Kaning hero, ai, boni but rassea yo, ammi man bhau;
hero, we are here today to worship you by earning for lives;

Dandakundanung hero, pancha bhaladmi kulkutumba yungnung, kaning hero ai hero hangyitingme hero;
(We) offered and feed (meat, millet beer etc.) you in the presence of *panchabhaladmi*, *kutumba* with *dandakunda hero*;

Chawa danba se so dokha allabi?me ayu saya labi?me hero;
(You) the owner of *chawa* (ancestors) also don't give trouble; bring *saya* (to this person) *hero*;

Margadanbaji hening, raikardanbaji, pagari hanbaji hening, hanbaje hanbaje hanbaje;
You *marga dangbaji* (who guide us), who hold *raikar*, owner of *pagari* (jimmawal), you kings, you kings, you kings;

Dokha allabi?me, saya labi?me, niw alabi?me;

Don't give trouble; bring saya and niwa;

Senjidanbaji, makchidanbaji, chawadanba, niwadanba, mindumdanbaji henning, dokha allbi?me;

You who can see the future, owner of *chawa*, source of *niwa*, have knowledge of *mindum*, don't give trouble;

Igo samsabai, mi kessaba samsabami, sayalagi?me, niwa labi?me, desana-masana, huklang hembik?me, hanbaje hanbaje, hanbaje;

Bring the *saya* of this person; bring the *niwa* of this person; drive away evil spirits; make his hands and legs work, you kings, you kings, you kings;

Dhal tarardangbaji henning, bonduke dnagbaji, hening, dhokha alabe?me, hanbaje hanbajeyo, hanbaje;

You are (the kings) having shield and swords and guns; don't bring trouble (to him) you kings, you kings, you kings;

Margadangbaji ,raikar dangnaji, hening, sanjidangbaje, hanbaje hanbajeyo, hanbaje;

You guide us; you holding *raikar*; you can see the future; you kings, you kings you kings;

Igo samsabami, niwa labikme, saya labi?me, yuman chawabi, hero niwa labi?me hero;

Bring his *niwa* and *saya* in the Yuma Chawa *hero*, bring *niwa hero*;

Ayo, pancha bhaladminung ayu hero, dandakundanung, ammi hero man bhau tammara bung nun, hanbaje yo, dokha alabe?me;

Today, (we) worshiped, respect and honor you in the presence of *panchabhaladmi* with *dandakunda*, with millet and flowers, you kings, you kings, you kings;

Hanbaje kalasa fungn ung hero, rupaling nung, sunakong nung hero, niw alabe?me hanbaje, hanbaje, hanbaje;

You kings, you kings, and you kings bring his *niwa* as we honored you with gold cocks and kalasa flowers;

Dokha allabe?me, suriallabe?me, hanbaje, hanbaje, hanbaje;

Don't bring trouble; don't bring anger, you kings, you kings, you kings;

Niw alabi?me hero, manapathi, tulopathi raikar karbardangba hening, hening; dhal tarawar dingbaje;

You, owner of *manapathi*, *tulopathi raikar karbar*; you are protected by gate keepers bring *niwa* of this person;

Chade! Chade! Chade!

I bow my head with reverence to you

The above *mindum* of *hangji sammang* conceptualizes the ancestors as kings who produce locality, history and collective political consciousness by their taxonomies. In this

hangji sammang, yadangba's *mindum* brings the invisible beings to the present and enabled to rule Yamphu society as kings. Yadangba frequently addressed the ancestors as kings and bowed his head with reverence to the ancestors. Most interestingly, he evokes ancestors as *jimmawal* (in the *mindum* pagari) who used to have *raikar* and *karbari*. The *mindum* portrayed the ancestors equipped with shield and sword. In this sense, *mindum* is a political memory.

The relationships between ancestral past and living being evoked in this appear unchanging whatever the socio-political context of the present. Through such shamanic *mindum*, Yamphu seems obliged to keep the name of ancestors because they were the powerful ancestors who ruled the territory as independent kings. The *mindum* demonstrate that Yamphu owe a last debt to the ancestors because they are the source of prosperity, wealth and knowledge. They have power to govern the individual and society. Therefore, such *mindum* gives Yamphu an identity. This identity seems to root within the ancestral order. The *mindum* explains that the ancestors are the true kings and owners of the lands, and they have right to govern the society.

This imaginary relation between ancestors and living being legitimize the foundations of the people, place and ancestors. If we look at the *mindum*, the ancestors are not disappeared. They are living with humans and act upon them, working for or against them. As the *yadangba* was making a relationship with ancestors through *mindum*, the relations were being more sacred and moving into the realm of power. Moreover, it should be noted that the *mindum* also legitimizes the fact that present individuals are the part of the ancestors and hence provide them material and cultural existence into the present landscape. Therefore, the above *mindum* demonstrate what Godelier (1999) says that the relationship with the origin where real human replace with imaginary humans is important for a society in order to produce and reproduce itself. In order to legitimize sovereignty of a human group

over a locality they "require theistic power" or localization of sovereignty (Surtherland, 2003/04:99).

By the *hanji mindum*, *yadangba* connects the present to the past and produces future in relation to the past. In this sense, *mindum* works as what Surtherland has noted in the case of localization of Himalayan history that, "villagers refer to the regional corpus of theistic knowledge so defined as "history" (*itihās*) (2003/04:89). Drawing on ethnographic survey of some thirty-five territorial gods listed for Rohru, India, Surtherland (2003/04:99) suggests us that "local gods are central to Pahari constructions of locality, history and political location, at the heart of which is a mythic transformation of the foreign into the local."

Chapter Six

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This final chapter provides summary of this dissertations. In this chapter, I highlight some potential contribution of this dissertation in anthropological study of oral traditions in relation to understanding history, indigeneity, place and identity of indigenous peoples in Nepal.

6.1. Summary

I studied my own people and culture as I realized that there are so many things unexplored such as *mindum*, history and traditions. Apart from these, most of the cultural practices are in the verge of extinction as the changes in rural life are more intensified and ongoing because of global flows of technologies, communication and ideas. In such context, local histories of any people as cultural construction are "like burning the library before we read the book" (Thornberry, 2002:21).

This dissertation is the culmination of my continuous involvement in the documentation of *mindum* since 2012 to 2014. During this period, I frequently visited my villages other Yamphu villages of Upper Arun Valley where I discussed about local issues and *mindum* with Yamphu elders delightfully for hours. I collected the *mindum* texts collaboratively with community members. The local participants were engaged in accurate transcription of the text jointly. We collectively set the research parameters and guided this study in the field. In this sense, this study is Yamphu research for Yamphu which has operationalized self-determination of Yamphu.

Throughout this dissertation, I have examined Yamphu oral tradition known as *mindum* with its local genres. It has focused on indigenous concept of *mindum*, *pellam* and

local narratives regarding *mindum*. The main research question I wished to explore in this study was to investigate the *mindum* to explore Yamphu notion of self-image, self-consciousness, identity, lands and territoriality. This study also aimed to explore how *mindum* and local histories produce power or capacitate Yamphu to define and legitimize their sovereignty over the territory and its resources. In addition to this, this dissertation aimed to explore how Yamphu, along with other indigenous peoples, interpret the ancestral past to legitimize the present to rationalize the future in New Nepal. In the following three headings, I highlight the major findings of this study.

6.1.1. Mindum: The Origin, World Views and Images

This dissertation shows that *mindum* is a key to the ways for groups to assert their unique identity within images of unity. The analysis of *mindum* in this study shows that *mindum* functions as an instrument to maintain their internal ethnic identity among the diverse Kirati groups, and gives Yamphu a sense of place and indigenous territoriality. This study has found that *mindum* as ideology ultimately determines Yamphu's self-consciousness and self-image. Drawing on Godelier's idea of "imaginary realities," this dissertation has demonstrated that *mindum* is not a so-called myth; rather it is a lived reality, which constitutes essential component of social relations among Yamphu society. For instance, *pellam* recounts the origin of Yamphu, foundation of villages and *chawas* and relations with clan groups (chapter one) gives an overarching "oneness" attaching all individuals to Yamphu territory (Upper Arun Valley). Yamphu inherit their *indigeneity* from distant ancestral past.

This study shows that for Yamphu, *mindum* appears as the self-evident truth that provides them with a visible primordial existence in the lands. It signifies their political-religious and social relationships among themselves and other Kirati groups. Therefore, *mindum* is made up of thought, a world of ideas and images. It is a corpus of knowledge that

ancestors invented both to explain the order or the disorder prevailing in society and explain principles that prescribe how an individual should behave with respect to each other and the world around them.

Such political-religious and social relations encoded in *mindum* are symbolized in social practices, rituals and symbols such as marriage practices, topographic writings *chawa* and other kind of rituals (chapter four). We have noted that Yamphu *pellam* that recounts the primordial history in which Yamphu present themselves in equal footing with Limbu, and Khombu (chapter one). Therefore, *pellam* gives them reference to their territory making boundaries with other Kirati groups.

Throughout the study, we have seen that *pellam* explains the origin of Yamphu that constitutes a system of beliefs explaining their boundaries and relations to the landscape and living humans. Therefore, *mindum* can be viewed as *verbal production of ideology*. This ideology is similar to what Mischa Titiev has observed, "An explanation of the origins of man and the universe, a rationalization of the present, and a statement concerning the future" (1964:283). Often such ideology constituted by *mindum* connects Yamphu to the land and the ancestors. This dissertation has shown that such explanation has often enabled Yamphu to rationalize their claims to their lands and social order.

As *mindum* is the source of Yamphu ideology, it is made up of past images as mental thought upon which the meaning of Yamphu life and cosmic world is organized and interpreted. It is the core component that has shaped Yamphu worldview on which they are to act on and live in. This is exactly what Titiev argues that "observances usually offers the believer a means of establishing and maintaining a secure relationship with what he considers the supernatural sources of his support" (Titiev,1964:284). In order to understand Yamphu worldview, then it is necessary to examine *mindum* as a cultural window that symbolize their experience and codify their beliefs in the present landscape.

6.1.2. Making a Sense of Place, Indigeneity and Territoriality

This dissertation has demonstrated that *mindum* is the key ways through which Yamphu associate themselves to their ancestral lands. The *pellam* of Yamphu migration recounts (chapter three) that at the beginning of the time, land existed but it was empty, nameless, and shapeless. By such explanation, *pellam* signifies that Yamphu ancestors are the first humans who gave names and shape to the virgin lands and appropriated them in different ways. Therefore, the names of the places, rivers and *chawa* are significant to communicate with ancestors and thus to connect place and people. In doing so this study shows that *mindum* is a key concept that enables Yamphu to claim that they are original or first human to inhabit a territory and they are distinct from other. Such conception of Yamphu *mindum* has led me to consider that *mindum* provides us with a useful analytical concept to in order to investigate how sacred relations with powerful imaginary past (ancestors) serves to legitimize the fact that Yamphu are original inhabitant of present territory. Drawing a useful analytical framework on anthropological perspectives on landscape, this dissertation have analyzed that *pellam* is a fundamental way of inscribing ancestral past into the landscape that in turn gives Yamphu a *sense of sovereign people* to claim rights to the land. Throughout this dissertation, we have seen that *pellam* is naming places, ancestral routes and river names that are believed to have travelled by the ancestors (chapter three). Yamphu identity is connected with the places identified in their oral traditions. For those places that are inherently sacred, the landscape itself is understood to be filled with numerous active agents of intelligence and power that have their own agency to create meaning and hence produces a *Yamphu sense of place*.

Chanting *pellam* is not merely remembering the ancestors but most significantly, it evokes an emotional attachment with the landscape. Through *pellam*, Yamphu experience as

if they are living, growing and producing and reproducing their society in their homelands. Following Basso, I have argued that *pellam* as place naming evokes images of ancestors, emotional bond with ancestors. Therefore, when the places are chanted in *pellam*, Yamphu acquire a capacity to evoke sacred relations with ancestors, and thus Yamphu transforms themselves as sovereign people to the land. This is how Yamphu spatialize their identity as *jimi-bhumi* into the present territory and thus, Yamphu and their landscape have become, borrowing Basso's term, "virtually as one" (1984:122).

The study further discussed about ancestral involvement in producing and reproducing society by drawing on Maurice Godelier's perspectives on the *origin of social sacred*. In Yamphu case, it is *mindum* through which Yamphu communicate with primordial ancestors. In so doing, Yamphu maintain special relations with ancestors: a relation that shows ultimate sovereignty of ancestors which in turn provides spiritual basis for Yamphu to exercise sovereign power over the territory.

Godelier (1999) has conceptualized "sacred" as a relationship that living human enjoy with the origin. In such relations, as argued by him, real human are replaced with imaginary human to legitimize their sovereignty over the territory. Following this perspective, *mindum*, is an explanation of the origin of man and the universe, not only it creates supra pan-Kirat identity to which Yamphu feel they belong to, but beyond this, *mindum* provides Yamphu with indigenous concept of lands and sovereign rights over it.

This social relation with ancestors have become a philosophical ground for them to legitimize their identity and to conceptualize their territoriality as ancestral land – "we emerged from here." For example, in the *pellam Hanghong Chawa* situated in Hedangna always gives a Mennawa and other clan groups associated with it a sense of historical continuity in the lands which they claim as their ancestral lands. *Hanghong Chawa* is the prime source of origin of five clan groups (chapter four) and stands as public confirmation of

their existence in Hedangna. In this sense, *chawa* provides them with an ideological framework for the exercise of sovereignty over the territory and resources by the virtue of being first settlers. In sum, *chawa* stands as symbol of each clan's identity by showing spiritual attachment with a territory. Thus, it gives Yamphu a sense of indigeneity, territoriality and belongingness in the present landscape. Given this, *chawa* remains an essential concept through which Yamphu conceptualize their self, identity and territoriality.

On this philosophical ground, Yamphu justify their indigenous rights to land and territory and deny the legitimacy of others to the land and resources. There are numbers of groups, whose boundaries are defined, perceived and recognized through their respective *chawa* which cannot be challenged or claimed by others.

6.1.3. Weaving the Past in the Present to the Future

In this study I have examined that *mindum* is a key way in which the primordial past legitimizes the present and rationalizes Yamphu future. Until a few decades back, the indigenous past: their histories, languages and cultures were considered to be a sign of so-called primitive, savage and backwardness, however, in the recent time, now it has become the ideological basis of the identity of indigenous peoples. This dissertation has demonstrated that Yamphu activism are largely based on the construction of the ancestral past in the present. In this sense, *mindum* as "images of the past" (Morphy and Morphy, 1984) has served as an ideological ground from which they are making the statement of the present. The local histories and cultural practices which were at the margin of the national historiography has become the major source of indigenous peoples' consciousness and provided a framework for their cultural politics and future action. In other words, this dissertation has demonstrated that *mindum* has become in Morphy and Morphy's words "history becomes the part of present consciousness" in Yamphu society (1984:59). Therefore, I argue that oral tradition of

indigenous peoples should not be treated as myth; rather it should be interpreted in relation to the history that shapes social consciousness of people. Such analysis of *mindum* led me to conclude that Yamphu history is inseparable from oral traditions i.e., *mindum* is localization of Yamphu history in the present landscape.

6.2. Conclusions

Oral tradition of a human group such as *mindum* is not myth, or must not only be confined as sacred text rather I argue that it should be treated as oral history, a voice from the past, philosophical texts, social and political narrations. Thus, oral tradition is important for human society to understanding how a group of individuals come together into a whole that adds to each individual an overarching and shared identity.

Central theme of this dissertation is that relationship with supernatural beings such as ancestors of any human community is a crucial factor to examine how they define and legitimize their sovereignty over the territory and its resources, which in turn give them capacity to produce and reproduce their society. For instance, in this study *chawa* as a string of relationship with ancestors and lands offers a valuable analytical framework to examine how Yamphu assert their sovereignty over the territory and its resources as first settler. The notion of *chawa* among Yamphu remains crucial factor to trace relationship with ancestors, historical continuity to a place and thus clan identity.

Oral tradition as the voice from the past plays crucial role to shape social and political strategies in the present. It works as a strategic way of asserting one's rights and existence in the contemporary society. For instance, interpreting *mindum*, Yamphu activism has sought to legitimize their original claims over their territory in the present political context. *Mindum* as the voice of the past has a power to provide Yamphu with capacity to create new political space in the struggle of identity. In this sense, *mindum* plays a crucial role to define Yamphu

boundaries and identity in relation to the other Kirati groups. Moreover, it gives them the proof of their existence and legitimizes the political – religious relations with others in the present landscape.

Analysis of *mindum* as oral tradition in this dissertation has demonstrated that to understand indigenous peoples' aspirations that are at the margin, and indigeneity of a group, it is necessary to investigate the inextricably intertwined relations between people, their land and the ancestral past which comes to act in the present. From this perspective, this study will provide an alternative perspective in the discourse of land, identity, Adivashi Janajati vs non-Janajati and federalism in New Nepal.

¹ Num, Hedangna, Makalu, and Debitar

² **Num:** Tula Maya Yamphu, Bhim Bahadur Gaurung, Kabiraj Gaurung, Arjun Kumar Yamphu, and Harkalal Yamphu. **Hedangna:** Gurungnimba (Prem Bahadur Yamphu), Khasinimba, Man Bahadur Yamphu, Lok Bahadur Yamphu, Krishna Bahadur Yamphu, Rai Man Rai, Suresh Yamphu, Tula Ram's Father, Mangali Maya and Amrita Maya Yamphu. **Uwa:** Mangmani. **Makalu:** Haikam Singh Yamphu, Mohan Singh Yamphu (Kangrejamba), Ram Kumar Yamphu, Talke Rai, and Hunemba. **Debitar:** Dhalke Pappa, Buddhman Yamphu and Mandhoji Yamphu.

³ For instance, the *palam* of Limbu is well known as Limbu folk songs. Limbu say *palam* in Dhan Nacha.

⁴ According to my personal interaction with Bhogi Raj Chamling, the oral tradition of Chamling is known as *muddum*. He told me that the *muddum* can be broadly divided into two categories: first is the *muddum* chanted by a shaman which is known as *Chinta mindum*. Second is the *muddum* chanted by *Rishimi*. *Rishimi* is a person who can sing *Rishiya*. *Rishiya* is similar to Yamphu *pellam*. *Rishimi* mostly chants the origins of the world, first human and ancestral migration to the present place through *Rishiya*. According to him, *Rishiya* is chanted when *chauwa* (offering newly harvested crops rite is performed (April 5, 2014).

⁵ The concept of *lawa* in Yamphu seems very complex. Literally, *lawa* is translated as Sato in Nepali. Sometimes, it is also understood as *shadow* of a person (Nepali). However, I found that the idea of *lawa* lies at the core of *sammangs* (Dewa 'N') than other rituals. According to Khasinimba a priest from Hedangna, a person possesses three types of *lawas*: *hindum lawa*, *chyak lawa* and *ho?p lawa*. They are the key concepts to understand Yamphu notion of an individual and illness. According to him, a person falls sick, when his or her *hindum lawa* leaves body and starts to wander around, different places. It is also called *Sirawa* (Y). In other words, the sick person becomes *hindum lawa* and wanders around. But, the sick person doesn't know whether his *hindum lawa* is wandering or not. He remains unconscious about this. In such case, the sick person may die. Then, a priest's duty is to bring *hindum law* back to the sick person and keep in its place. To this end, especially, *mangba* travels different places in trance to search and retrieve *hindum lawa*. In order to cure the sick, *mangba* needs to retrieve *hindum lawa* and put it in the sick person.

Chyak lawa is connected to the life. A person can live as long as *chyak lawa* stays with him or her. Therefore, a person's *chyak lawa* follows the *hindum lawa*; it persuades *hindum lawa*, and even tries to catch *hindum lawa* if it shows unwillingness to come back. *Chyak lawa* of the sick person try to catch *hindum lawa*

and put it in the sick person. Khasinimba argues that *chayak lawa* even wash *hindum lawa* if it has become more dirty. Here, his concept of dirty seems to be related with roaming nature of *hindum lawa*. As it keeps on travelling on for long time, it becomes dirty, (mayek ‘Y’).

Ho?p lawa is connected with death. *Ho?p lawa* takes away one’s life. If *hindum lawa* keeps on roaming, it is easy for *ho?p lawa* to take one’s life. By this, it seems *lawa* has *niwa* as Hardman also noted the same in Lohourng Rai. She writes, “I was told that *lawa* also have *niwa*.” (2000:188).

⁶ Allen writes: “In fact priests were not the only people to have some knowledge of the tribal rites and traditions, and as I discovered rather late in the day, there existed a certain number of individuals who knew the chants and were able to stand in when priests were not available.” (2012:12)

⁷ Dialogues occur between two parties in different stages in a marriage ceremony and mortuary rite.

⁸ During the liminal period in the death ritual, Yamphu elders usually dialogue with the spirit of *sigayu* (deceased) such as before and in the final purification day. In such dialogues Yamphu elders, on behalf of the deceased family members, call the *sirawa* (soul of the deceased) at home and request to stay for one night before the final ritual. At this point they go at the grave and call him as if the deceased listen to them and do one way dialogue with the *sirawa*.

⁹ Yamphu usually have no concept of God of gods. Literally, *khokwayu + tanbi tube?ε* means in *khokwaluj + grandfather of grandfather*. Then *pappa* (grandfather) and *maama* (grandmother) are the ancestors who created the world and human. Other Kirati people call them as Paruhang and Sumnima.

¹⁰ According to Allen, Thulung creation myth tells: "As to the Primal Lake- long, ago, at the time of the creation, Heaven rained, Earth opened (?). The heavens formed a Lake here below, and into it the Wind swept together fallen leaves. From the moistened mass there sprang up a plant called *wadakhor*, and in the plant Namprangma was created" (2012:24).

¹¹ Gurungnimba did not say where *Saikhuwa and Sadiya* lie.

¹² *Khokwaluj* also known as *kunjani dem*, *madaye dem*, *nagaye dem*, *waksuye dem*, *phokma dem*: the place of origin.

¹³ This version of migration *pellam* was translated from the *pellam* chanted by Gurungnimba

¹⁴ The number of brothers differs person to person. Krishna Bahadur, a *pellamdangba* recite five brothers and two sisters, but Gurungnimba recites four brothers (See Ann, 1995). In Mewahang migration myths, Gaenzle finds four brothers and four sisters who started their journey to northward (Gaenzle, 2000:112).

¹⁵ People use different terms to denote the place of origin such as *Khokwalung*, *Kakchirilung*, and *Kashi*. In Yamphu concept, this place is located down below the earth where first human was created by *khokwayu tanbi tube?ε pappa*.

¹⁶ A place situated near the present day Chatara, in Sunsari District.

¹⁷ A tiny bird called *Chibrike* in Nepali. Since then, this bird has become totem for many Yamphu clans.

¹⁸ A famous pilgrimage located in Sunsari district, near the confluence of the great Seven River. It is also known as *Chatara*.

¹⁹ Who was the second brother? The version of Khasinimba differs from Krishna Bahadur. Khasinimba, a *yadangba* and also *pellamdangba* claims that Yamphu is the second eldest brother and Limbu is the third.

²⁰ However, myths of Lohorung and Mewahang tell that they followed the Arun (See Gaenzle, 2000; and Hardman, 2000). Actually, in my observation, whoever followed, they are the descendants of a common ancestor who followed the Arun.

²¹ King of Nepal

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- ²² When I asked Krishna Bahadur where Chupchikmi dem is situated, he did not give me clear answer, but he guessed, it would be located near Leguawa Khola.
- ²³ Referring to Bed Prakash Upreti's report 1966, Bista writes: "In the old days there were two brothers who were adventurous and enterprising. They had cultivated all the land there was to cultivate in the area in which they lived. So, they set out in search of more land to cultivate, cutting their own way through a thick forest. One brother was leading the other who, being a little slower was eventually left far behind. After a while the one in front entered into a forest of banana trees in this forest grew very fast. The elder brother cut a passage through. But in no time the forest was just as thick and dense behind him as it was in front of him. When the younger brother arrived near the banana forest lost. He could not find the trail his brother had made. He thought that his brother did not want him to follow and therefore had run ahead. Having not much choice the younger brother decided to settle at the spot and gradually began his reclamation whereas the leading brother traversed the forest area and finally reached the hills. In the hills he founded his tribe of Limbu and the younger brother who remained in the forest of the plain of Jhapa is known as the first ancestors of the Dhimals" (2044 [1967]:170).
- ²⁴ Nicolette writes: Khokcilip and Welim had a son called Dukolip. Dukolip had a son named Khar, and Khar's son was Tunilu. Tunilu's son's name was Khop who had four sons – Khambu, Limbu, Menho and Mertup. The myth tells, "These four brothers lived in the place where the Kirati originally came from, at Minaponkha Halkhumbu (Kr), which lies to the south, in the direction of the River Sapta Kosi, at Gaya, not far from Kasi" (2006:45-46). He further writes, "Thus it was the three brothers left the southern plains and went northwards, towards the hills and mountains of Nepal. Hunting and making always for the north, they founded several villages and reached the territories where their descendants still live. Form these four brothers are descended the different groups of the Kirati and the Kulunge Rai themselves, the "offspring" of the firstborn, Khambu" (ibid.)
- ²⁵ Gaenzle writes: Mewahang kept following course of Arun, engaging all the while in hunting. In this way he finally reached the lands of Tibetans (Bhote Muluk N). There he met a Tibetan girl (Bhoteni) and the fell in love with each other and stayed together. One day they stole a *phuru* (a wooden drinking cup) from the Tibetans. The women took it and threw it in the river, where it floated away. "Wherever this *phuru* turns up is our *kipat* shall be," she/he said. They looked and looked for it, until they found it in Hedangna. Immediately they settled down there (2000:278-79). He codes a narrative told him: After (Mewahang) reached the upper Arun Valley and married the Bhoteni there in the land of the Tibetans, he returned and obtained numerous offspring. The Yamphu Rai, the Athpahariya Rai, Lohorung Rai split off, marrying here and there and remaining in the various locations (ibid.)
- ²⁶ Senior people are cared of and taken with great respects among Kirati people. For instance, they are placed first in the row or given first priority while serving anything. In other words, being senior, an individual gets first priority to exercise his or her rights e.g., a younger brother cannot marry to a girl before his brother gets married. If he wants, he is expected to get approval of marriage from his brother.
- ²⁷ The notion of "seven levels down" is found to be symbolically reflected in many Yamphu rituals and *sammangs*. For instance, in mortuary rite, a deceased is buried down deep and covered with stones by making seven layers (Sat Tala 'N'). But in case of female, it must be five levels down grave. In Yamphu Khamang (pitri 'N') two bamboo sticks are placed on the right and left side. The right bamboo is peeled at nine points. On the other hand, the bamboo placed on the left is peeled at seven points. Bhim Bahadur Gaurung told me that in Yamphu cosmic view, there are seven layers down below the earth and nine layers above the earth.
- ²⁸ This version of migration *pellam* was translated from the *pellam* chanted by Gurungnimba
- ²⁹ Here the informants contradict on the matter of how long the ancestors lived in Kharta. For instance, Krishna Bahadur argues that the ancestor who reached to Lhasa lived only for some years. Krishna Bahadur argues that if he and his decedents had stayed for that long period, there would be *chawa*. But Gurungnimba believes that the ancestor lived in Kharta for five to six generations and among them two sons decided to return back.
- ³⁰ According to Gurungnimba, Popti is located above Honghong

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- ³¹ There are different versions regarding what the Yamphu ancestors sailed from Rudan pond. An informant from Shyaksila said that while coming down from Tibet, Thikkepa (ancestor of Yamphu) could not cross Arun River. So, they threw their *Toklang* (stick) into the river. Later, Thikkepa found their Toklang shored up in Rudan and they decided to settle down in Hedangna.
- ³² According to Gurungnimba, Kharta is located in Tibet.
- ³³ It is located in Shyaksila, a village of Hatiya VDC.
- ³⁴ I visited Syaksila in December 2014. Compared to Hedangna, the place is very steep, not good for dwelling and farming.
- ³⁵ Today, people call this place as Mani Danda. However, in *pellam* according to Gurungnimba, this place is called as *nokluṅna dem*, where the two brothers made Mani. The Mani is still can be observed in the site. But the Bhote (Lhomi and Nukpu) people from Hatiya and Hongong and surrounding call this place as *Seppa lamjon*.
- ³⁶ The old name of Hedangna is Rudan. Bhote from Hatiya and other areas still call Hedangna as Rudan and people of Hedangna as Rudanja.
- ³⁷ As the *pellam* tells immediately other four clan brother also came there to claim the land of Hedangna. Here, Gurungnimba was not clear who came first in Hedangna. Most probably, according to him, the four clan groups were already there. Regarding who came first, we get very conflicting information.
- ³⁸ According to Gurungnimba, Sunakhari Lambuwa *chawa* is situated at Gadi.
- ³⁹ However, according to Man Bahadur Yamphu, Pyakkhim Chawa has been claimed by four different clan groups: Cha Mennawa, Yungsaba Mennawa, Khakkura and Khikkura.
- ⁴⁰ These five stone pillars and five small ponds still can be observed in the site.
- ⁴¹ Here it is important that among the five ancestors, the Mennawa who came down from Lhasa is known as ungsaba Mennawa. Therefore, his descendants are known as *ungsaba* Mennawa today. Other four ancestors and their descendants are known as *kessaba* since they did not reach the Lhasa. Similarly, the Sppa who established Noklung *chawa* and Seduwa village is also known as *ungsaba* as he returned back from the Lhasa. The descendants of the two ancestors Mennawa and Seppa are considered Lhasa –gotra, and the descendants whose ancestors did not reach the Lhasa are considered Kashi-gotra. Such category of Lhasa gotra and Kashi gotra seems to be a common feature among the Kirati groups. The term gotra comes from Khas Nepali. For Yamphu, it is *samek*. Generally, the Yamphu who belongs to Lhasa-gotra call themselves as *ungsaba*, *Lashahangba* and the Yamphu who belongs to Kashi-gotra call themselves as *kessaba*, *Kashihangba*.
- ⁴² In Mewahang migration myth, Gaenszle finds that “the Mewahang myths describe an exact emigrational route taken by the ancestors: according to one version they traveled along the eastern side of the Arun as far up as the region north of Hosanna, where married with the Bhatia, and in the end moved along the western side of the valley back south to their present area of settlement” (Gaenszle, 2000:50)
- ⁴³ Non-Bhote people Bhote as dirty and beef eater.
- ⁴⁴ *i ei pappo* (Y) in Nepali *eh ni lai lai* is expression of grief and loneliness because of separation or death of relatives and friends.
- ⁴⁵ *bokhonḍi dem* (Y) expressing like *i ei lahai kasto danda* (biraha danda 'N')
- ⁴⁶ *sebukya dem* (Y): a place where a grass plant, *Thysanolaena maxima* whose flowers are used as broom (Amliso 'Y') grow
- ⁴⁷ *Baṅlaliṅkhaba* (Y): a place where we find White Rhododendron
- ⁴⁸ *Gaikharka* (Y): Near Deurali, below Gaikharka, above Mangane

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- ⁴⁹ *larewaba bororathiya gongudem* (Y): Below Barathe, above Gaikharka
- ⁵⁰ *Tokcikya dem* (Y): Above Barathe, near Barun River
- ⁵¹ A special type of arrow used only to make run away not for killing.
- ⁵² However, according to Man Bahadur Yamphu, Pyakkhim Chawa has been claimed by four different clan groups: Cha Mennawa, Yungsaba Mennawa, Khakkura and Khikkura.
- ⁵³ There are five types of Seppa: Pau Seppa, Rangbisong Seppa, Yung Seppa, Thukmana Seppa, Langbisong Speppa, Ketra Seppa and Khaisong Seppa
- ⁵⁴ The ancestor of Khombuwa Tyangsa is believed to have come from Hanrok, Khombuwan.
- ⁵⁵ The ancestor of Prithya Tyangsa is believed to have come from Pilwa.
- ⁵⁶ Tingyak and Miring came to Hedangna by following Ikuwa Khola. Gurungnimba described that Tingyak and Miring were originally descendants of Limbu, but now they have become Yamphu. When they were returning from Pakkang, the origin of Tamor, mistakenly they followed Ikuwa and arrived in Arun Hongma
- ⁵⁷ There are five types of chankha: Tumyahang chankha, o?khriwahang chankha, Sakhure chankha, khayasong chankha, rikwahang chankha.
- ⁵⁸ However, there exists ambiguity because along with Hanglemba, the Yuma *chawa* is also claimed by Chankha.
- ⁵⁹ But, nowadays, Yamphu only observe *ubhauri chawa* rite.
- ⁶⁰ The land under which was the authority of the government
- ⁶¹ According to the constitution (2060) of YamphuKirat Society, the main objectives of the Society are: to preserve and promote the language, script, culture, literature, arts, history of the Yamphu; to preserve and promote the traditional knowledge, skill, technology and special knowledge of the Yamphu and to make efforts in its vocational use; to advocating for the safeguard, promotion and protection of the rights of Yamphu as indigenous peoples; organizing campaigns regularly on issues affecting indigenous peoples in Nepal within the community; encouraging community reflection and action to ensure their right based access and participation in decision making level for the future of the indigenous peoples through different interactive programs; developing research program and systematic documentation of various issues and aspects of indigenous peoples' lives and to publish and disseminate them and others.
- ⁶² In many instances, indigenous peoples have looked to the International Labour Organization Convention 169 on Indigenous and Tribal Peoples (ILO 169) and United Nations Declaring on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP) as a basis for supporting their claims. ILO 169 is currently one of the only international instruments in force- in the countries having ratified the Convention- that deals explicitly with the rights of indigenous peoples to natural resources pertaining to their lands. Thus, at the moment, it provides one of the few positive law bases for defending indigenous land and resource rights. For Nepal's indigenous peoples, in particular, it has been viewed as an important legal tool. It is for this reason that this article will focus on ILO 169 as a source of rights, obligations and potential recourses available to Bolivia's indigenous peoples in the face of the incursion of oil enterprises into their territories.
- ⁶³ See the constitution of Limbuwan Sanghiya Parisad, 2062
- ⁶⁴ Limbuwan based political parties that are demanding Limbuwan Autonomous State, have incorporated Yamphu their territory as a sub-category within the Limnbuwan.
- ⁶⁵ The agreement no. 3 states that "By keeping Nepal's sovereignty, national unity and integrity intact, provision shall be made for scientific autonomous federal republic states by the Constituent Assembly based on the

historical backgrounds, languages, geographical regions and economic resources and viability of Limbuwan, Khambuwan, Tamangsaling, Tharuhat as well as other indigenous nationalities....." (The agreement between the Government Talks Team comprising the Seven Parties and the Federal Republic National Front, Nepal on 2 March 2008).

⁶⁶ According to Schlemmer, as the given lack of documented history, Kirant intellectuals have used "a mix of sources, like traditional myths collected among elders of the community (which can be considered as one kind of 'local history'), and other materials, such as researchers' books, classical Sanskrit literature (such as the *Mahabharata*), as well as royal chronicles" (2003/04:120).

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⁶⁷Forbes further writes: Unlike *raikar*, only people with a particular ethnic and geographic identity can hold *kipat* rights to the land. *Kipat*, as an official category within the national government, politicalized cultural and geographic ties. The web of cultural, political, economic, and geographic relations expressed and re – enacted in *kipat* reinforced a conception of Yamphu identity that is different from that of *raikar* (1995:159-60)